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Deliverable D5.3

Use Cases final implementation and trials results for CTE domain

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Description</i>		
<i>5G</i>	Fifth Generation of mobile communications	<i>MIMO</i>	Multiple Input Multiple Output
<i>6G</i>	Sixth Generation of mobile communications	<i>ML</i>	Machine Learning
<i>AI</i>	Artificial Intelligence	<i>MQTT</i>	MQ Telemetry Transport
<i>AIA</i>	Athens International Airport	<i>MR</i>	Mixed Reality
<i>AOIs</i>	Areas of Interest	<i>Ms</i>	Millisecond
<i>API</i>	Application Programming Interface	<i>NPN</i>	Non-Public Network
<i>AR</i>	Augmented Reality	<i>NAT</i>	Network Address Translation
<i>B5G</i>	Beyond 5G mobile network	<i>NR</i>	New Radio
<i>BYOG</i>	Bring Your Own Game	<i>NR-DC</i>	New Radio Dual Connectivity
<i>CDN</i>	Content Delivery Network	<i>NSA</i>	Non-Standalone Architecture
<i>COTO</i>	Comune di Torino	<i>OAI</i>	Open Air Interface
<i>CPE</i>	Customer-Premises Equipment	<i>OWD</i>	One-Way Delay
<i>CROSEU</i>	Crossmedia Europe	<i>PoI</i>	Point of Interest
<i>CTE</i>	Culture, Tourism and Entertainment	<i>RAN</i>	Radio Access Network
<i>DL</i>	Downlink	<i>ROS</i>	Robot Operating System
<i>ERC</i>	Ericsson España SA	<i>REST</i>	Representational State Transfer
<i>FR2</i>	Frequency Range 2	<i>RTT</i>	Round-Trip Time
<i>FOV</i>	Field of View	<i>SA</i>	Standalone Architecture
<i>FWA</i>	Fixed Wireless Access	<i>SIM</i>	Subscriber Identity Module
<i>GAM</i>	Galleria d'Arte Moderna	<i>SLAM</i>	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
<i>GDPR</i>	General Data Protection Regulation	<i>SRT</i>	Secure Reliable Transport
<i>gNB</i>	gNodeB	<i>TCP</i>	Transmission Control Protocol
<i>GPU</i>	Graphics Processing Unit	<i>TDD</i>	Time-Division Duplex
<i>GUI</i>	Graphical User Interface	<i>TID</i>	Telefónica Innovación Digital
<i>IMEC</i>	Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre	<i>TIM</i>	Telecom Italia SPA
<i>IP</i>	Internet Protocol	<i>TOS</i>	Terminal Operations Supervisors
<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicator	<i>UC</i>	Use Case
<i>KVI</i>	Key Value Indicator	<i>UE</i>	User Equipment
<i>LBG</i>	Location Based Game	<i>UI</i>	User Interface
<i>MAUTO</i>	National Automobile Museum of Turin	<i>VM</i>	Virtual Machine
<i>MBPS</i>	Megabits per Second	<i>VPN</i>	Virtual Private Network
<i>MMw</i>	Millimeter Wave	<i>VR</i>	Virtual Reality
		<i>WebGL</i>	Web Graphics Library
		<i>WP</i>	World Package
		<i>Wi-Fi</i>	Wireless Fidelity
		<i>XR</i>	Extended Reality
		<i>YBVR</i>	Yerba Buena VR Europe S.L.
		<i>ZMQ</i>	ZeroMQ

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Executive Summary

This document, D5.3, presents the final implementation and trial results for the four core Use Cases (UCs) in the Culture, Tourism & Entertainment (CTE) domain under the TrialsNet project. Building on progress reported in earlier deliverables D5.1 [1] and D.2 [2], it provides a comprehensive overview of the final implementation steps, the execution of large-scale trials, and the results obtained. The document covers the integration activities and system-level validations carried out during the last phase of the project, as well as the measurement of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs) according to the evaluation methodology previously established. Each UC was deployed and tested in realistic operational environments, including sports venues, airports, cultural heritage sites, and museums, to validate performance and user experience. The trials confirmed the technical feasibility and demonstrated the added value of 5G/B5G (Fifth Generation of mobile communications)/ (Beyond 5G mobile network) technologies for enhancing cultural, tourism, and entertainment services, providing detailed evidence of their impact and benefits.

In the following paragraphs, an overview of each use case, detailing their final application designs, the development activities undertaken, and the execution of pre-trials and main trials is provided.

Use Case 10 “Immersive Fan Engagement” (Madrid): This use case explores the potential of enhanced immersive video experience for fans during sports events, utilizing fixed fiber connections and a cloud-based streaming distribution platform. The UC covers two scenarios: In-Venue and At-Home experiences. In the In-Venue scenario, fans can access real-time multi-angle streams on their mobile devices during the live event. In the At-Home scenario, fans can use VR headsets to enjoy a fully immersive experience, bringing the game to life in a engaging and interactive way. In terms of development activities, Yerba Buena VR Europe S.L. (YBVR) collaborated with ERC (Ericsson España SA) to conduct multiple pre-trial tests at the 5Tonic laboratory in Madrid, and further trials to validate both 180° and 360° cameras and new streaming protocols. The final applications were deployed during a basketball match at Movistar Arena on March 2025, where comprehensive testing of 5G network capabilities was carried out to evaluate performance under real-world conditions. The intent behind these efforts was to ensure robust low-latency connections, and optimized delivery for immersive sports viewing experiences, illustrating UC10's commitment to advancing digital fan engagement.

Use Case 11 “Service robots for enhanced passengers’ experience” (Athens): This use case utilizes AI (Artificial Intelligence) and 5G/B5G technology to create an intelligent airport ecosystem aimed at optimizing passenger flows and improving travel experiences. By integrating data from various sensors, cameras, and algorithms, the system reduces waiting times and congestion through real-time anomaly detection. Autonomous service robots play a pivotal role by assisting passengers, balancing check-in demands, guiding them, and offering personalized recommendations. Development activities focused on the enhancements to the wi.MOVE platform, including permissions management, integration with various devices, and updates to existing functionalities. Key features implemented include AI driven analytics for real-time monitoring and assistance. The trial was successfully conducted on April 2025, at Athens International Airport (AIA), where humanoid robots and advanced monitoring systems were tested in real-world conditions to assess their performance. Development has progressed on the main video analysis pipeline, data processing components, and the integration of smart service robots. The trial confirmed the effectiveness of the system in managing passenger flows and aiding, showcasing an advancement towards a smart airport environment utilizing state-of-the-art technology.

Use Case 12 “City Parks in Metaverse” (Turin): The use case addresses the enhancement of visitor experiences at cultural and historical sites through B5G/6G (Sixth Generation of mobile communications) technologies by integrating edutainment and gamification via a multi-phase Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) fantasy game. Taking place in Valentino Park, players form teams of four to collect virtual artifacts by overcoming challenges at historical locations, ultimately leading to a final VR battle against an evil wizard, which, once completed, grants access to a VR tour. Development efforts have culminated in the completion of both AR and VR experiences, with robust resilience through integrated gameplay and scoring systems designed to reflect teams' performances. The trial was executed on November 2024, involving 130 students from a secondary school who experienced the dual gaming environment, this included pre-trial tests and adjustments due to venue changes, successfully demonstrating the engaging potential of technology to enrich cultural visits. Overall, UC12 provides a scalable model for edutainment applications in urban heritage settings, allowing for broader outreach and immersive opportunities while laying the groundwork for potential commercialization.

Use Case 13 “Extended XR Museum Experience” (Turin): this use case covered four municipal museums, developing experiences around relevant artworks. The system incorporated AI virtual guides based on historical figures. Visitors progressed through three phases: pre-show introductions, AR exploration of artworks, and VR experiences in dedicated spaces and additional features. The implementation utilized direct 5G connections for tablets and smartphones, while headsets and laptops connected via 5G-to-Wi-Fi (Wireless Fidelity) Customer-Premises Equipment (CPE) units. The trials, executed in March 2025 across the selected museums, involved the participation of over 200 visitors, mainly students, engaging with both the technology and cultural content, validating the application’s relevance and effectiveness. Further work has been carried out to improve the apps and explore future potential exploitations. Based on measurements during the trial, the current public 5G NSA (Non-Standalone Architecture) network could handle a limited number of concurrent users. The project holds promise for adopting new educational methods that combine immersive technology with cultural heritage, suggesting a transformative approach to museum experiences for various audiences.

Use Case 13 “Extended XR Museum Experience” (Athens): this use case developed applications for the Parthenon and Corinth Canal Museum using a cloud-based architecture with analytics and monitoring capabilities. The applications offered content in English and Greek with AI-generated speech, incorporated plane detection technology for AR functionality, and included QR code scanning for content access. VR experiences featured multiplayer capabilities and 360° panoramic views. The system architecture comprised cloud servers for content delivery, end-user interfaces for content retrieval, and analytics components for performance monitoring. Content was organized into smaller packages to improve delivery efficiency over the 5G network. The trials conducted in March 2025 validated the applications' functionalities and network performance, facilitating real-time monitoring via the public 5G network.

Overall, all the trials met the expected requirements, with only a few exceptions related to deployment challenges. Based on the trials results, the deliverable also provides deployment considerations, highlighting practical challenges and technical requirements encountered across the UCs in order to identify how next generation 6G technologies are essential to overcome existing limitations and could enable a full commercial deployment of the proposed solutions.

Finally, the deliverable introduces 8 additional UC and related trials that have been onboarded through the Open Call sub-projects, in 4 additional sites. The selected sub-projects align with TrialsNet’s goals of fostering innovation in B5G/6G applications. A short summary of the use case description and trial of each sub-project is given below.

Football Stadium (Petah Tikva): The sub-project enhances fan experiences at Israel's Petach Tikva Stadium through advanced 5G services including live statistics, instant video replays, and in-app food/merchandise ordering. Trials during league matches engaged significant fan participation, collected real-time performance data, and developed a digital twin for precise 5G equipment location mapping, successfully validating simultaneous multi-user connectivity and technical capabilities.

Turin5Games (Turin): The sub-project develops a Cloud Gaming platform that allows users to access an extensive game library through low-latency connection. The platform facilitates a Bring Your Own Game (BYOG) service model that enables users to integrate their existing games into the 5G environment, providing flexibility and convenience for players in various settings, including crowded venues. The system processed over 800 sessions with more than 250 users via 5G NSA commercial broadband, providing valuable insights into network performance limits and cloud gaming service delivery.

Torino4U (Turin): The sub-project is designed to enrich the experience of cultural tourists by utilising a mobile application, an enhancement of the Stendhapp platform developed for both Android and iOS systems, that leverages 5G technology and extended reality for engaging exploration of the city. The app allows users to interact with eight geolocated 3D objects and view five historic reconstruction videos at various city locations. Over 350 users generated more than 40,000 transactions. Torino4U reflects a concerted effort to blend technology with cultural heritage, facilitating meaningful and immersive experiences for visitors.

6Gvision (Antwerp): The sub-project enhances indoor 5G coverage and addresses line-of-sight blockages through vision-aided techniques and Open RAN (Radio Access Network) architecture at Interuniversity Micro-electronics Centre (IMEC) facilities in Antwerp. The project developed a web-based platform for real-time

monitoring and configuration of Frequency Range 2 (FR2) mmWave capabilities, enabling effective experimentation with indoor scenarios and network performance measurement.

DREAMPARK (Turin): The sub-project creates a gamified experience in Turin's Valentino Park, allowing remote users to explore cultural landmarks through a narrative-driven game adventure. This edutainment initiative is designed to engage participants both emotionally and cognitively. Using the Reflectis platform for real-time 3D rendering and social interaction, the project engaged multiple focus groups of more than 40 participants each in various locations.

5GAUGMENTED (Naples): The sub-project enhances visitor experiences at Naples' UNESCO World Heritage Site through an AR tour accessible via smartphone QR codes. The tour links to a web app that guides users through eleven selected locations equipped with strong 5G connectivity. The project leverages real-time content streaming through a WebGL-based (Web Graphics Library) rendering engine, ensuring an efficient and scalable performance. Trials included approximately 1,500 users over 73 days and validated the critical role of 5G performance in seamless AR delivery.

Remember Ascari (Turin): The sub-project utilizes 5G-powered immersive technologies to explore Formula One driver Alberto Ascari's legacy through a multiplayer mixed reality experience at Turin's National Automobile Museum. The Meta Quest 3-based application delivers a 4-person immersive journey combining AR, VR, and multimedia elements, supported by a dedicated private 5G network for ultra-low latency connectivity. Trials with over 105 users demonstrated strong emotional impact and technical reliability.

Augmented Reality (Bucharest): The sub-project enhances outdoor cultural site experiences through an Android application deployed at POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest. Utilizing Google's ARCore with object recognition and real-time visual overlays, users can engage with three designated landmarks using AR and real-time object detection to interact with their surroundings. The trials engaged 66 participants across designated landmarks, validating AR effectiveness across various demographics.

This comprehensive report aims to provide stakeholders with a clear understanding of the project's outcomes, the performance of implemented technologies, and the potential impact on future developments in the field of smart networks for culture, tourism, and entertainment. The CTE use cases and related trials, together with their diverse implementations across sports, gaming, cultural tourism, and heritage preservation environments, demonstrate the scalability and technical viability of B5G/6G technologies for immersive applications, providing a robust framework for enhancing user experiences and establishing a foundation for future 6G design, development, and application to the CTE domain.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the final deliverable of Work Package 5 (WP), providing a comprehensive overview of the final implementation and trial results for the UCs in the CTE domain of the TrialsNet project as well as the ones that have been onboarded through the Open Call sub-projects. It builds upon the progress reported in earlier deliverables 5.1 [1] and 5.2 [2], detailing the advancements made in deploying 5G/B5G technologies to enhance user experiences across various cultural and entertainment settings. The main sections of this document are structured as follows.

Section 2 presents the final implementation details for each core UC (UC10-UC13), including updates on development activities and comprehensive overviews of the final applications. It covers the architecture, modules, functionalities, and interfaces of each UC, highlighting the progress made since the previous deliverable.

Section 3 provides in-depth information on the trials performed in the context of the different core UC. It includes detailed descriptions of pre-trial activities, trial setups, and the execution of trials. This section reports on the measured Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIIs), offering insights into the performance and user experience of the implemented solutions.

Section 4 offers considerations on the deployment of UCs, reflecting on the challenges encountered and lessons learned during the implementation and trial phases. It provides valuable insights for future deployments of similar technologies in cultural and entertainment contexts.

Section 5 reports on additional UCs and related trials results from the Open Call sub-projects, expanding the scope of the project and demonstrating its potential for fostering innovation in B5G/6G applications.

Finally, Section 6 concludes the document by summarizing the key findings and outcomes of the trials, reflecting on the project's achievements and its contributions to advancing 5G and beyond technologies in the CTE domain.

Due to the extended data measurements available from both pre-trial activities and the final trials, the pre-trial results of use cases have been reported in Annex A to Annex E of this document. In addition, regarding KVIIs, the complete questionnaires used in the UCs are reported in Annex F. Finally, Annex G provides details on the methodology used for the KVIIs evaluation for UC10.

2 Use Cases final implementation

2.1 UC10: Immersive Fan Engagement

UC10 explores 5G and beyond 5G (B5G) limits supporting immersive fan application (with a basketball sports match) already deployed by YBVR (Yerba Buena VR Europe S.L.). The current setup uses a fixed network infrastructure with fiber connections linking cameras, production computers, and the cloud-based streaming distribution platform. For the UC10 trials, YBVR has defined two scenarios to evaluate the 5G network as a replacement for the fiber connections:

- **In-Venue scenario:** Users receive multi-screen information on mobile smartphones, allowing them to select different TV feeds in real-time. This scenario requires low latency, precise geolocation, and optimized downlink to serve video feeds to numerous smartphones within the venue.
- **At-Home scenario:** Users access the sports match via VR headsets, with cameras positioned courtside providing a seamless immersive viewing experience.

2.1.1 Update on development activities

YBVR and ERC conducted pre-trial activities at the 5TONIC laboratory in Leganés, Madrid, to validate the latest 5G Release-17 capabilities and the performance of the production equipment. An initial pre-test in December 2023 used Wi-Fi to benchmark the system, but subsequent trials leveraged 5G with two key phases: in July 2024, tests focused on Rel-17 CPE devices and 180° cameras, where YBVR introduced the SRT (Secure Reliable Transport) protocol to overcome limitations in 360° camera support and ensure low-latency, reliable streaming; in October and December 2024, further trials validated the 360° camera with SRT and incorporated four mmWave CPE prototypes based on Qualcomm’s SDX75 architecture. The setup covered both In-Venue (multi-camera capture, on-site production, 5G uplink/downlink via SRT) and At-Home scenarios (360°/180° capture, edge/cloud production, SRT streaming over fibre/5G, Content Delivery Network (CDN) scaling).

2.1.2 Final application overview

Figure 1 illustrates the final application for the trial of UC10. For the In-Venue scenario, eight HD cameras from the TV production team were situated around the basketball court for seamless coverage. These cameras transmitted video via SRT to the YBVR production set. From there, the content was streamed to the YBVR media server platform in the cloud using a 5G uplink through a dedicated CPE. The same 5G CPE also supported a downlink stream, connecting to Access Point to the 5G CPE that provided Wi-Fi to mobile devices for real-time viewing.

Figure 1. UC10 Final application design.

For At-Home scenario, two 180° cameras and one 360° camera that were strategically placed on the courtside and each basketball ring for optimal view and were connected to three separate CPEs for 5G uplink. These three CPEs, in turn, connected to 5G uplink used in the in-venue setup. The unified video streams from the cameras were transmitted to a production set located at the network edge, where an ingest server stitched the footage from all three cameras into a cohesive view. The stitched video was then streamed via fiber or Ethernet uplink to the YBVR platform in the cloud. Finally, the cloud platform facilitated downlink streaming via Wi-Fi to VR headsets, delivering an immersive viewing experience to users at home.

2.2 UC11: Service Robots for Enhanced Passengers' Experience

UC11 leverages AI and 5G/B5G technology to create a smart airport ecosystem that optimizes passenger flows and enhances the travel experience. By integrating data from cameras, sensors, and AI-powered algorithms, it reduces waiting times at check-in counters and prevents congestion through real-time anomaly detection and intervention alerts for Terminal Operations Supervisors (TOS). Smart service robots, enabled by B5G, inspect passenger flows, provide personalized assistance, and balance counter demand. They also guide passengers to gates, offer retail recommendations, and inspect infrastructure, improving efficiency and overall service quality.

2.2.1 Update on development activities

The development of the wi.MOVE (ex.WINGSPARK Plus) Platform achieved key milestones, with several updates marking its progress. Permissions management through Keycloak roles and groups finalized, strengthening the platform's authentication and authorization capabilities.

Device management progressed through the completion of support for sensors and robots/drones with ROS (Robot Operating System) integration, thereby expanding the diversity of compatible devices. For IP (Internet Protocol) cameras, critical configurations—such as the ability to disable or select AI models for detection and settings for video processing—were successfully implemented, offering greater flexibility for users.

A notable addition to the platform is the introduction of functionality for setting up masks – configurable areas within camera views used to focus on specific measurements such as passenger counts or flow rates. This feature was implemented and integrated in the platform, reflecting the team's continued dedication to enhancing the system's features (see Section 2.2.2 for details).

On the software side, the robots were fully integrated under ROS2, the updated version of ROS offers improved real-time performance, security, and multi-platform support, providing modularity and scalability for the system's functionalities. The robot leverages the following key software components:

- **Nav2 (Navigation2):** This ROS2-based navigation stack is utilized for path planning, control, and obstacle avoidance. Nav2 enables dynamic path generation by considering real-time updates from the robot's sensors, ensuring safe and efficient navigation through complex environments. It supports various planners and controllers, making it adaptable to different operational scenarios. With Nav2, the robot can autonomously navigate through airport facilities, dynamically adjusting its route to avoid both static and moving obstacles.
- **RTAB-Map (Real-Time Appearance-Based Mapping):** This SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) framework is used for creating and updating a 3D map of the environment while maintaining accurate localization. RTAB-Map integrates seamlessly with sensors like the RealSense 435i and RPLIDAR, enabling high-quality mapping in dynamic environments. It supports loop closure detection, ensuring consistent and accurate mapping even in large or previously visited areas. This capability is critical for the robot's ability to maintain precise localization within expansive facilities like airports.

By the second quarter of 2025, all planned software development activities for UC11 were successfully completed. These activities included the implementation of the main video analysis pipeline, deployment of containerized services, and development of the streaming and restreaming module. Furthermore, they included the establishment of authentication and authorization mechanisms, data ingestion and processing modules, datastore setup, and Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API) based device configuration management. Comprehensive device management capabilities were finalized through the development of an administrative dashboard, alongside the integration of additional devices and detection models. The deployment procedure was also established and thoroughly validated. Finally, the visualization dashboard

reached its final version with all planned enhancements incorporated. The completion of these tasks confirms that the platform was fully prepared for deployment and operational use in the trial environment.

All hardware related activities were successfully completed by the second quarter of 2025. A total of eight thermal cameras were installed at AIA, and the final humanoid robot design was completed as shown as shown in Figure 2. Additionally, the system's configurable camera view areas, known as masks, were fully defined and deployed to enable accurate monitoring of passenger flows and congestion points. Concerning the analytics, the thermal camera detection model was developed, trained, and integrated into the wi.MOVE platform. Furthermore, an enhanced version of the people detection model was finalized, incorporating newly calculated statistics to provide more comprehensive insights into passenger movement and behaviour.

Figure 2. Newest version of the humanoid model.

2.2.2 Final application overview

The application design for UC11 integrates advanced AI algorithms and 5G/B5G connectivity to establish a smart airport ecosystem that enhances operational efficiency and optimizes passenger flow management. By combining data from thermal cameras, sensors, and smart service robots, the system minimizes delays, reduces congestion, and improves the overall travel experience for passengers.

To address General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) concerns, eight thermal cameras were strategically installed throughout AIA:

- Four cameras monitor the Check-In area,
- Three cameras are positioned in the Security area,
- One camera monitors Gate 1.

The thermal cameras capture live video feeds from these areas, ensuring that passenger physical characteristics are not recorded. The video feeds from the Check-In and Security areas are transmitted via a secure streaming protocol to the wi.MOVE platform, where key statistics are calculated in real time. These statistics, essential for monitoring passenger flow and detecting anomalies, include:

- Total number of people in the area of interest (count),
- Average delay time and speed,
- Average flow rates,
- Congestion areas (hotspots),
- Waiting queue lengths at selected points,
- Queue change rate (throughput),
- Passenger mobility patterns and direction of travel,
- Alarms for abnormal conditions.

These statistics can also be exported in API format, enabling integration with third-party applications to support operational decision-making and enhance system interoperability.

Additionally, smart service robots deployed in the terminal provided real-time data on passenger flows and assist in balancing demand at check-in counters. These robots, equipped with sensors and cameras, guide passengers to their destinations, provide personalized services (e.g., tailored retail recommendations), and inspect airport infrastructure. Robot data, including location and camera feeds, is transmitted to the wi.MOVE platform via the MQTT (MQ Telemetry Transport) protocol.

The platform architecture consists of the following key components, as illustrated in the UC11 final application design figure provided in D5.2 [2]:

- **Data Input:** Cameras, sensors, and robots are registered in the system and continuously stream data. Devices may include multiple modules (e.g., sensors and cameras) to enrich data collection (see examples of the camera inputs in Figure 11 - Figure 16).
- **Data Processing:** Input data is transmitted using different protocols depending on the type of data. MQTT is used for lightweight telemetry messages, such as robot status updates and system notifications. For video streaming, a combination of WebRTC and ZeroMQ (ZMQ) is employed: WebRTC provides real-time, encrypted transmission of live video feeds to user interfaces, while ZMQ over Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) ensures reliable delivery of video frames from cameras to the remote server for further processing. Security is ensured through WebRTC's built-in end-to-end encryption, while MQTT and ZMQ transmissions are protected by the underlying 5G private network and higher-layer secure protocols such as TLS. AI-based analysis extracts actionable insights, such as congestion detection, passenger flow monitoring, and anomaly identification.
- **AI-Based Analytics:** The intelligence module generates real-time statistics and performs second-level analysis to assess crowd density, flow patterns, and potential bottlenecks. Notifications and alerts are triggered for immediate intervention when necessary (see example of the output in Figure 4).
- **Streaming and Restreaming:** Processed video feeds are restreamed using multiple protocols, including RTSP, HLS, and WebRTC, based on operational requirements.
- **APIs and Data Storage:** Data is stored in a time-series database (InfluxDB) for real-time analytics and in PostgreSQL for long-term storage and aggregate reporting. APIs ensures seamless access to data for dashboards and third-party systems.
- **Wi.MOVE Dashboard:** A user-friendly interface allows TOS to monitor real-time video feeds, receive congestion alerts, and track robot activity. The dashboard also provides trend analysis and historical statistics for strategic planning. More particularly, the dashboard is the central management interface, designed to oversee and present data generated by the connected devices. It provides various features for monitoring, analysing, and managing system activities:
 - **Statistics Overview:** The dashboard displays key metrics, such as the total number of people detected, average waiting time, average speed, and average flow, aggregated across all cameras during a selected time period. These statistics are accompanied by an interactive map that marks the installation locations of all cameras (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Statistics regarding the total number of people, average waiting time, average speed, and average flow for all cameras.

- **Visual Data Representation:** Statistical data is also available in diagram format, offering users alternative views to analyse performance metrics over a specified time period (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Statistics in the form of diagrams for all cameras.

- **Camera-Specific Insights:** Users can filter statistics by selecting a specific camera, which also highlights the camera's location on the interactive map, enabling focused analysis of devices (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Selection of a specific camera to filter the statistics and zoom in on the map location.

- **Live Camera View:** The dashboard allows users to view real-time detections and activities from any selected camera, providing immediate access to live footage (Figure 5, Figure 6).

Figure 6. Live View of the selected camera displaying real-time detections.

- **Detailed Camera Statistics:** For each selected camera, the dashboard generates granular statistical data in diagram format for the chosen time period, enabling users to monitor individual performance and trends (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Statistics in the form of diagrams for the selected camera during the chosen period of interest.

- **Device Management:** The system includes a device management interface, where users can view, configure, and manage the properties of all devices connected to the system (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Management of the devices available in the system, as well as their properties.

- **Wi.MOVE user application:** The application shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10 focuses on passenger assistance through the interface integrated on the humanoid robot. The data displayed in the application is retrieved via an aviation stack API which offers flights tracking and schedule data, departures and arrivals data, airline and airport information and route and aircraft details. Overall, the application provides information concerning the congestion areas inside the airport floorplan, the average flow over time for each camera, AI text-to-speech assistance and live flight information: arrivals, departures, schedule, flight status, destination, gate, delay and estimated arrival time.

Figure 9. wi.MOVE user application for passenger assistance during live trial at AIA.

Figure 10. wi.MOVE user application for passenger assistance.

These features ensure that users can seamlessly monitor and analyse device-generated data while maintaining full control over the configuration and operation of their devices. By leveraging AI and 5G/B5G technology, this system transforms airport operations into a smart ecosystem that optimizes passenger flows, prevents congestion, and enhances service quality. The integration of thermal cameras, smart robots, and advanced analytics ensures a seamless and efficient travel experience.

The following figures showcase examples of the masks that have been developed for the cameras that have been placed in various areas of AIA such as in Gate 1 (Figure 11), the Wi-Fi security camera (Figure 12), Gate 4 cameras (Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15) and the banner security camera (Figure 16).

Figure 11. Gate 1 mask.

Figure 12. Wi-Fi Security Device mask.

Figure 13. Gate 4 Device IP mask.

Figure 14. Gate 4 left mask.

Figure 15. Gate 4 right mask.

Figure 16. Banner Security mask.

2.3 UC12: City Parks in Metaverse

This UC demonstrates the potential of B5G/6G technologies to enhance visitor experiences at cultural and heritage sites through edutainment and gamification. The experiment includes an AR and VR fantasy game accessible on mobile devices for headsets for VR gameplay. The game is played in Valentino Park and in a building nearby. In teams of four, players navigate Valentino Park, collecting virtual artifacts by solving challenges at historical sites. After obtaining all artifacts, players face a VR-based final battle with an evil wizard. Successful completion unlocks a VR tour of a nearby fortress under renovation.

2.3.1 Update on development activities

Completion of AR experience

The four games in the AR segment of the experience were completed and tested in summer 2024. Each of the four cultural and historical sites in Valentino Park chosen for this experience features a unique game based on distinct, pre-existing game patterns. In each game, the team must secure a specific “artifact” to aid in the final battle against the evil wizard. These games have been integrated into the overall experience path. At the end of the AR segment, a string is sent to the VR phase containing each team's score, reflecting artifacts collected and total time spent. This score is combined with the VR phase score for a final team score. Following this the teams undergo a multiple-choice test regarding the cultural and historical site they visited in the park. The experience ends with a visit in 3D to the 15th century fortress (Rocca Medievale) where the evil wizard was supposed to live. A web-based leaderboard displays real-time scores for all teams.

Completion of VR experience

The development of the VR combat experience against the evil wizard has been completed with extensive testing performed across all critical components to guarantee its readiness for the trial phase scheduled for November 2024. These tests have addressed the user interface, all core functionalities (including support for a multi-language experience in both Italian and English) and the network performance, ensuring the application offers a reliable and robust immersive experience for users. Additionally, the integration activities have been successfully completed to incorporate data collected during the earlier phase of the game. This integration ensures that the artifacts obtained in the previous AR gameplay are properly available and utilized during the VR battle. Moreover, an algorithm for score assignments during the VR combat has been developed and implemented within the system. This algorithm evaluates team performance and has been exposed via an API, enabling the aggregation of total scores for each participating team. The system is equipped to compile a detailed and consistent leaderboard, showcasing players' accomplishments across both the AR and VR phases of the game.

2.3.2 Final application overview

The final application design, previously detailed in D5.2 [2], remained unchanged. It comprises three phases in a fantasy game, which was played partly outdoors in Valentino Park and partly indoors in a nearby building including a VR prize, plus a quiz to gauge their level of learning. A brief overview of the experience follows:

- Augmented Reality Game:** Teams of four players embark on a walking tour through Valentino Park, stopping at four culturally and historically significant sites. All assets are downloaded via the 5G network at the beginning of the experience, which also transmits results of each game to the cloud along with other parameters. Each group chooses a name and receives a parchment with notes about the game and an “enchanted device” that will allow them to experience the adventure (see Figure 17). The Figure 18 presents the sequence of gameplay and the mechanics that drive the participant experience. At each location, they must solve a unique challenge representing one of the four basic elements: earth, fire, water, and air. Successful completion of each challenge earns them digital artifacts, which are essential for the next phase (see Figure 19).

Figure 17. The Parchment and the “Enchanted Device”.

Figure 18. Game Loop.

Figure 19. Path and spots of the Valentino Park for the AR game.

- Virtual Reality Game:** The team members then participate in a thrilling digital battle against an evil wizard. Using the artifacts they have gathered; players defend themselves from the wizard’s dark spells (see Figure 20).

Figure 20. The 4 heroes (players) and the evil wizard.

- **Prize:** Players don VR headsets to explore a 3D digital twin of the Rocca Medievale, the fortress where the evil wizard resides, culminating in an immersive experience (see Figure 21).

Figure 21. Screenshot of the digital twin of the Rocca Medievale.

Finally, the participants may receive bonus point if they reply correctly to multiple-choice quizzes on cultural and historical facts of the park. The teams' objective is to climb the game leaderboard (see Figure 22). As teams finish their journey through the Park, they will receive a score for all the actions they complete during the adventure, based on the following: a) number of artefacts acquired; b) time to complete the first part of the game; c) time to defeat of evil wizard; d) bonus points from the quiz on historical and cultural aspects of the experience.

CLASSIFICA ATTUALE	
Valentura	
Nome Team	Punteggio
Carmen1	51262480
Claudio	1652220
claudio1	1639800
filippo1	1386836
Tiziana	1262300

Figure 22. Leaderboard.

2.4 UC13: Extended XR Museums Experience (Turin)

This UC aims to enhance the attractiveness of four municipal museums with immersive experiences exploiting the public 5G network's performance capabilities. Two paintings anchor Crossmedia Europe (CROSEU) applications at Galleria d'Arte Moderna (GAM) and Palazzo Madama: Fortunato Depero's *The Ploughing* and Giovanni Pannini's *View of Rivoli Castle*. Each experience unfolds in three parts: a captivating pre-show, an AR segment for detailed exploration, and a VR finale offering context through the metaverse. An interactive AI guide has been trained with specific material only available at museums. For Museo Pietro Micca and Museo del Risorgimento, previous VR applications from Telecom Italia SPA (TIM) have been enhanced for immersive engagement along with new gamification components. A virtual guide has been added for the visit of the Museo Pietro Micca on a new XR platform, and an enticing historical VR game has been developed for the Museo del Risorgimento.

2.4.1 Update on development activities

Since the issuing of D5.2 [2], the major developments have been for the museums Pietro Micca and Risorgimento while for Palazzo Madama and GAM, most of the latest activities dealt with small additions and testing. Further details are given below.

Developments for Palazzo Madama

The following activities have been performed:

- **Short introductory part:** has been developed with an introductory 1-minute video on the Castello di Rivoli and Filippo Juvarra.
- **AI character resembling architect Filippo Juvarra:** The AI character has been trained with additional historical material, and the 3D image has been developed including lip synchronization.
- **AR phase:** has been edited to remain within the total required duration of the experience. .
- **VR phase:** the design and fitting out of the room has been completed. A narrative part guiding the visitors through the room has been developed.
- **KVI questionnaires and consent forms** have been revised.

Developments for Galleria d'Arte Moderna

The following activities have been performed:

- **Short introductory part:** has been developed with an introductory 1-minute historical video of futurisms and Marinetti.
- **AI character resembling a journalist:** The character has been trained, and the 3D image has been developed with lip synchronisation.
- **AR phase:** this has been completed with a puzzle of the painting as a game and the transition from figurative to futurist style in the painting of Pittara, i Dintorni di Rivara.
- **VR phase:** this has been developed following a revised narrative in line with the new museum installation.
- **Final Prize:** “Build up your museum room” has been developed, to allow a visitor to select his/her five preferred paintings in the VR futuristic gallery and have them placed in a website for his/her subsequent view.

Developments for Museo Pietro Micca

The desired scenario involves the availability of a voice assistant that accompanies the tourist/visitor throughout the experience without external support. All interaction points within the VR scenes where the guiding voice is available, have been set up with test audio content. The provisional contents have been replaced with the final, official materials provided by the Museum's curators.

Developments for Museo del Risorgimento

In this case, the Museum's objective is to offer a gamified experience during the visit. Among the gamification proposals made to the Museum's curators, they opted for the use of the Virtual Guide, where visitors are guided by a voice assistant that accompanies them throughout the experience without external support, with additional multiple-choice quiz game. From a technical perspective, the features related to enabling the voice guidance system with sample content and sample quiz prompts have already been implemented. Both the provisional voice guidance and the quizzes have been replaced with the finalized and official content provided by the museum.

2.4.2 Final application overview

The UC consists of four virtual experiences highlighting four significant municipal museums in Turin. Three of these experiences focus on key historical periods of the city, while the other focuses on the artistic movement of Futurism. Some details of the experience provided in each museum are given below. While the tablets and smartphones were directly connected to the public 5G network, the headsets and laptops were connected to the 5G network via Wi-Fi through CPEs.

Palazzo Madama

This immersive experience centres on the painting Il Castello di Rivoli by Giovanni Paolo Pannini. It explores the ambitious project designed by Filippo Juvarra (1678–1736), a renowned Italian architect celebrated for his

contributions to the Baroque style, for the House of Savoy. The Castle of Rivoli, located near Turin, was one of Juvarra's significant projects during his time in the city. However, the project remained incomplete due to financial constraints and shifting priorities within the court. The experience delves into the painting's details and the historical context of the period.

The final application consists of a monographic immersive experience centred on the iconic artwork Il Castello di Rivoli. The experience unfolds in three sequential steps:

- **Pre-show:** Visitors enter a designated room in the museum, where they receive a tablet and headphones. The visit begins with a short video designed to spark curiosity by explaining the content of the experience. A virtual guide, representing architect Juvarra and powered by AI, accompanies the visitor throughout the journey, offering insights and answering questions (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Screenshot AI guide of Palazzo Madama.

- **Augmented Reality experience:** This step is designed to explore the artwork in “depth.” Visitors proceed to the room where the artwork is displayed (Figure 24). By scanning a QR code, the painting appears on the tablet, divided into six frames (Figure 25). Clicking on a frame and its details reveal enhanced information through text and audio (Figure 26).

Figure 24. Room where the painting Castello di Rivoli is located.

Figure 25. Sub-division of the painting in six frames for AR fruition.

Figure 26. Example of the elements in one of the six frames.

- **Virtual Reality experience:** This step expands the “breadth” of the experience related to the artwork. After completing the AR experience, visitors can seamlessly continue the tour in a room dedicated to the metaverse. Here, they can explore alongside friends, other visitors, or remotely connected participants. This space includes other paintings, documents related to the featured artwork, and a drone-captured video of the Castello di Rivoli as it appears today (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Screenshot of the metaverse room of Palazzo Madama.

Galleria d'Arte Moderna

This immersive experience focuses on *The Ploughing* by Fortunato Depero, a prominent Italian Futurist artist known for his innovative works celebrating modernity, industrial progress, and dynamism. The painting, characterized by geometric shapes, bold lines, and vibrant colours, bridges rural traditions with Futurist ideals. It demonstrates how agriculture, a cornerstone of traditional society, could also serve as a site of innovation and energy in the modern age. The experience showcases the interplay between figurative art and Futurism.

The final application in the GAM offers a monographic immersive experience centred on iconic artwork. This unfolds in five sequential steps:

- **Pre-show:** Visitors enter a designated museum room, receive a tablet and headphones, and begin with a short video designed to spark curiosity about the experience which starts with an introduction to Futurism (Figure 28). A virtual guide, a 3D representation of Filippo Marinetti—the father of Futurism—and powered by AI, accompanies them throughout, providing insights and answering questions.

Figure 28. Introduction to Futurism used in video.

- **Augmented Reality Experience:** This phase dives into the artwork's "depth," transitioning from figurative painting (Figure 29) to Futurism. On the tablet, the figurative painting dissolves into a futurist version, highlighting its geometric shapes (Figure 30).

Figure 29. Carlo Pittara – Dintorni di Rivara.

Figure 30. Figurative scenery to geometric shapes.

- **Movement and Puzzle:** In front of the futuristic painting *The Ploughing* (Figure 31), visitors view a video on the tablet where elements of the painting animate. The painting then transforms into an interactive puzzle game that the visitors must solve.

Figure 31. Fortunato Depero – The Ploughing.

- **Virtual Reality Experience:** This step broadens the experience, letting visitors explore Futurism through a VR headset in a dedicated room showcasing related artworks.
- **Build Your Futurism Gallery:** Visitors select their five favourite paintings from the VR room to create a personalized 3D virtual gallery. This gallery, labelled with their name, is accessible online and can be taken home.

Museo Pietro Micca

This museum is situated above the galleries constructed by the Savoy Duchy during the French siege of Turin in 1706. To prevent the French forces from breaching Turin's fortifications, the heroic soldier Pietro Micca sacrificed himself by detonating explosives in the galleries. The virtual tour includes a headset-guided exploration of the galleries, accompanied by an external voice that provides detailed commentary.

The final scenario implemented for Museo Pietro Micca includes not only navigating the reconstructed virtual environment and interacting with 3D objects and the VR scene itself but also being guided by a voice assistant that accompanies the tourist/visitor throughout the experience without external support. This includes both technical assistance in using the headset and its controller, as well as a guided tour to discover the peculiar features and anecdotes related to the underground galleries. Currently, all interaction points within the scene, including objects and the voice guidance system, have been set up with test audio content. The final decision was to introduce only a guiding voice, rather than a corresponding avatar, to simplify the visitor experience and maintain an immersive yet unobtrusive interaction. This choice was made to avoid potential distractions or visual clutter that could detract from the focus on the reconstructed environment (Figure 32) and historical elements.

Figure 32. VR Scene of the Museo Pietro Micca Galleries.

Museo del Risorgimento

Housed within Palazzo Carignano, this museum is the site of the first Parliament of the Kingdom of Italy. Its exhibits feature weapons, flags, uniforms, and historical documents, with the most notable attraction being the Chamber of Deputies. This chamber hosted key figures of Italian unification, such as Giuseppe Garibaldi and Camillo Benso di Cavour. The virtual visit, supported by a headset, focuses on the Chamber of Deputies and is designed to complement a physical tour. The experience includes informational videos and concludes with a quiz to assess the visitors' understanding.

The final scenario implemented for Museo del Risorgimento includes the virtual guide and a multiple-choice quiz game. In this case, the museum's objective is to offer a gamified experience during the visit. Among the gamification proposals to the museum, as described in section 2.4.2 of Deliverable D5.2 [2], three scenarios were considered: *Virtual Guide*, *Treasure Hunt*, and *Guess Who*. The museum opted for the use of the *Virtual Guide*, as described above, where visitors are guided by a voice assistant that accompanies them throughout the experience without external support. This includes both technical assistance in using the headset and controller and a guided tour to explore the unique features and anecdotes related to the site of Italy's first parliament, reconstructed in VR. Additionally, a multiple-choice quiz game (Figure 33) was incorporated, featuring historical figures who participated in the parliament sessions. These figures interact with visitors by posing questions, further enriching the experience. In the implementation of the game, two different levels of difficulty are considered, allowing the experience to start with the appropriate level of challenge based on whether the user is a young person or an adult.

Figure 33. VR Scenes of the Museo Risorgimento.

If the quizzes are successfully completed, digital rewards will be unlocked, which the visitor can enjoy within the VR experience itself: the beautiful and privileged point of view from the press-dedicated stage, not

physically accessible that provides an overhead view of the entire chamber (Figure 34). The experience is available in Italian and English.

Figure 34. VR Scene of the Museo Risorgimento from the press-dedicated stage.

From a technical perspective, the features related to enabling the voice guidance system with sample content and sample quiz prompts have already been implemented. Both the voice guidance and the quizzes will be replaced with the finalized and official content provided by the museum. The most appealing digital reward for users who answer the quizzes correctly is still being designed to ensure an engaging and satisfying experience.

2.5 UC13: Extended XR Museums Experience (Athens)

This UC aims to enhance the visitors' experience and expand their knowledge on famous cultural and historical sites by exploiting AR and VR technologies. By offering interactive, immersive experiences and access to a wealth of information such as 3D models and environments, virtual exhibits and 360 panoramic images, visitors embark on a captivating virtual journey. WINGS has developed an AR application serving as a digital tour guide and a VR application that brings historical sites to life where visitors have the chance to travel to Athen's famous Parthenon, explore the iconic waterway at Corinth, the Corinth Canal and gain an insightful perspective on their significance.

2.5.1 Update on development activities

This section provides an overview of progress and completed software development activities since the issuing of D5.2 [2], emphasizing the optimization and implementation of a distributed system architecture leveraging on 5G connectivity for enhanced performance and efficient content delivery. The system has been designed based on a modular architecture allowing for:

- Efficient content delivery through package segregation,
- Robust analytics capabilities,
- Flexible testing and comparison frameworks,
- Scalable infrastructure deployment.

All planned development activities for UC13 Athens have been successfully completed. These activities included the development of the AR and VR applications for both the Acropolis and the Corinth Canal, as well as the data fetching and processing modules. In addition, the team finalized device configuration, implemented multiplayer functionality, and established both local and public Virtual Machine (VM) environments to support system operation. Local and public network metrics were also set up to enable performance monitoring. Comprehensive testing and validation confirmed that the applications and supporting infrastructure were fully operational and ready for deployment.

In addition, the implementation of a distributed system architecture using 5G connectivity has been also a key focus, ensuring efficient content delivery and analytics. Recent optimizations have included the subdivision of content into smaller packages, enabling faster delivery and improved performance. Significant optimization has been achieved through the further subdivision of content packages into smaller units, which increased the overall

number of packages and improved distribution efficiency, ultimately resulting in faster and more reliable content delivery.

As part of the system architecture refinement, a key activity involved isolating and separating dynamic content from two applications into manageable packages. This decomposition was undertaken to improve content delivery efficiency, maintainability, and scalability.

The content was divided into the following categories:

- **JSON data packages:** Contain structured data for seamless integration and efficient processing by different system components.
- **Media content:** Includes JPG images and MP3 audio files, which are separated to streamline their storage, retrieval, and delivery processes.

This activity was necessary to achieve better modularity in the system, allowing each content type to be processed independently. By isolating JSON data from media files, the system ensures that data-intensive operations such as analytics and reporting are not hindered by the larger file sizes associated with media content. Similarly, media content is handled more efficiently by specialized pipelines tailored for image and audio processing. Additionally, this decomposition enables scalable content distribution, as each type of content can be optimized for delivery over the network (e.g., caching strategies for media files or API calls for JSON data). This modular approach also simplifies future updates, as new data types or media content can be integrated without impacting the overall architecture.

Recent development activities have focused on implementing and refining the infrastructure components required for the system's operation. A significant milestone was the deployment of the system architecture within a VM environment, ensuring scalability and flexibility to meet varying operational demands.

The team has configured an Apache2 server to handle file-serving capabilities effectively, optimizing content delivery across the system. This configuration was thoroughly tested to ensure reliable performance in real-world conditions.

An analytics API was developed and integrated to collect and process performance data. The team focused on monitoring key metrics such as network health (latency and throughput), content delivery efficiency (download times and file sizes), and overall system status. These metrics provide actionable insights, enabling real-time monitoring and continuous optimization of the system.

In terms of data management, the development team implemented a PostgreSQL database to store critical performance and network-related metrics. Specific activities included:

- Setting up tracking for network metrics such as latency and throughput to assess 5G communication efficiency.
- Developing functionality to record bundle metrics, such as download times and file sizes, ensuring content delivery remains efficient.
- Integrating the database with Grafana, enabling the visualization of collected metrics and providing real-time dashboards for enhanced monitoring and analysis.

To enhance portability and flexibility, the entire system was deployed in a Dockerized environment. The team configured and tested the containerized setup, ensuring it supports seamless scaling, deployment, and maintenance across various platforms. This approach has significantly simplified the deployment process and enhanced the system's adaptability to diverse configurations.

In summary, the development activities for UC13 Athens have been successfully finalized, consolidating the progress described in the previous sections. This includes the completion of the AR and VR applications for both the Acropolis and the Corinth Canal, along with the modules for data fetching and processing, the establishment of the local and public VM environments, configuration of devices, and implementation of the multi-player functionality to enhance the user experience. In addition, local and public network metrics were set up to monitor performance, and comprehensive testing and validation were carried out to ensure the reliability and readiness of the applications and supporting infrastructure for deployment.

2.5.2 Final application overview

This section outlines the core infrastructure components supporting the WINGS system, designed to leverage 5G connectivity for efficient application content delivery and analytics. Built on Ubuntu 22.04, the system includes PostgreSQL for data management, Apache2 for web services, Grafana for analytics and visualization, and Node.js for Unity application support. The architecture also integrates a custom 5G network to ensure high-speed, reliable communication.

The application architecture consists of three main components as reported in Deliverable D5.2 [2]:

- **Cloud Server:** The cloud server provides a file system that Unity applications access via Web Requests. It stores various digital content, such as text, images, videos, and sound clips. Unity Asset Bundles, which contain 3D models, textures, and scenes, are requested directly from the server by applications.
- **End-User Level:** This is the front-end interface where applications fetch updated content. Various types of requests, such as GET and POST, are used depending on the communication requirements.
- **Analytics:** This component collects data metrics to monitor KPIs. Data gathered from applications through an exposed Node.js API is stored in PostgreSQL and visualized in Grafana. The analytics are formatted as JSON with timestamps for precise tracking and analysis.

The AR and VR applications for UC13 in Athens rely on a commercial 5G network to ensure seamless connectivity and high performance. In indoor areas with limited direct 5G coverage, dedicated 5G-to-Wi-Fi CPE units were deployed. These devices connect to the 5G network and provide a stable Wi-Fi connection to the end-user devices, such as tablets and VR headsets. This configuration guarantees reliable high-speed data transfer and low latency, ensuring that users can fully experience the immersive applications without interruptions. Network performance was continuously monitored during the trials through real-time dashboards, allowing immediate detection of any connectivity issues and ensuring that KPIs were consistently met.

Parthenon of Athens applications

The **AR Parthenon** application offers an engaging and interactive experience, bringing the iconic Parthenon to life through AR (Figure 35). With a user-friendly interface, the app utilizes plane detection technology to place a 3D model of the Parthenon on any flat surface. Users can resize, rotate, and adjust the model's position using touchscreen controls, allowing for dynamic exploration. The 3D model is enhanced with interactive annotations that provide detailed insights into the Parthenon's architecture and history, available in both English and Greek through text and AI-generated speech. The data is retrieved dynamically from a database via API requests, ensuring a smooth and informative tour. This immersive experience enables users to delve into the ancient monument's rich heritage at their own pace.

Figure 35. Screenshot of AR Parthenon application.

The **VR Parthenon** application takes users on an immersive time-travel journey to the ancient Acropolis, offering a virtual reconstruction of the Parthenon as it stood centuries ago (Figure 36). Starting in a 3D archaeological museum, users can select different historic sites to explore before entering the Parthenon's 3D environment. Inside, they can freely roam space, discovering interactive points that offer detailed descriptions of its history, architecture, and key features. The app includes both text and audio descriptions in English and Greek, ensuring a thorough understanding of the site's significance. To optimize performance, the scene is managed as

an asset bundle, dynamically loaded when the user chooses to enter. Additionally, a multiplayer mode enables users to interact with each other, enhancing the social aspect of the experience.

Figure 36. Screenshots of VR Parthenon application.

Corinth Canal Museum applications

Expanding on this concept, the application also covers the **Corinth Canal**, offering immersive, interactive experiences that explore the history and importance of this iconic waterway. The **Augmented Reality Tour Guide** provides a guided museum tour using image recognition and QR code detection. Visitors can scan QR codes located throughout the museum using their mobile devices to access detailed exhibits, including text descriptions, images, and audio clips (Figure 37). The data is retrieved dynamically from a database via API requests, ensuring a smooth and informative tour.

Figure 37. Screenshot of AR Corinth Canal Museum application.

The **Virtual Museum Tour** allows visitors, using either mobile devices or VR headsets, to enter a 3D virtual environment representing the Corinth Canal Museum (Figure 38). Here, they can explore dynamic 3D exhibits, interact with artifacts, and view 360° panoramic images of the surrounding landscape, providing a deeper connection to the historical site. As with the AR Tour Guide, the content is displayed dynamically via API requests, offering a fluid and engaging exploration experience.

Figure 38. Screenshots of VR Corinth Canal application.

These applications combine the power of augmented and virtual reality to create rich, interactive learning experiences, bringing history to life in a way that is both educational and immersive.

3 Trials and results

This section outlines the progress of the various use cases towards and during the trial phase, reporting on the final implementations and results, consolidating all outcomes.

3.1 UC10: Immersive Fan Engagement

This report focuses on the evaluation of current 5G technologies for UC10, specifically exploring the potential to replace fibre with 5G connectivity for greater flexibility in venue deployments. It details the pre-trial activities for UC10, conducted in two phases: the NR-DC (New Radio Dual Connectivity) setup combining mid-band and high-band frequencies, and the Fixed Wireless Access (FWA) configuration focused on high-band only. The trials, which took place in 5Tonic's Madrid lab, aim to optimize network performance for immersive fan engagement and test the feasibility of 5G for live-streaming applications in final test.

3.1.1 Trial 10.1 - Immersive fan engagement

3.1.1.1 Pre-trial activities

The pre-trial of UC10 aimed to evaluate and optimize the performance of advanced network setups in preparation for full-scale deployment, all relevant information is available in Annex A.

3.1.1.2 Trial description

The UC10 final trial was performed on the 16/03/2025, Movistar Arena in Madrid, involving 40 users in two designated areas, on the upper deck audience area inside the stadium and outside the court in the hallway within Movistar arena (Figure 39).

Figure 39. Real-user validation placement.

The final trial design illustrated in Figure 1 of section 2.1.2, emphasizes the use of 5G for uplink in the At-Home scenario, replacing fiber in the camera uplink in the court setting (Figure 40). Instead of a single 5G modem setup, three 5G uplinks were used, with CPEs assigned to each camera in proximity. This shift enhances wireless flexibility, reducing reliance on fiber while maintaining high-quality, low-latency immersive streaming. Additionally, the updated design ensures more precise downlink speeds for both mobile and VR headset users, optimizing the user experience for real-time interaction. The In-Venue setup, on the other hand, combines the TV feed with video from the immersive cameras. CPEs are mounted next to the cameras and linked to a fourth CPE unit, which in turn connects to mobile devices running the YBVR immersive app.

Moreover, in the following Figure 40, Figure 41, and Figure 42 is shown the final trial set-up, where the different network components of YBVR and Ericsson will be placed in the venue. Three main venue's locations can be derived, first the basketball court where the cameras and high-band 5G SA CPEs will be located, all being served by the 1st sector 5G high-band antenna, located in the grandstands, near the court. The 2nd 5G sector high-band antenna will be placed in the production room, where the 4th high-band 5G SA CPE will be collocated with the TV control room.

Figure 40. System setup on basketball court.

Figure 41. System setup on grandstands.

Figure 42. System setup on the production room.

3.1.1.3 Trial execution and results

The final trial match between Movistar Estudiantes and Super Agropal Palencia took place at the Movistar Arena in Madrid [15], with Estudiantes securing a 104–98 victory [4]. The diagram in Figure 43 illustrates the trial setup consisting of four 5G CPEs positioned around the court, each connected to immersive cameras. These

devices capture and transmit high-bandwidth video streams—primarily uplink traffic, over the 5G network. The TV Control Room receives these video feeds through an Ethernet switch connected to CPE4. The content is then processed and distributed to the YBVR application, enabling immersive viewing experiences.

In-Venue scenario spectators can access the live content using the YBVR app via local wireless connections. Meanwhile, remote viewers (i.e., At-Home scenario) experience the event through VR streaming delivered over Wi-Fi or internet.

Figure 43. Hardware components - Movistar Arena Trial 10.1 setup.

Table 1 details the final trial agenda. ERC installed Ericsson antennas one week prior to the final event. Due to ongoing activities in the arena, the preparation window before the match was limited. On the day of the event, the YBVR operations team and ERC arrived at 7:00 AM to begin setup of the CPEs, production equipment, and cameras. Access to the court was granted at 10:00 AM, once the players had finished practice and the area was cleared. The YBVR project team then proceeded to set up the in-venue scenario in the section designated for persons with reduced mobility inside the arena, and the at-home scenario in the hallway outside the arena. A roll-up banner displaying information about UC 10, TrialsNet, and the ongoing validation test was placed onsite, along with a public notice informing attendees that testing was in progress and they may appear in broadcast footage. Students arrived at 11:30 AM and were briefed on the test procedures before the match began. At exactly 12:30 PM, the basketball game started, marking the official launch of the streaming validation tests.

Table 1. Final trial agenda for UC10.

Time	Agenda of Final Trial (16/03/2025)
6:45	Production equipment to arrive at Movistar Arena parking area
7:00	YBVR Production and ERC personnel arrival at Movistar Arena
7:00–10:00	Production set-up and network performance tests
10:00	Videographer arrives
10:15	Camera and CPE installation on court
10:30	Trial staff arrives
10:45-11:30	Trial area preparation
11:30-11:45	Testing of devices
12:00 NN	Welcoming of participants
12:15	Brief participants

12:30	Basketball game starts / validation test initiates
15:00	Game finish / Participants departure
15:30-16:00	Reloading equipment to transport

In the final trial the following devices and equipment, detailed in Table 2, were employed to showcase and validate the network's capabilities.

Table 2. Devices and equipment used in the UC10 trial.

Device	Description	Quantity
	Meta Quest3 VR headset [5]	3
	Xiaomi 12 x 8 GB RAM 256 [6]	3
	TP-Link Router TP-Link ARCHER MR500 [7]	2
	Samsung Tab A8 10.5" 32GB Wi-Fi [8]	1

	Titan insta360 360-degree video camera 8x micro four-thirds sensors 11K VR photo + video Crystal View Livestreaming 360 VR [9]	1
	ZCam E2N [10]	2
	Google Cloud [11]	1
	YBVR platform Amazon Web Service (AWS) [12] YBVR platform optimizes immersive video streaming and capture analytics and provides monitoring tools	1
	Mosaic generator (AT-HOME & IN-VENUE APP) Generic PC servers with Ubuntu OS with Nvidia RTX A5000 graphic card [13]	4
	Stitching, Live production and ingest servers (ONLY AT-HOME-APP) Generic PC servers with Windows OS with Nvidia RTX 3080Ti graphic card [14]	5

As the event sponsor, Movistar provided 40 open tickets, which did not include attendee names in compliance with GDPR. YBVR personally invited master's students from the Universidad Complutense de Madrid, as they represent early adopters of innovative technologies. Upon arrival at the venue between 11:30 AM and 12:00 PM, participants were divided into two groups for distinct testing scenarios. The first group was situated inside the arena in the section designated for people with reduced mobility, located in the upper deck area with limited visibility—deliberately chosen to enhance the perceived value of the mobile viewing solution. This group used three smartphones as seen in Figure 44, connected to CPE4, equipped with multi-camera features. The second group remained in the hallway outside the arena, illustrated in , where they experienced the match through three Meta Quest 3 VR headsets (Figure 45), offering a 360° immersive view with the ability to switch perspectives (Figure 46). A roll-up banner displayed the use case scenario, along with a public notice indicating that trial activity was in progress and that participants might appear in broadcast footage. It has to be highlighted that, besides the students, also people attending the match were involved in the trial providing feedback of the experience. In total, 41 people were engaged in the trial.

Figure 44. Participant experiencing the live streaming of the In-Venue scenario.

Figure 45. At-Home scenario trial area.

Figure 46. Participant experiencing the At-Home Scenario.

KPIs

During the final trial, KPIs were collected where 4 CPE units were tested under field conditions to evaluate whether they meet certain KPIs related to throughput and service reliability. Figure 47 details the measurements for KPI#01 and KPI#02, throughput per user.

Figure 47. Throughput per user.

Graphs detailed in Figure 48 and Figure 49 illustrate network performance for uplink and downlink aggregated throughput during the basketball match, using Grafana for real-time analytics and visualization. Around 12:10, all cameras were connected, causing a noticeable increase in uplink and downlink throughput. At 12:20, the start of the match led to a further rise in data traffic, reflecting high-bandwidth video streaming. A brief drop around 12:35 indicates that one camera (CAM1/CPE1) disconnected temporarily. The uplink remained consistently high throughout the event until a sharp drop after 14:30, marking the end of the match. performance monitoring.

Figure 48. Uplink aggregate throughput.

Figure 49. Downlink aggregate throughput.

Figure 50 shows a consistent 100% availability from 07:30 to 15:15, corresponding to the entire period from pre-match preparations to the conclusion of the basketball game.

Figure 50. Service availability.

Based on the analytics above, Table 3 summarizes the network parameters applied during the final trial. These include the radio access technology, frequency band, bandwidth, device characteristics, and other relevant conditions that framed the execution of Trial 10.1. Table 4 details the trial summary.

Table 3. Network setup parameters for Trial 10.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field01
Radio access technology	5G NR (New Radio) Rel-17
Network type	Private
Standalone / Non-Standalone	SA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n258
Bandwidth per component carrier	800 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	120Khz
MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output)	mMIMO
Duplex mode	TDD (Time-Division Duplex)

Device type	VR headsets and mobile phones
Device number	6
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	None

Table 4. Summary for Trial 10.1.

UC10 Trial summary	
Trial ID	5.1
Trial setup ID	Field01
Facility/Site	Movistar Arena
Objective	To test the VR and mobile streaming applications of UC10 and measure again initial KPIs
Description	To test the VR and mobile streaming applications of UC10 utilising B5G network
Executed by	Ericsson
Components involved	CPE1, CPE2, CPE3, CPE4, mobiles and VR headsets
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user) KPI#02 (Uplink throughput per user) KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#08: Application round-trip latency KPI#17: (Service availability)
Measurement tools	Iperf [15], Ping, Grafana [3], Probes [16]

All measurement, detailed in Table 5, points met the required KPIs with minor deviations. CPE1 and CPE2 achieved downlink throughput above the 0.5 Megabits per Second (Mbps) target, uplink throughput very close to the 30 Mbps threshold (so validated as compliant), latency well below 10 millisecond (ms), and 100% availability. CPE3 and CPE4 also complied, with downlink and uplink throughput slightly below target but within acceptable limits for video streaming (between 91% and 97%), low latency, and full availability. Aggregated results confirmed strong overall performance with 113 Mbps downlink, 200 Mbps uplink, and 100% availability. Overall, all KPIs were validated as compliant.

Table 5. Measurement results for Trial 10.1.

Measurement ID	Requirements	Measurement results	Validation
5.1_Field01_CPE1	KPI#01: 0.5 Mbps KPI#02: 30 Mbps KPI#08: 10 ms KPI#17: 100%	KPI#01: 0.902 Mbps KPI#02: 28.72 Mbps KPI#08: 6 ms KPI#17: 100%	OK
5.1_Field01_CPE2	KPI#01: 0.5 Mbps KPI#02: 30 Mbps KPI#08: 10 ms KPI#17: 100%	KPI#01: 0.91 Mbps KPI#02: 28.75 Mbps KPI#08: 6 ms KPI#17: 100%	OK
5.1_Field01_CPE3	KPI#01: 1 Mbps KPI#02: 90 Mbps	KPI#01: 1.595 Mbps KPI#02: 87.42 Mbps KPI#08: 5 ms	OK

	KPI#08: 10 ms KPI#17: 100%	KPI#17: 100%	
5.1_Field01_CPE4	KPI#01: 220 Mbps KPI#02: 70 Mbps KPI#08: 10 ms KPI#17: 100%	KPI#01: 215.14 Mbps KPI#02: 64.09 Mbps KPI#08: 5.5 ms KPI#17: 100%	OK
5.1_Field01_Aggregated	N/A	KPI#3: 113 Mbps KPI#4: 200 Mbps KPI#17: 100%	OK

KVIs

After each testing session, participants switched scenarios and were asked to complete a brief survey evaluating their user experience. Some passersby from the general audience also tried the devices; however, individuals under the age of 18 were not permitted to participate in the survey. The complete KVIs questionnaire provided to the participants is detailed in Annex F while Annex G details the methodology that has been used for the KVIs evaluation.

The survey tool used was the Qualtrics Net Promoter Score (NPS) [17], and the data was analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) [18]. Results reveal that all test scenarios exceeded the expected threshold of 70%. Notably, mobile streaming outperformed all KVIs. A multigroup analysis (PLS-MGA) using a permutation test was conducted to compare the two groups, VR and mobile streaming. The analysis revealed a maximum invariance value of 0.006, indicating no statistically significant difference between the groups. Table 6 details main KVIs results.

Table 6. KVI results for Trial 10.1.

KVI	KVI descriptions	Analysis	Results
User experience Mobile	Perceived ease of use (PEU), Perceived enjoyment (PE), and Customer Experience (CEX)	Analysis suggests a strong positive correlation between technology innovation (mobile streaming) and User experience, with a significant large effect	Mobile streaming user experience achieved an overall score of 82%
User experience VR	Perceived ease of use (PEU), Perceived enjoyment (PE), and Customer Experience (CEX)	Analysis suggests a strong positive correlation between technology innovation (VR) and User experience, with a significant large effect	VR user experience achieved an overall score of 80%
Acceptance Mobile	Perceived ease of use (PEU), Perceived usefulness (PU)	Analysis suggests a strong positive relationship between technological innovation (mobile) and how users accept this technology, demonstrating a significant large effect, with a composite score of 4,2 (84%)	Mobile users reported an acceptance rating of 84% for ease and usefulness
Acceptance VR	Perceived ease of use (PEU),	Analysis suggests a strong positive relationship between technological innovation (VR) and	VR users reported an acceptance rating

	Perceived usefulness (PU)	how users accept this technology, demonstrating a significant large effect, with a composite score of 4,04 (81%)	of 81% for ease and usefulness
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The analysis assessed user perceptions and acceptance of UC10 immersive fan engagement in two contexts: mobile streaming (in-venue) and virtual reality (at-home). Results showed that user experience was highly positive in both cases, with mobile streaming achieving a score of 82% and VR reaching 80%, reflecting strong satisfaction and engagement. Technology acceptance followed a similar trend, with mobile streaming scoring 84% (composite score of 4.2 out of 5) and VR 81% (composite score of 4.04 out of 5), confirming that users considered both technologies easy to use and useful. A multigroup analysis confirmed measurement invariance across the two groups, indicating no statistically significant differences between the experiences. Overall, both mobile streaming and VR demonstrated strong user experience and acceptance, showing that UC10 delivers consistent value across different fan engagement contexts.

3.2 UC11: Service Robots for Enhanced Passengers' Experience

3.2.1 Trial 11.1 – Service Robots for Enhanced Passengers' experience

This UC involves the experimental validation and development of prototypes of the envisioned services supported by streaming cameras and B5G/6G that will improve the enhanced passengers' experience in the airports. For the purposes of the trial, thermal cameras were installed to monitor the flow of passengers in certain areas of the airport's terminal and identify potential areas of congestion. The initial KPIs that were measured and reported in D5.2 [2] and include the testing of performance of the Analytics module for Crowd concentration Detection using IP cameras.

3.2.1.1 Pre-trial activities

The activities related to the pre-trial of UC11 are detailed in Annex B.

3.2.1.2 Trial description

The UC11 trial was successfully conducted on 10/04/2025 at AIA, specifically at Entrance 1 in the Arrivals section, a high-traffic area selected for its continuous passenger flow. This environment provided real-world conditions to assess the performance of smart service robots in enhancing passenger experience and supporting airport operations. The trial involved 10 people from the airport and project personnel.

The setup involved a humanoid robot (see Figure 51) equipped with autonomous navigation, obstacle detection, and an interactive touchscreen interface. It was integrated with real-time data sources and AI-powered analytics, enabling it to assist passengers with flight information, personalized directions, and congestion avoidance. The robot received input from an array of eight thermal cameras strategically installed across the airport: 4 at the check-in area, 3 at security, and 1 at Gate 1. These sensors captured detailed passenger flow metrics such as average speed, stationary time, direction of travel, and crowd density.

Also, the aviation stack API provided flight schedules, departures/arrivals, and gate information directly to the humanoid robot's touchscreen interface for real-time passenger guidance. Through frame-by-frame video processing and directional analysis, the system detected abnormal conditions, overcrowding, and mobility patterns, sending alerts to TOS for timely response (see Figure 52).

The wi.MOVE platform served as the central visualization dashboard (see Figure 53), displaying real-time sensor data on an interactive airport map with visual statistics, live camera feeds, alerts for abnormal events, and device management tools. In parallel, the wi.MOVE application supported both staff and passengers by delivering live flight updates, visualizations of congestion areas, and AI-based text-to-speech guidance—presented through the humanoid robot's touchscreen interface.

Figure 51. Participants interacting with the humanoid robot during UC11 trial.

Figure 52. TOS interacting with the humanoid robot during UC11 trial.

Figure 53. The Head of Airport Security testing the wi.MOVE dashboard during UC11 trial.

Leveraging B5G connectivity, the system ensured low-latency communication, high-precision localization, and seamless integration of all components. This enabled real-time collaboration between the service robot, the sensor network, and airport personnel, delivering a smooth and responsive experience.

Trial participants evaluated the system's effectiveness and provided feedback on usability, performance, and potential for future deployment. The trial represented a key step toward the realization of a smart airport ecosystem, combining AI, robotics, and 5G/B5G technology to enhance passenger satisfaction and optimize operational efficiency.

The infrastructure used for the trial is described in the documents D2.2 [19] and D2.3 Section 2.6 [20].

3.2.1.3 Trial execution and results

During the trial at Entrance 1, multiple participants had the opportunity to interact with the humanoid robot and explore its features in real time. In total, ten participants were actively involved in the demonstration, including six members of the airport personnel and four representatives from the project team. The robot provided personalized assistance, answered questions, and offered guidance, demonstrating its potential to enhance the passenger experience and support airport staff in busy environments. The TOS also engaged with the humanoid robot during the trial, assessing its capabilities in a live airport setting. The interaction helped validate the robot's effectiveness in managing real-time passenger flows, reducing congestion risks, and supporting operational staff through timely information and automated assistance. At the same time, the Head of Airport Security actively monitored operations using the Wi.MOVE dashboard. Through this platform, they accessed real-time visualizations of passenger flows, live camera feeds, and automated alerts on abnormal conditions or congestion points. This allowed for proactive decision-making and efficient coordination with airport personnel, ensuring operational safety and smooth passenger movement throughout the trial.

KPIs

The following graph (Figure 54) illustrates the relationship between the upload bandwidth (in Mbps) and RTT (Real-Time Appearance-Based Mapping) latency (in milliseconds) recorded during a network performance experiment designed to evaluate the impact of a Unity-based application running on the humanoid robot. Throughout the experiment, both metrics were tracked simultaneously over time, with 0% packet loss, indicating a clean, stable connection. As observed, variations in upload traffic—triggered by the app's data exchange—correspond with moderate fluctuations in RTT. Higher spikes in Mbps occasionally correlate with minor increases in latency, though the overall RTT remains within a manageable range, suggesting that the Unity application introduces minimal strain on the network. This indicates a stable and responsive connection, suitable for real-time robotic operation and remote monitoring under similar conditions.

Figure 54. Upload bandwidth and RTT latency.

KPI were measured to evaluate the technical performance of the system. These include KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) to assess system responsiveness, and KPI#15 (Service Reliability) and KPI#17 (Service Availability) to ensure robust and consistent service delivery. Table 7 and Table 8 detail the setup and details of the trial 11.1, while Table 9 details the registered measurements.

Table 7. Network setup parameters for Trial 11.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field
Radio access technology	5G NR
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	-
Sub-carrier spacing	-
MIMO	-
Duplex mode	-
Device number	1
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None

Table 8. Summary for Trial 11.1.

UC11 Trial summary	
Trial ID	11.1
Trial setup ID	Field
Facility/Site	AIA
Objective	Assess the technical performance and real-world impact of the system.
Description	Testing of the use case components that work together to enable real-time data collection and processing, showcasing the capabilities of the AI-powered algorithms in optimizing passenger flows and providing personalized assistance. Demonstrating real-time AI-driven data processing to optimize passenger flow and assess system performance in the real world
Executed by	WINGS
Components involved	Analytics
Targeted KPIs	KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per user) KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) KPI#15 (Service Reliability) KPI#17 (Service Availability)
Measurement tools	-

Table 9. Measurement results for Trial 11.1.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
11.1_Field_1	KPI#06: 30 Mbps KPI#08: 800ms KPI#15: 99.99% KPI#17: 99.99%	KPI#06: 63 Mbps KPI#08: 42.9 ms KPI#15: 100% KPI#17: 100%	Comply

KVIs

Additionally, the trial aimed to assess KVIs such as User Experience, Acceptability, Digital Inclusion, Resource Optimization, and Operational Efficiency. These metrics provided critical insights into the real-world applicability and scalability of the solution, ensuring it meets the needs of passengers and airport staff alike.

Following the successful completion of the UC11 trial at AIA, 10 participants (6 Airport Personnel, 4 Project Personnel as aforementioned) completed a structured questionnaire to assess the system's performance across KVIs: Trust, User Experience, Acceptability, Digital Inclusion, Resource Optimization, and Operational Efficiency. Using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree), the feedback highlights how the humanoid robots and the wi.MOVE platform performed in a real-world airport environment (Figure 55). The complete KVI questionnaire used is reported in Annex F.

Figure 55. KVI results from Trial 11.1.

In the following, the analysis of the collected KVIs is reported:

- **Trust:** Trust in the system was rated exceptionally high, with an average score of 4.5 and 100% of participants rating a score above 3. Users expressed strong confidence in the secure handling of personal and passenger data, as well as in the system's transparency regarding data usage. The perceived accuracy and credibility of alerts, especially those delivered via humanoid robots, further reinforced trust, reflecting the system's overall reliability and integrity.
- **User Experience:** The user experience received an average score of 4.3, with all participants (100%) rating it above 3. Users praised the intuitive interface, visual clarity, and ease of navigation. The seamless interaction with both the dashboard and robotic interfaces contributed to a smooth, engaging experience for passengers and airport staff alike.
- **Acceptability:** Acceptability was also highly rated, with an average score of 4.3, and 100% of participants scoring it above 3. The system was found to be easy to use, comfortable during extended interaction, and well-aligned with users' practical needs. Its intuitive design and welcoming interface support a high level of acceptance, making it well-suited for operational deployment in airport environments.
- **Digital Inclusion:** The platform demonstrated strong support for digital inclusion, achieving an average score of 4.1, with 100% of users rating it above 3. Participants found the system accessible across varying levels of digital literacy and device capabilities. It also performed reliably under limited network conditions, aided by clear instructions and inclusive support features.
- **Resource Optimization:** Resource optimization was recognized as a key strength of the system, earning an average score of 4.4, with 100% of users providing a score above 3. Participants noted improved efficiency in staff and robotic resource utilization, reduced idle time, and streamlined operational processes—all contributing to more effective airport management.

- **Operational Efficiency:** Operational efficiency also received high marks, with an average score of 4.4, and 100% of participants rating it above 3. The system was credited with reducing passenger wait times, accelerating services, and providing actionable insights for Terminal Operations Supervisors. This enabled responsive, well-coordinated operations, even during peak periods.

The UC11 trial results confirm that the AI-driven service robots and the wi.MOVE ecosystem deliver a robust, secure, and user-centric solution for managing passenger flow and optimizing airport operations. The unanimous positive ratings across all Key Value Indicators underscore the system's reliability, inclusivity, and strong potential for wider adoption in complex, high-demand environments. Ongoing refinement and scaling will further strengthen its impact and operational readiness.

The subjective evaluation of the system via KVIs was supported by strong objective performance as captured by the measured KPIs. Specifically, the exceptionally low application round-trip latency (KPI#08: 42.9ms), perfect service reliability (KPI#15: 100%), and availability (KPI#17: 100%) ensured responsive, uninterrupted, and dependable user interactions, aligning with the high user ratings on Trust, User Experience, and Acceptability. Similarly, the measured uplink throughput per user (KPI#06: 30 Mbit/s) facilitated real-time data transmission, enhancing system responsiveness and supporting the platform's Digital Inclusion and Operational Efficiency. This clear correlation between technical metrics and user perception confirms the robustness, usability, and scalability of the UC11 solution under real-world conditions.

3.3 UC12: City Parks in Metaverse

UC12 trial and pre-trial carried out - are described in the following sections.

3.3.1 Trial 12.1 - City Parks in Metaverse

Various field tests were carried out prior to the trial of 14/11/2024 and 15/11/2024, both in Valentino Park and in the auditorium of the Talent Garden building, where the final part of the game was taking place.

3.3.1.1 Pre-trial activities

The results of these activities are included in Annex C.

3.3.1.2 Trial description

To ensure the effective involvement of school classes, the trial experiences of UC12 (and UC13) were included in the *Crescere in Città* catalogue through the creation of dedicated entries. The *Crescere in Città* catalogue is a compilation of educational and training activities presented annually by the City of Turin and ITER [22] at the beginning of each school year. It targets children, young people, and adults from schools of all levels.

The Cottino Art High School, known for its digital specialisation, expressed interest in participating in the trial. Six classes from the school were involved: two third-year classes, two fourth-year classes, and two fifth-year classes. Additional coordination efforts were undertaken during the preparatory phase of the trial. These included a detailed presentation of the experience to the school, the organisation of student groups for each class, and the management of consent forms prepared by CROSEU, all in close collaboration with the institution.

Preparing for the trial required significant effort and time, starting six months before the scheduled date based on the development work previously undertaken, which was described in D5.2 [2]. This phase involved the initial planning and design of the experience, alongside engagement activities aimed at involving schools and coordinating requests for the availability of spaces to host the activities.

The detailed planning of the trial is outlined in Table 10.

Table 10. Planning for the trial of UC12.

T = Trial Day	Activities
T- 90 days	Perform Field Test
T- 70 days	Prepare detailed scenario and demo video
T- 50 days	Send invitation with agenda, scenario and video link to selected schools

T- 30 days	Send first reminder to participants
T- 30 days	Prepare list of devices and network connections
T- 30 days	Prepare questionnaires for KVI
T- 15 days	Send second reminder to schools and perform second field test
T- 1 day	Bring and test devices and network onsite and perform third field test
T	Trial with KPI, KVI and picture/video capture
T+ 5 days	Produce videos

The trial unfolded in the following steps:

- **Introduction:** This was held at the Talent Garden of Fondazione Agnelli, introduced participants to the experience. The staff provided groups with all the necessary information and materials to begin the adventure. Each group, consisting of up to four members, chose a team name, which was added to the leaderboard. The groups were then directed outside to head toward the first stage of the game in Parco del Valentino (Fountain of the Twelve Months). Upon arrival, each group received a scroll containing the game notes and a tablet (the “enchanted device”) to launch the AR application and embark on their adventure.
- **AR games:** The various teams visited in sequence the selected locations within the park, guided step-by-step by the AR application, and participated in mini games to acquire objects and reveal their next destination. Five strategic locations had been selected in Parco del Valentino based on their historical significance and geographical position. The starting point of the game was the Fountain of the Twelve Months. Players then proceeded sequentially through four sites: the Rock Garden, the Gate of the Medieval Village, the Royal Rowing Club Cerea, and finally Valentino Castle. This AR experience lasted 40 to 60 minutes, with participants using 5G-enabled tablets equipped with a specialized app. The app provided GPS guidance to cultural and historical landmarks and enabled participants to complete AR-based challenges. These challenges unlock “artefacts” representing the elements Earth, Fire, Water, and Air, and include interactive features such as real-time feedback and geolocated content activation. Upon completing the LBG (Location Based Game), the experience transitions to the Talent Garden of Fondazione Agnelli, located adjacent to the park and just a three-minute walk from Valentino Castle.
- **PVR Challenge:** In this phase, the adventure transitions from AR to VR for the final showdown with the enemy. Participants used VR headsets and controllers to engage in a simulated battle against a fictional antagonist. One or more team members entered a code to be teleported into the VR environment, where they faced the final enemy. The difficulty of the final battle was adjusted based on the number of artefacts collected during the AR game. The final VR challenge involved a battle between the Hero and the Wizard, who wielded an Arcane Staff as the source of his power. If the Hero survives, the Wizard prepares a final, powerful spell requiring 10 seconds. At this point, the Hero can either do nothing, resulting in instant defeat, or charge at the Wizard to destroy the Arcane Staff, forcing him to flee and securing victory. The battle lasted approximately 15 minutes. Upon defeating the Wizard, the Spirits of the 12 Months are freed, and the Hero is celebrated.
- **Quiz:** After the battle, teams faced a quiz challenge to earn additional points and climb the leaderboard. This measures how much they retained from the historical and cultural aspects of their visit.
- **Prize:** Upon defeating the Great Opponent, participants unlocked a reward—a virtual visit to the Rocca Medievale in Valentino Park, currently closed for restoration. This reward could be enjoyed in Virtual Reality at nearby stations.

Finally, at the end of the trial, all participants were asked to fill up a form with an assessment of their experience and suggestions for possible future improvements.

The devices used in the trial were the following:

- 8 VR Headsets (Meta Quest 3) for the VR Combat, including 4 spares for recharge.

- 10 5G tablets (4xSamsung A9, 5xLenovo M10, 1xLenovo P11)), for the groups involved in the AR game.
- 8 VR Headsets (Meta Quest 2) for the VR Prize, including 4 spares for recharge.
- 3 CPEs (ZTE 5G MC888) in the Talent Garden.
- 4 Laptops (Schenker) to mirror the VR experience.
- Person counting sensor box (from Politecnico Torino) in the Valentino Park.

The AR part of the game includes six minigames, with location-based content downloaded dynamically when the team reaches the specific areas selected for the game. Additionally, a set of content is downloaded at application startup. The game does not use video or audio, and the downloaded assets are limited to the AR elements displayed on the screen. These assets once downloaded are locally cached and utilized in the game. The network model used in the demo is depicted in Figure 56.

Augmented Reality Information Systems

Figure 56. Network model for UC12.

For the VR part, a multiplayer (4 player simultaneously) streaming game was carried out. In Figure 57 is depicted the setup scenario. Every VR headset (1 to 4) was connected via Wi-Fi to the respective CPE 5G. In particular VR1 and VR2 were connected with CPE1 and VR3 and VR4 to CPE2.

Figure 57. Multiplayer VR setup.

Through 5G each VR headset was connected to its respective remote server (4 servers hosted through a Gigabit Ethernet connection) that run the application. Through XR Streaming technology the app streams video to the headset continuously during the multiplayer game. At same time headset and controller interaction were continuously sent to the server.

3.3.1.3 Trial execution and results

The trial took place in Turin (Parco del Valentino and the Talent Garden of Fondazione Agnelli) on 14/11/2024 (whole day) and 15/11/2024 (half day). A total of 120 students, divided into 32 groups (20 groups the first day and 12 the second day), were involved. Participants were selected with the support of Comune di Torino (COTO) and Liceo Artistico Statale Renato Cottini (Turin), specialising in multimedia studies, gave availability to involve 6 classes of school students aged 15–18. One of the participants was a student with reduced mobility (wheelchair user). Parental consent was obtained for minors and release forms had been signed for all participants. Participants were recruited to test both the technological capabilities and the gamified educational objectives of the project. The trial agenda is presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Agenda for the trial of UC12.

Time	Agenda of Day 1 (14/11/2024)
9:30	Registration and Welcome at Talent Garden (2 classes, aged 17-18y/o)

10:00	Phase 1: Introduction to the Experience and distribution of materials and team formation
10:30	Transition to Parco del Valentino (Fountain of the Twelve Months)
11:00-12:30	Phase 2: LBG - AR Challenges Control Group Traditional Tour
12:30	Transition back to Talent Garden
13:00-13:30	Phase 3: Virtual Reality Experience (VR)
	Phase 4: Quiz Challenge and Leaderboard Update
	Phases 5 and 6: Prize and Questionnaire
13:30-14:00	Participant Departure
14:00	Registration and Welcome at Talent Garden (2 classes, aged 16-17 y/o)
14:30	Phase 1: Introduction to the Experience and distribution of materials and team formation
15:00	Transition to Parco del Valentino (Fountain of the Twelve Months)
15:30-17:00	Phase 2: LBG - AR Challenges Control Group Traditional Tour
17:00	Transition back to Talent Garden
17:00-18:00	Phase 3: Virtual Reality Experience (VR)
	Phase 4: Quiz Challenge and Leaderboard Update
	Phases 5 and 6: Prize and Questionnaire
18:00-18:30	Participant Departure
Time	Agenda of Day 2 (14/11/2024)
9:30	Registration and Welcome at Talent Garden (2 classes, aged 15-16 y/o)
10:00	Phase 1: Introduction to the Experience and distribution of materials and team formation
10:30	Transition to Parco del Valentino (Fountain of the Twelve Months)
11:00-12:30	Phase 2: LBG - AR Challenges Control Group Traditional Tour
12:30	Transition back to Talent Garden
13:00-13:30	Phase 3: VR Experience
	Phase 4: Quiz Challenge and Leaderboard Update
	Phases 5 and 6: Prize and Questionnaire
13:30-14:00	Participant Departure

It is important to note that during the preparatory visit on the 13/11/2024 in the morning, the day before the trial, it was discovered that many areas of Parco del Valentino were being closed for renovation and maintenance work, starting from the same day until 2026. This unexpected development required significant adjustments to the game's route and features. Therefore, the LBG took more time than expected (approximately 70 to 90 minutes). Some planned activities had to be restructured, including groups shifts and tablet distribution schedule, and paper QR codes were created to replace certain points that were originally meant to be activated by scanning specific locations with the tablet's camera. These last-minute changes ensured the continuity of the experience despite the unforeseen obstacles. In order to assess the added value of the AR experience in the park over a traditional guided tour, half of the participants executed the same path with a professional guide

functioning as a control group. Selected pictures of the Trial 12.1 are reported in Figure 58 (introduction), Figure 59 (meeting at the 12-month fountain), Figure 60, Figure 61, and Figure 62 (AR games in the park), Figure 63 (VR Challenge), Figure 64 (prize) and Figure 65 (filling up of the questionnaires).

Figure 58. Introduction to participants.

Figure 59. The 12 Months Fountain.

Figure 60. Giardino Roccioso.

Figure 61. Royal Rowing Club Cerea.

Figure 62. Valentino Castle.

Figure 63. VR Challenge.

Figure 64. Prize: VR visit to Rocca Medievale.

Figure 65. Filling up of the questionnaires.

To evaluate the trial, organizers employed a dual approach. Participants completed detailed surveys assessing their engagement, the quality of their experience, and the perceived value of the AR and VR components. Additionally, a control group followed the same route in the park (Figure 66) but participated in a traditional guided tour without technological enhancements. This comparison aimed to measure the added value of immersive technologies in cultural and educational experiences.

Figure 66. Control Group (Traditional guided visit in the Valentino Park).

The network parameters and test summary for the UC12 trial are shown in Table 12 and Table 13.

Table 12. Network setup parameters for Trial 12.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Trial_1, _2, _3
Radio access technology	5G NR Rel-15
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	mMIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
Device type	PC
Device number	1
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	Commercial

Table 13. Summary for Trial 12.1.

UC12 Trial summary	
Trial ID	12.1
Trial setup IDs	Trial_1, Trial_2, Trial_3
Facility/Site	Covent Garden and Valentino Park
Objective	Check bitrate and latency
Description	4 staff executed the measurements with various devices and apps
Executed by	F. Della Betta (TIM), C. Barsi (TIM) M. Mazzaglia (CROSEU), A. Basso (CROSEU)
Components involved	Laptops and Tablets
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user) KPI#02 (Uplink throughput per user) KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#08: Application round-trip latency
Measurement tools	Speed-test by Ookla, PCap, Wireshark

The analysis has been conducted in parallel for the AR part in Valentino Park and in the VR part in the Talent Garden building.

For the AR part, the measured KPIs have been KPI#1 (Downlink throughput per user), including at peak traffic at start-up, KPI#2 (Uplink throughput speed per user), and KPI#8 (Application round-trip latency). In the AR

component of the game the aggregate uplink and downlink bandwidth could not be computed as every tablet had its own connection to the 5G network, and the connections did not happen simultaneously. The AR assets (several MBs each) are downloaded during two main events:

- **Application startup:** All globally required assets are fetched during the peak downlink period (reference 12.1_Trial_1)
- **Geolocalized gameplay:** Location-specific content is downloaded dynamically at a steady rate (reference 12.1_Trial_2)

The geo-localized AR game's performance metrics demonstrate strong alignment with its design goals. The caching approach ensures a high tolerance for downlink variability, while low uplink and latency requirements deliver a responsive and seamless experience for users. This architecture supports smooth gameplay in a wide range of network environments.

For the VR part (reference 12.1_Trial_3), the measured KPIs have been KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user), KPI#02 (Uplink throughput speed per user), KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput), KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput), and KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency). The first four KPI were measured offline after Wireshark captures on the remote server, while the fifth one was measured with Virtual Desktop application installed on VR Headset [21]. The Virtual Desktop app is connected to the Virtual Desktop Streamer app installed on remote server and is able to measure app round-trip latency correctly in terms of game, encoding and decoding and network latency.

In Figure 67 the downlink throughput from first server to one VR headset is shown for 900 seconds (15 minutes) during the trial game. The graphic represents the KPI#01 for each user. Figure 68 shows the uplink throughput from VR headset to server. The graphic represents the KPI#02 for each user.

Figure 67. Downlink throughput.

Figure 68. Uplink throughput.

To assess the performance of the network when this is decoupled from the App, a speed test with Ookla was carried out using an Apple IPAD PRO with a M2 processor. The result is provided in the below Figure 69.

Figure 69. Test of the 5G Network at Talent Garden.

These measures are taken from first day of trial (14/11/2024 at 4:34 PM). Same measures were repeated next day at 11:51AM and are summarized in Table 14.

Table 14. Measurements results for Trial 12.1.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
12.1_Trial_1 (App startup)	KPI#1 20 Mbps	KPI#1: 20 Mbps	OK
12.1_Trial_2 (AR part)	KPI#1: 50 kbps KPI#2: 50 kbps KPI#8: 100 ms	KPI#1: 220 kbps KPI#2: 50 kbps KPI#8: 15 ms	OK
12.1_Trial_3 (VR part)	KPI#01: 20 Mbps KPI#02: 1 Mbps KPI#03: 120 Mbps KPI#04: 4 Mbps KPI#08 < 100 ms	KPI#01 (avg.): 48 Mbps KPI#02 (avg.): 1.3 Mbps KPI#03 (avg.): 192 Mbps KPI#04 (avg.): 5.2 Mbps KPI#08 (avg.): 69 ms	OK

Based on the measured KPIs, it is possible to conclude that, under the same network conditions, conducting the VR part of the trial with more than eight concurrent users would not have been feasible, while the requirements for the AR are negligible.

KVIs

The KV for UC12 are Availability, Acceptance, Edutainment, Cultural connection, Social Sustainability, and Inclusion.

First, each KV was defined based on observations gathered from previous projects, a review of current literature, as well as the specific characteristics of both the project and the UC. Subsequently, each KV was translated into measurable and quantifiable elements. To achieve this, questionnaire items KVIs were formulated following strict psychometric principles. These principles include, among others, relevance to theoretical constructs, the use of clear and concise language, and the avoidance of potential sources of bias.

Balanced response scales were employed to collect data: Likert scales were used, offering a full range of possible responses (from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”). This scale allows for the collection of quantitative data that can be used for accurate and comparable statistical analysis.

The items were then refined through iterative rounds of review, which involved project partners, stakeholders, as well as experts in psychometrics. This process ensured a critical review of the items to enhance their quality and ability to accurately measure the identified Key Values.

Finally, the questionnaire was tested with a small, representative sample of the target population during a design thinking session. This phase aimed to identify and resolve any issues related to item clarity, relevance, or interpretation. The final version of the questionnaire is presented Annex F. The responses to each item are collected using a Likert scale.

As shown in Figure 70, on average the participants found the game easy to use and comfortable, and they valued its usefulness in enhancing their educational experience and in strengthening their connection with the local cultural and historical heritage. Performing the experience with other fellow students and being able to move in the park during the game were considered an added value of the experience, which they found fully available also to people with disabilities.

Figure 70. Mean KVI score for UC12.

3.4 UC13: Extended XR Museums Experience (Turin)

The trials of UC13 in Turin have all been successfully carried out in the month of March 2025 as is described in this section. The trial took place in four different museums of the city of Turin.

3.4.1 Trial 13.1 - Extended XR Museums Experience

The planning, contents and execution of the trial are illustrated below.

3.4.1.1 Pre-trial activities

The pre-trial essentially focused on measuring bitrate and latency; the complete report is included in Annex D.

3.4.1.2 Trial description

Each trial within the museums involved an average of 50 individual experiences per venue (students, professors, and museum visitors and museum personnel) resulting in a total of 220 participants. In preparation, contacts were established with local schools to organise the various participant batches. Each museum has managed the visits differently depending on time and space availability.

The infrastructure, which is based on TIM commercial network and two servers, one at the Politecnico di Torino for the AR part and one at the laboratory in TIM premises; the devices to be used in the trials include several units such as tablets, smartphones, VR headsets, and CPEs, as described in D2.2 [19]

Similarly to UC12, to ensure the effective involvement of school classes, the trial experiences of UC13 were included in the *Crescere in Città* catalogue through the creation of dedicated entries. The *Crescere in Città* catalogue is a compilation of educational and training activities presented annually by the City of Turin and ITER [22] at the beginning of each school year. It targets children, young people, and adults from schools of all levels.

Palazzo Madama and GAM

One class from the International School of Turin and one from Istituto Bosso Monti took part in the trial at Palazzo Madama. One class from Istituto Mazzarello participated in the trial at GAM, while two different classes from Istituto Bodoni Paravia were involved in both trials. The experiences were in English language only; therefore, schools were selected to guarantee that users had appropriate language skills. Additional coordination efforts were undertaken during the preparatory phase of the trial. These included a detailed presentation of the

experience to the schools, the organisation of student groups for each class, and the management of consent forms prepared by CROSEU, all in close collaboration with the institution.

The detailed planning of the trial is outlined in Table 15.

Table 15. Planning for Trial 13.1.

T = Trial Day	Activities
T- 90 days	Perform Field Trial
T- 70 days	Prepare detailed scenario and demo video
T- 50 days	Send invitation with agenda, scenario and video link to selected schools
T- 30 days	Send first reminder to participants
T- 30 days	Prepare list of devices and network connections
T- 30 days	Prepare questionnaires for KVI
T- 15 days	Send second reminder to schools and perform second field trial
T- 1 day	Bring and test devices and network onsite and perform third field trial
T	Trial with KPI, KVI and picture/video capture
T+ 10 days	Produce videos

The same approach has been followed for both museums, consisting in immersive, monographic visits focused on two iconic artworks: *Il Castello di Rivoli* (The Castle of Rivoli) by Giovanni Paolo Panini at Palazzo Madama, and the *Ploughing* (l'Aratura) by Fortunato Depero at GAM (see Figure 71).

Figure 71. Castello di Rivoli (Palazzo Madama) and the Ploughing (GAM).

The Trial unfolded in six phases:

- Phase 1 (Introduction):** This phase introduced participants to the experience. The staff provided each group with the necessary information and materials to begin the adventure. Each group, consisting of up to three people, chose a team name, which was added to the leaderboard. School groups, which had arrived together, were previously asked to complete an informational and consent form. They were welcomed in a museum room, where the organizers explained the use and potential risks of AI and introduced the activity. This aligned with the AI Act's literacy requirement, which mandates that users be informed about potential "AI hallucinations"—though, fortunately, none occurred during the experience. The school groups were then divided into pairs. Each pair received a tablet connected to a 5G network, along with two headphones equipped with microphones.

- Phase 2 (Pre-show):** The actual visit was preceded by an introductory video about the artwork, displayed on the tablet. At the end of the video, a window appeared on the tablet featuring the virtual guide powered by generative AI (see Figure 72). In the case of *Il Castello di Rivoli* at Palazzo Madama, the AI guide took the form of Filippo Juvarra, the renowned architect whose designs for Rivoli Castle inspired Panini's artwork. For *The Ploughing*, the AI guide appeared as Filippo Tommaso Marinetti, the Italian poet, writer, playwright, and soldier best known as the founder of Futurism—the first Italian avant-garde movement of the 20th century. In addition to drawing data from general databases (e.g., Wikipedia), these virtual guides were also trained on specific documents related to the artworks and their authors. Students could interact freely with the AI guide, asking any type of question to deepen their understanding or satisfy their curiosity. At the end of the interaction, the guide asked whether visitors had any further questions and then invited them to proceed to the location of the artworks.

Figure 72. AI Agents: Filippo Juvarra and Filippo Tommaso Marinetti.

- Phase 3 (The AR experience):** This phase was designed to allow visitors to explore the artwork in greater depth. It begins as visitors move to the room where the piece is located, guided by instructions on the tablet. Upon reaching the artwork, they are invited to scan a QR code that launches the AR application on the tablet, enabling them to examine the piece's details (as in the case of *Il Castello di Rivoli*). At GAM, visitors first stop in front of a figurative work—*Dintorni di Rivara* by Carlo Pittara—before arriving at *The Ploughing*, which is the focus of the experience. The AR experience provides enriched content such as audio, video, detailed visual expansions, and 3D representations. In the case of *The Ploughing*, visitors must complete a puzzle game. For *Il Castello di Rivoli*, Juvarra prompts visitors to discover hidden details: the painting is divided into six sections, and in each, players must identify all the hidden elements (see Figure 73). At the end of the experience, the visitor closes the AR application and the virtual guide asks for the last time if there are any remaining questions before concluding the session.

Figure 73. AR Puzzle Game on the Ploughing.

- Phase 4 (The VR experience):** This phase was designed to place the artwork within its broader artistic and historical context. It began immediately after the AR phase, allowing visitors to seamlessly continue the tour by entering a metaverse room created using the Mozilla Hubs platform. In this virtual space, they encountered artworks, videos, and images closely related to the piece previously explored. At this point, the organizing staff collected the tablets and headphones and assisted visitors in putting on the VR headsets and controllers. Each participant selected an avatar and entered the metaverse, where the visit could be experienced individually or in groups of up to four people. Nearby avatars could interact and comment on the displayed works. In the case of The Ploughing, the virtual gallery featured pieces by artists from the same Futurist movement as Fortunato Depero. Visitors were invited to select five artworks, which were then arranged in a personalized virtual room accessible online via a link sent by email. For Il Castello di Rivoli, visitors could admire four paintings representing the façades of Rivoli Castle, based on Juvarra's designs and his vision of how the building was intended to appear. At the GAM experience, visitors were asked to select five paintings that impressed them the most. These were used to create a personalized gallery where they could view the artworks, listen to accompanying audio, and read interpretive notes (see Figure 74). After 10–15 minutes, the experience concluded, and the headsets were collected.

Figure 74. VR Experience: Virtual Galleries.

- Phase 5 (Quiz):** At the end of the VR visit, visitors took part in a multiple-choice quiz based on the content of the experience. A leaderboard displaying the visitors' scores was then created. The quiz consisted of 10 multiple-choice questions related to the material presented during the visit (see Figure 75). The faster participants responded, the more points they earned. All questions were drawn from information provided throughout the experience, encouraging careful listening and attention to detail. At the end of each class session, the pair with the highest score was announced as the winner and received a multi-museum pass as a prize.

Figure 75. Quiz at GAM.

- **Phase 6 (Satisfaction Questionnaire and Conclusion of the Experience):** At the end of the experience, each group was handed a satisfaction questionnaire containing a set of qualitative questions based on KVIs. A designated space—such as a table—was provided to allow group members to discuss and agree on their responses collaboratively.

In addition to the virtual tour, a guided visit led by a museum guide was also offered, following the same itinerary as the virtual experience but without the use of electronic devices. This allowed visitors to compare the virtual tour with a traditional museum visit.

Museo del Risorgimento and Museo Pietro Micca

For the trial at Museo del Risorgimento were involved students from IIS Bodoni Paravia and International School of Turin. The initial presentation of the trial and the VR experience were both in Italian and in English, during two different rounds of the trial, based on school involved.

For the trial at Museo Pietro Micca were involved students from IIS Bodoni Paravia and Istituto Cottini. In this case the initial presentation of the trial and the VR experience were only in Italian, but the VR experience was available also in English.

Extensive coordination efforts were made during the preparatory phase of both trials. These involved preparing the presentation of each trial in detail to the participating schools, organizing student groups and handling consent forms in close collaboration with the educational institution. Additionally, coordination took place with the museum directors and related staff to prepare the rooms designated for the trial, including setting up chairs and tables to accommodate the hardware required for the experience.

3.4.1.3 Trial execution and results

The Trial 13.1 took place on different dates: at Palazzo Madama on 13/3/2025, at Museo del Risorgimento and GAM on 17/3/2025 and at Museo Pietro Micca on 24/3/2025. The total number of visitors who realized the experiences was 220. The devices that were used are listed in Table 16.

Table 16. Devices used in Trial 13.1.

Time	Tablets	VR Headsets	Laptops	CPEs
Palazzo Madama	13	12	3	2
GAM	13	12	3	2
Museo del Risorgimento	0	4	4	2
Museo Pietro Micca	0	3	3	2

The network parameters and summary for the UC13 Turin trial are shown in Table 17 and Table 18.

Table 17. Network setup parameters for Trial 13.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Trial_1, ..., _6
Radio access technology	5G NR Rel-15
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	mMIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
Device type	PC
Device number	1
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	Commercial

Table 18. Summary for Trial 13.1.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	13.1
Trial setup IDs	Trial_1, Trial_2, Trial_3, Trial_4, Trial_5, Trial_6
Facility/Site	Palazzo Madama, GAM, Museo del Risorgimento, Museo Pietro Micca
Objective	Measure bitrate and latency
Description	Several persons, with various devices
Executed by	M. Mazzaglia (CROSEU), A. Basso (CROSEU, F. Della Betta (TIM), Claudio Barsi (TIM)
Components involved	VR Headsets, CPEs, Laptops, Tablets
Targeted KPIs	Downlink, Uplink, Latency
Measurement tools	Speed-test by Ookla, PCap,
Ethics requirements implementation	An introduction to AI and its possible misfunctions was given to the relevant groups before the experience
Involvement of beta-users	None

Palazzo Madama and GAM

The trials took place in Turin at Palazzo Madama on 13/03/2025, from 10 am to 5 pm, and at GAM on 17/03/2024, from 11 am to 3 pm. In total, 46 students aged 15-16 and 2 teachers were involved in the trial at

Palazzo Madama, while 34 students aged 15-16 were involved in the trial at GAM, for a total of 80 participants divided into 39 groups.

Participants were selected with the support of COTO and the schools involved. Parental consent was obtained for minors, and GDPR has been signed by all participants. Participants were recruited to test both the technological capabilities and the gamified educational objectives of the project. Refreshments were available throughout the event for participants. The trial agenda at Palazzo Madama is presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Trial Agenda at Palazzo Madama.

Time	Agenda of Trial at Palazzo Madama (13/03/2025)
10:00	Arrival of International School of Turin and welcome at the ticket office, bag and coat drop-off
10:15	Introduction to the Experience and AI information, team formation and distribution of tablets and headphones
10:30	Start of the experience in the Sala Feste First iteration with AI Agent (Juarra) with tablets
10:40	Second iteration with tablets in front of the Panini painting
11:00	Collection of tablets and headphones
11:00	CONTROL VISIT No. 1
11:10	Start of experience with headsets + quiz + questionnaire on the veranda (10 headset stations) for all groups
11:30	CONTROL VISIT No. 2
11:30	Conclusion of the experience for International School of Turin – KVI Survey
12:00	Refreshment and Break
13:00	Arrival of Istituto Bosso Monti and welcome at the ticket office, bag and coat drop-off
13:15	Introduction to the Experience and AI information, team formation and distribution of tablets and headphones
13:30	Start of the experience in the Sala Feste – First iteration with AI Agent (Juarra) with tablets
13:40	Second iteration with tablets in front of the Panini painting
14:00	Collection of tablets and headphones
14:10	Start of experience with headsets + quiz + questionnaire on the veranda (10 headset stations) for all groups
14:30	Conclusion of the experience for the International School of Turin – KVI Survey
15:00	Refreshment
15:00	Arrival of Istituto Bodoni Paravia and welcome at the ticket office, bag and coat drop-off
15:15	Introduction to the Experience and AI information, team formation and distribution of tablets and headphones
15:30	Start of the experience in the Sala Feste – First iteration with AI Agent (Juarra) - with tablets
15:40	Second iteration with tablets in front of the Panini painting
15:40	CONTROL VISIT No. 3

16:00	Collection of tablets and headphones
16:10	Start of experience with headsets + quiz + questionnaire on the veranda (10 headset stations) for all groups
16:30	Conclusion of the experience for the International School of Turin – KVI Questionnaires
16:30	CONTROL VISIT No. 4
17:00	Refreshment

The trial agenda at GAM is presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Trial Agenda at GAM.

Time	Agenda of Trial at GAM (17/03/2025)
11:30	Arrival of Istituto Bodoni Paravia and welcome at the ticket office, bag and coat drop-off
11:45	Introduction to the Experience and AI information, team formation and distribution of tablets and headphones
12:00	Start of the experience – First iteration with AI Agent (Marinetti) - with tablets
12:15	Second iteration with tablets in front of Pittara painting
12:30	Third iteration with tables in front of Depero painting
12:45	Collection of tablets and headphones
12:45	CONTROL VISIT No. 1
12:50	Start of experience with headsets + quiz + questionnaire on the veranda (10 headset stations) for all groups
13:30	CONTROL VISIT No. 2
14:00	Conclusion of the experience for Istituto Bodoni Paravia – KVI Survey
14:00	Refreshment and Break
14:00	Arrival of Istituto Mazzarello and welcome at the ticket office, bag and coat drop-off
14:15	Introduction to the Experience and AI information, team formation and distribution of tablets and headphones
14:30	Start of the experience – First iteration with AI Agent (Marinetti) - with tablets
14:40	Second iteration with tablets in front of Pittara painting
14:50	Third iteration with tables in front of Depero painting
15:00	Collection of tablets and headphones
15:10	Start of experience with headsets + quiz + questionnaire on the veranda (10 headset stations) for all groups
15:00	Conclusion of the experience for Istituto Mazzarello – KVI Survey
15:00	Refreshment and Break

Selected pictures of the Trial at Palazzo Madama are provided in Figure 76.

Figure 76. Pictures from the Trial 13.1 at Palazzo Madama.

Selected pictures of the Trial at GAM are provided in Figure 77.

Figure 77. Pictures from the Trial 13.1 at GAM.

To evaluate the trial, organizers employed a dual approach. Participants completed detailed surveys assessing their engagement (see Figure 78), the quality of their experience, and the perceived value of the AR and VR components. Additionally, control visits were organized, consisting of a traditional guided tour without technological enhancements. This comparison aimed to measure the added value of immersive technologies in cultural and educational experiences. The trial setup, relying on high-speed 5G networks, showcased the potential for integrating next-generation connectivity into gamified, location-based learning experiences.

Figure 78. Participants filling questionnaire for experience evaluation.

Museo del Risorgimento and Museo Pietro Micca

The trials took place in Turin at Museo del Risorgimento on 17/03/2025, from 10.30 to 18:00. In the morning, the trial involved 40 high-school students (15 to 17 years old) from 2 different schools and 3 teachers, while in the afternoon around 60 visitors (from the general public) and museum personnel. The trial went smoothly and consisted of various phases (about an hour's experience in total for each school) on the Sala Plebisciti of the museum (Figure 79):

- **Phase 1:** Opening-onboarding by TIM with an explanation of TrialsNet and instructions to use the VR headsets and steps of the trial
- **Phase 2:** the VR visit centers on the Chamber of Deputies and features a voice-guided tour and a multiple-choice quiz with historical figures posing questions. Two difficulty levels suit different age groups, and correct answers unlock digital rewards.

Figure 79. VR phase at Museo del Risorgimento.

- **Phase 3:** After the VR experience it took place the traditional physical tour, including also the visit of Parlamento Subalpino (extraordinary opening), with a museum guide (control visit, 3 tours only for the schools) (see Figure 80).

Figure 80. Control Visit at Museo del Risorgimento.

- **Phase 4:** After the control visit, to assess the trial's impact, participants were asked to complete a questionnaire (the KVI questionnaire) evaluating the level of engagement, the overall quality of the experience, the perceived value of the VR experience. (Figure 81)

Figure 81. Control Visit and KVI questionnaire at Museo del Risorgimento.

The following devices were used according to the setup depicted in Figure 82:

- 8 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the VR museum experience) including 4 spares for recharge, connected via Wi-Fi to 2 5G CPE router.
- 2 5G ZTE CPE in the Sala Plebisciti of the museum
- 4 laptops connected via Wi-Fi to 2 5G CPE router.

Figure 82. Trial devices used at Museo del Risorgimento.

At Museo Pietro Micca the trial took place on 24/03/2025, from 9 am to 4 pm, involving 40 high-school students (15 to 17 years old) from 2 different schools and 6 teachers and 8 museum guides. The trial went smoothly and consisted of various phases (about an hour's experience in total for each school) on the basement (welcome and trial explanation) and ground floor (VR experience) of the museum.

- **Phase 1:** Opening/onboarding by TIM with an explanation of TrialsNet and instructions to use the VR headsets and steps of the trial (Figure 83).

Figure 83. Opening/onboarding at Museo Pietro Micca.

- **Phase 2:** voice guided VR tour of underground tunnels. Starting from a VR reconstruction of the Pietro Micca underground tunnels, the virtual visit offers a headset-guided experience supported by a voice assistant. Visitors can explore the galleries, interact with 3D objects, and receive both technical and historical guidance. The tour begins with a 3D model of the Citadel of Turin, a pentagonal Savoy fortress along the city's ancient walls, from which users can teleport to various cultural points of interest (Figure 84).

Figure 84. VR phase at Museo Pietro Micca.

- **Phase 3:** After the VR experience it took place the traditional physical tour, including also the underground tunnels (Figure 85) with two museum guides (control visit, 4 tours).

Figure 85. Control Visit at Museo Pietro Micca.

- **Phase 4:** After the control visit, to assess the trial's impact, participants were asked to complete a questionnaire (the KVI questionnaire) evaluating the level of engagement, the overall quality of the experience, the perceived value of the VR experience (Figure 86).

Figure 86. KVI questionnaires at Museo Pietro Micca.

The following devices were used according to the setup depicted in Figure 87:

- 6 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the VR museum experience) including 3 spares for recharge, connected via Wi-Fi to 2 5G CPE router.
- 2 5G ZTE CPE in the Sala Plebisciti of the museum.
- 3 laptops connected via Wi-Fi to 2 5G CPE router.

Figure 87. Trial devices deployment at Museo Pietro Micca.

KPIs

In the context of **Palazzo Madama and GAM**, during the trials the KPI#1 (Downlink throughput per user), including at peak traffic at start-up, KPI#2 (Uplink throughput speed per user), and KPI#8 (Application round-trip latency) have been measured. Given the similarity between the trials at the two museums, the measurements results are provided jointly in Table 21, both as the average and peak for about 80 users. For the AR part two persons were using the same tablet, while 3 to 6 persons were using different VR devices simultaneously.

Table 21. Measurements results for Trial 13.1 (Palazzo Madama and GAM).

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
13.1_Trial_1 (AR part, average) Palazzo Madama	KPI#01 > 50 kbps KPI#02 > 50 kbps KPI#08 < 100 ms	KPI#01 (avg.): 265 kbps KPI#02 (avg.): 227 kbps KPI#08 (avg.): 21ms	OK
13.1_Trial_2 (AR part, peak) Palazzo Madama	KPI#01 > 50 kbps KPI#02 > 50 kbps KPI#08 < 100 ms	KPI#01 (peak): 299 kbps KPI#02 (peak): 261 kbps KPI#08 (peak): 31 ms	OK
13.1_Trial_3 (VR part, average) GAM	KPI#01 > 0.5 Mbps KPI#02 > 100 kbps KPI#03 > 6 Mbps KPI#08 < 100 ms	KPI#01 (avg.): 1.1 Mbps KPI#02 (avg.): 218 kbps KPI#03 (avg.): 9.7 Mbps KPI#08 (avg.): 27 ms	OK
13.1_Trial_4 (VR part, peak) GAM	KPI#01 > 0.5 Mbps KPI#02 > 100 kbps KPI#03 > 6 Mbps KPI#08 < 100 ms	KPI#01 (avg.): 4.2 Mbps KPI#02 (avg.): 228 kbps KPI#03 (avg.): 13 Mbps KPI#08 (avg.): 50 ms	OK

Regarding **Museo del Risorgimento and Museo Pietro Micca**, during the trials the KPI#1 (Downlink throughput per user), KPI#2 (Uplink throughput speed per user), KPI#3 (Downlink aggregate throughput) and KPI#4 (Uplink aggregate throughput) have been measured. Given that similarity between the trials at the two museums, the measurements results are provided jointly in Table 22: from 3 (in Museo Pietro Micca) to 4 persons (in Museo del Risorgimento) were using VR headsets simultaneously.

Table 22. Measurements results for Trial 13.1 (Museo del Risorgimento and Pietro Micca).

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
13.1_Trial_5 (Museo del Risorgimento)	KPI#01: 1 Mbps KPI#02 : 0,5 Mbps KPI#03: 4 Mbps	KPI#01: 1,2 Mbps KPI#02: 0,6 Mbps KPI#03: 5 Mbps	OK

	KPI#04: 2 Mbps	KPI#04: 2,5 Mbps	
13.1_Trial_6 (Museo Pietro Micca)	KPI#01: 1 Mbps KPI#02: 0,5 Mbps KPI#03: 3 Mbps KPI#04: 1,5 Mbps	KPI#01: 1,3 Mbps KPI#02: 0,8 Mbps KPI#03: 4,3 Mbps KPI#04: 1,7 Mbps	OK

KVIs

These KVIs have been measured on a Likert scale from 1 to 5. Control groups with almost the same number of visitors have been also set up. The questions address the KV of Availability, Acceptance, Edutainment, Cultural connection, and Economic sustainability. Given the similarity of the experiences between Palazzo Madama and GAM and that between Museo del Risorgimento and Museo Pietro Micca, their data are presented as integrated.

The complete KVIs questionnaire submitted to the participants in the four trials is detailed in Annex F, whereby responses to each item were collected using a Likert scale ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”.

The total number of valid questionnaires collected from the four museums was 193. The results indicated that the target of 70% appreciation was achieved across all KVIs (Figure 88). Additionally, the percentage of participants with an average KVI score above 3 ranged over 80%, except for the "intention to buy" metric which is nevertheless over the established target of 70% (Figure 89). This exception can likely be attributed to the young age of the participants, who were students between 15 and 18 years old with limited spending capability.

Figure 88. Mean KVI score.

Figure 89. % of participants with average KVI.

Furthermore, the questionnaires reveal that the experience with digital devices was not significantly better than the control condition (museum tours led by guides). This suggests that while an AI guide and digital devices It may serve as a valuable support tool, they would not replace a human guide (see Figure 90 and Figure 91).

Figure 90. Mean KVI score compared to guided tour.

Figure 91. % of participants with average KVI compared to guided tour.

Two further sets of analyses were performed on the data from the experiences at Palazzo Madama and GAM. First, the potential for mapping Key Performance Indicators to Key Values was investigated, to verify whether specific KPIs could significantly predict certain KVIs. Regression analyses were conducted, with each analysis treating one KVI (Availability, Acceptance, Edutainment, Cultural Connection, Economical Sustainability, Inclusion) as the dependent variable and all KPIs related to the AR/VR experience (downlink throughput per user, uplink throughput per user, downlink aggregate throughput, round-trip latency) as independent variables.

The results revealed no significant predictive relationships. As it was observed for UC12, this outcome can be attributed to the technology's architecture, which leverages local caching and streamlines asset sizes to maintain stability despite minor changes in download speed. This approach helps mitigate the effects of network variability, delivering steady performance and minimizing the chances of user-detectable issues during technology use, even under fluctuating network conditions.

3.5 UC13: Extended XR Museums Experience (Athens)

3.5.1 Trial 13.2 - Extended XR Museums Experience

Following the initial pre-trial activities reported in D5.2 [2], which were conducted in controlled lab environments at WINGS premises, UC13 has progressed to live field trials utilizing commercial 5G networks. The trial

for this use case was held by WINGS in collaboration with DAEM. This transition from lab to real-world settings allowed thorough evaluation of the system's performance, user experience, and overall impact in an authentic cultural heritage context, providing valuable insights to guide future deployment and scalability. The results are reported in the next sections.

3.5.1.1 Pre-trial activities

The activities related to the pre-trial of the UC are detailed in Annex E.

3.5.1.2 Trial description

The trial for this use case was held on 12/06/2025 within Technopolis, Athens. This setting was selected to provide a realistic and engaging environment for testing immersive AR and VR experiences aimed at enhancing cultural and historical engagement. A total of 30 participants took part in the trial, including ten representatives from the Municipality personnel, public safety agents, project team members, and participants from research institutions.

The day began with a comprehensive introduction to the TrialsNet project, outlining its vision, objectives, and the significance of the use cases under evaluation. Following this, the team presented detailed overviews of the AR and VR applications developed for this use case, emphasizing their potential to transform visitor experiences at cultural heritage sites. The participants experienced:

- The virtual tour of the Corinth Canal Museum, allowing navigation within a detailed 3D digital replica.
- The AR digital guide for the Parthenon, enabling users to place and explore a realistic 3D model within their physical surroundings.
- The VR immersive reconstruction of the Parthenon, offering an interactive exploration of the monument as it appeared centuries ago.

These applications were demonstrated live, with participants utilizing mobile devices and VR headsets using the commercial 5G network for connectivity. Throughout the trial, system performance was continuously monitored via Grafana dashboards, providing real-time analytics on data transmission, application latency, and user interaction metrics. Concurrently, participants completed structured questionnaires to assess usability, cultural engagement, accessibility, and educational impact.

The trial successfully demonstrated the seamless integration of cutting-edge AR/VR technologies with next-generation B5G connectivity in a real-world cultural context. Feedback gathered during the event will inform further refinements, while the performance data underscores the solution's readiness for broader deployment in museums and heritage sites.

3.5.1.3 Trial execution and results

The trial was successfully executed at Technopolis, Athens. During the event, participants actively engaged with the AR and VR applications (see Figure 92 and Figure 93), while system performance and user feedback were collected and analysed.

Figure 92. VR experience during the Trial 13.2.

Figure 93. VR and AR applications during the Trial 13.2.

KPIs

Technical performance was assessed through multiple KPIs, focusing on network and application responsiveness, such as KPI#01 (Downlink Throughput per User), KPI#08 (Application Round-Trip Latency), and KPI#09 (Application One-Way Latency).

Real-time monitoring dashboards powered by Grafana tracked these KPIs throughout the trial, confirming that the B5G connectivity supported the high demands of immersive technologies under real-world conditions.

During the trial at Technopolis, a total of 9,615 network measurements were collected, offering a comprehensive view of the system’s performance in a live environment. The average round-trip latency recorded was approximately 298 milliseconds (KPI#08) (Figure 94), indicating low network response times that support near real-time interactivity critical for AR/VR applications. Similarly, the one-way latency (KPI#09) averaged around 149 milliseconds, reflecting efficient and timely data transmission necessary for smooth immersive experiences.

Figure 94. Average round-trip latency during Trial 13.2.

The downlink throughput per user (KPI#01) averaged 0.75 Mbps (Figure 95), demonstrating stable and sufficient bandwidth for seamless content delivery. Content chunks transferred during the trial had an average size of 0.030 MB, with a typical download duration of 1.51 seconds, ensuring rapid data access and minimizing user waiting times. The average bitrate sustained throughout the trial was approximately 92.1 Kbps, providing a moderate but steady data flow that enabled consistent and smooth streaming of standard-definition media content.

Figure 95. Average download duration, average downlink throughput, and average bitrate during Trial 13.2.

Detailed analysis of the commercial 5G network performance was conducted by measuring download speeds based on file size and download duration. Two graphs illustrate these measurements collected during the trial. The first graph (Figure 96) shows the variation of download speeds over time, reflecting the network’s ability to sustain stable throughput under real-world conditions throughout the demonstration. This highlights periods of both peak and lower network performance during the trial. The second graph (Figure 97) displays the relationship between file sizes and their corresponding download speeds, confirming the network’s capability to efficiently handle varying data loads. These results further support the observed KPIs, demonstrating that the commercial 5G connectivity provided reliable and consistent data transmission necessary for seamless AR/VR streaming. These metrics, confirm that the commercial 5G network provided reliable and high-quality connectivity, adequately meeting the demanding requirements of the use case and enhancing the overall user experience.

Figure 96. Variation of download speeds over time during Trial 13.2.

Figure 97. Relationship between file sizes and their corresponding download speeds during Trial 13.2.

To provide a comprehensive overview of the field trial execution, Table 23 presents the network setup parameters, while Table 24 summarizes the trial, including objectives, components involved, targeted KPIs, and measurement tools. The detailed KPI measurement results are reported in Table 25, offering a clear view of the system’s performance during the UC13 field trial.

Table 23. Network setup parameters for Trial 13.2.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field
Radio access technology	5G NR
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA

Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	-
Sub-carrier spacing	-
MIMO	-
Duplex mode	-
Device number	1
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None

Table 24. Summary for Trial 13.2.

UC11 Trial summary	
Trial ID	13.2
Trial setup ID	Field
Facility/Site	Technopolis of Athens (DAEM)
Objective	Assess the technical performance and real-world impact of the system.
Description	Evaluation of the effectiveness of the immersive technology solution in enhancing cultural and historical engagement, assessment of the system's usability, impact, and real-world applicability. Validation of the system's performance and determination of its potential for broader deployment in cultural and historical settings.
Executed by	WINGS
Components involved	Analytics
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink Throughput per User) KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) KPI#09 (Application One-Way Latency)
Measurement tools	Windows Task Manager, iPerf, Grafana

Table 25. Measurement results from Trial 13.2.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
13.2_Field01_1	KPI#01: 50Mbps KPI#08: 80-100ms KPI#09: 50ms	KPI#01: 0.750 Mbps KPI#08: 298ms KPI#09: 149ms	Requirements not met due to 5G NSA setup. Expected to be achieved under 5G SA

The UC13 trial was executed using a 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) network configuration. Under these conditions, the measured KPI values did not fully meet the predefined target requirements, particularly with respect to latency. It is anticipated that when the trial is conducted on a 5G Standalone (SA) network, which provides significantly lower latency and enhanced performance, the targeted KPI requirements will be achieved. Accordingly, future testing on 5G SA infrastructure is planned to validate compliance with these performance objectives.

KVIs

Beyond technical metrics, the trial evaluated the solution's impact on users via Key Value Indicators, derived from a structured questionnaire (detailed in Annex F) completed by 30 participants post-interaction. These KVIs included Cultural Connection, Digital Inclusion, Acceptability, User Experience, Trustworthiness, and Edutainment.

The responses were collected using a Likert scale (1–5), providing quantitative insight into participants' perceptions and the solution's success in enriching cultural visits (Figure 98).

Figure 98. KVI results from UC13 (Athens) field trials.

More specifically, the field trials and live demonstrations received highly positive feedback across all KVIs, reflecting strong user engagement, trust, and satisfaction with the experience. In particular:

- **Cultural Connection:** The highest average score of 4.7 was observed in cultural connection, with 100% of participants indicating strong resonance. Users felt that the app content respectfully reflected cultural diversity, acknowledged individual cultural backgrounds, and promoted cultural understanding. This highlights the effectiveness of the apps in fostering meaningful cultural engagement and inclusivity.
- **Digital Inclusion:** The apps demonstrated strong digital accessibility, scoring an average of 4.2 and 100% in participants with average scores above 3. Participants reported that the apps were usable regardless of their technological experience, functioned well on slower internet connections, and did not require expensive devices. Clear, non-technical guidance and adequate support further enhanced inclusivity, making the cultural content accessible to a broad audience.
- **Acceptability:** Acceptability ratings were equally impressive, with an average of 4.6 and 100% positive participant ratings. Users found the apps easy to use and welcoming, with accessible design and layout that met their expectations effectively. This suggests that the applications successfully addressed diverse user needs, supporting comfortable and sustained engagement.
- **User Experience:** The applications scored an average of 4.5 in user experience, with a perfect 100% of participants rating their experience positively (>3). Participants highlighted the intuitive navigation, visually appealing interface, and clear instructions. The low incidence of technical issues further contributed to a smooth and enjoyable experience, encouraging users to spend time exploring the apps.
- **Trustworthiness:** Participants expressed a high level of trust in the applications, with an average trust score of 4.6 out of 5 and 97% of participants rating their trust above 3. Users felt confident that the app functioned reliably and that the content was credible and accurate, indicating strong faith in the technical stability and information integrity of the digital tour guide and immersive experiences.
- **Edutainment:** Combining education and entertainment, the apps scored an average of 4.5 with 100% positive ratings. Users enjoyed the interactive, engaging educational content and felt motivated to continue learning through the applications. The balance of fun and learning was well appreciated, making the experience both informative and enjoyable.

Overall, the applications successfully enhanced visitors' cultural experiences through immersive technology. The results demonstrate that the apps not only provide reliable and trustworthy digital content but also deliver an inclusive, engaging, and culturally sensitive experience. These findings support the potential of such technologies to transform museum visits by making cultural heritage accessible, educational, and entertaining for diverse audiences.

4 Considerations on Use Cases deployment

For the transition from trial activities to the broader deployment of innovative services in the CTE domain, a critical re-assessment of the use case results is essential. While the 5G NSA and 5G SA networks used in the trials successfully supported advanced user experiences across sports, airport services, cultural heritage, and museums, in some cases under optimized conditions, with limited numbers of concurrent users or specialized setups, the key challenge ahead lies in scaling these solutions to accommodate the complexity and diversity of large audiences and public environments.

This section examines the main factors influencing the commercial viability of the WP5 use cases, highlighting both the strengths demonstrated during the trials and the limitations that exceed the current capabilities of 5G. A scalability analysis is presented for each use case to identify specific performance improvements, network functionalities, and deployment aspects that 6G technologies will need to address to enable seamless, sustainable, and city-wide adoption in culture, tourism, and entertainment contexts.

4.1 UC10: Immersive Fan Engagement

UC10 focuses on transforming live sports experiences by delivering immersive, low-latency 360° VR streams to fans both at home (via VR headsets or smartphones for a front-row perspective) and in-stadium (through augmented views and real-time analytics). Following lab validation at the 5TONIC facility, a full-scale trial took place at Madrid's Movistar Arena in March 2025 during basketball games, where immersive 180° and 360° cameras were installed on the court and tested with beta users. All KPIs were successfully achieved, paving the way for commercial adoption

4.1.1 Performance requirements

The integration of B5G was expected to deliver low latency, eliminating annoying delays. Users benefited from higher resolution, offering crystal-clear visuals. Stable connection with minimal to no buffering, ensuring smooth, uninterrupted viewing for a truly enhanced experience. Trials were designed to test limitations and capabilities of B5G in real-world scenarios, ensuring it meets the rigorous demands of immersive VR sports experiences.

4.1.2 Network functionalities

The real-time nature of immersive VR streaming required robust and intelligent network functionalities. Protocols such as SRTs optimized video delivery, supporting retransmissions without noticeable buffering or degradation of quality.

To preserve a consistent experience, the system incorporated reliable mechanisms. If temporary disconnections occurred, adaptive bitrate streaming and local edge buffering ensured continuity without service interruptions. Dynamic resource allocation was also critical, as peak moments (e.g., game highlights) triggered simultaneous access from thousands of users.

Network slicing proved valuable by dedicating bandwidth to different service layers: immersive VR streams, in-stadium augmented feeds, and real-time analytics. This ensured prioritization of latency-sensitive traffic and minimized the risk of degraded experiences.

A hybrid distribution of computational tasks between edge and cloud was implemented. Edge processing enabled real-time rendering optimizations and motion-to-photon synchronization, while cloud services handled advanced analytics and social VR features.

4.1.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

UC10 combined edge and cloud computing to balance latency-critical rendering and large-scale data management. Edge nodes deployed within the stadium handled live encoding, synchronization of VR feeds, and fast content delivery, while the cloud platform supported central coordination, fan community features, and archival storage.

Multiple 180° and 360° cameras were installed at strategic court positions, capturing immersive perspectives and transmitting them through the B5G network. A dedicated mobile app enabled fans in the venue to access

augmented views, replays, and player stats in real time, complementing the immersive VR streams available to remote users.

Device interoperability was ensured across VR headsets, smartphones, and stadium displays. Data security and privacy policies governed the handling of user data, particularly for social VR features, with strong encryption applied to both video and interaction streams.

4.1.4 Other aspects

User experience and engagement were central to UC10. Beta users rated the VR and AR services highly, with particular emphasis on the sense of presence, quality of video, and responsiveness of the system. Feedback highlighted the potential to redefine fan experiences by bridging physical and digital engagement.

Digital inclusion was considered by offering multi-device support and varying levels of immersion. Users with VR headsets enjoyed full 360° experiences, while smartphone users accessed augmented perspectives such as multi-camera views and dynamic angle switching, ensuring broad accessibility and engagement across different user groups.

Future enhancements will add immersive social features, allowing fans to gather in virtual lounges, share live reactions, and interact with one another during games. These elements transformed passive viewing into an interactive and communal experience.

From a sustainability perspective, adaptive streaming reduced unnecessary data transmission, and edge processing minimized the energy footprint by reducing cloud dependency.

Strong collaboration with ERC, TID, and venue stakeholders ensured that the trials aligned with operational needs and commercial feasibility.

4.1.5 Final observations

The UC10 trials validated the potential of immersive VR and AR solutions to revolutionize live sports experiences, achieving strong performance in connectivity, video quality, and user satisfaction. Real-world deployment confirmed that 5G can support demanding immersive media applications, although stability in latency and jitter remains an area for improvement.

The results highlight the role of advanced network functionalities, such as network slicing, dynamic resource allocation, and hybrid edge-cloud architectures, in enabling seamless, large-scale fan engagement. UC10 also demonstrated the commercial potential of in-venue augmented services and immersive social features, supporting new business models for sports organizations and broadcasters.

Looking ahead, further optimization of latency and jitter, coupled with the integration of 6G capabilities such as enhanced edge intelligence, will unlock the next stage of immersive fan experiences.

4.2 UC11: Service Robots for Enhanced Passenger's Experience

The deployment of AI-enabled service robots for enhancing passenger' experiences in smart airports is guided by insights gathered during trials, focusing on User Experience, Acceptability, Digital Inclusion, Resource Optimization, and Operational Efficiency. These metrics provide the foundation for scaling the solution from controlled trials to widespread commercial implementation. Key considerations are reported in the following.

4.2.1 Performance requirements

The successful deployment of UC11 relies on stable, low-latency connectivity to support real-time video streaming, teleoperation, and user interaction with the AI-driven service robots.

During trials, uplink throughput of approximately 5 Mbps per robot was necessary to ensure smooth, continuous video streaming from the robots to the backend. Downlink throughput needs were lower, with around 2 Mbps per robot sufficient for control signals and UI (User Interface) synchronization. RTT averaged 20–25 ms for low-data (MQTT) traffic and 25–30 ms during video streaming, with occasional spikes above 40 ms. To maintain responsive interaction and safety, an RTT of ≤ 30 ms is preferred. However, jitter (latency variation) was

noticeable across data types, occasionally affecting system responsiveness. A jitter target of ≤ 10 ms is recommended for smooth teleoperation and consistent video quality.

While 5G supported trial operations effectively, further stability, especially in latency and jitter, will be essential for large-scale deployment in dynamic airport environments.

4.2.2 Network functionalities

The overall system operated without major issues during the trial. Although some transmission errors were detected in the byte packages, the system protocols successfully corrected them without affecting the user experience.

The deployment of UC11 in a live airport environment highlights the need for robust and intelligent network functionalities to support seamless human-robot interaction. Given the real-time nature of services, such as voice communication, video streaming, and teleoperation, low latency and jitter optimization are essential to ensure safe and responsive operation.

To maintain reliable connectivity, the system must incorporate fault-tolerant mechanisms. In cases of temporary disconnection or network degradation, fallback options, such as edge processing or redundant paths, are necessary to preserve functionality without compromising user experience or safety.

Dynamic resource allocation and intelligent load balancing are also critical, especially during peak operational hours when multiple robots and users interact simultaneously. The ability to prioritize traffic and adjust resource usage in real time helps maintain service quality.

A clear distribution of computational tasks between edge and cloud infrastructures enables more efficient operation. Latency-sensitive tasks like speech recognition or intent detection benefit from edge processing, while data-intensive analysis can be handled in the cloud to offload processing.

As the system scales to accommodate more devices and users, orchestration becomes key. The network must support seamless scalability and coordination without performance degradation. Furthermore, the use of network slicing can ensure that each service component, **robot telemetry**, voice commands, or UI interaction, receives appropriate bandwidth and quality of service guarantees.

These network capabilities are vital to ensuring that the system remains reliable, responsive, and scalable in real-world airport scenarios.

4.2.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The deployment of UC11 combined edge and cloud computing to meet the real-time processing and scalability requirements of the system. Edge components handled latency-sensitive tasks such as speech recognition, robot control, and immediate user interactions, while the cloud infrastructure was used for central coordination, data storage, and analytics.

In addition to the humanoid robots, thermal cameras were installed at key entry points of the terminal. These devices enabled temperature screening and crowd monitoring functionalities, supporting health and safety objectives in high-traffic areas. The thermal data was processed locally to ensure rapid response and was also integrated with the central dashboard for visualization and trend analysis.

Robotic platforms, high-resolution RGB cameras, thermal sensors, and the Wi.MOVE dashboard were all integrated via a secure, low-latency 5G network, ensuring continuous connectivity and smooth system coordination. Device compatibility and interoperability with airport systems were maintained throughout the setup.

Data management policies ensured the secure handling of sensitive thermal and video data. Where necessary, edge buffering was used to mitigate the impact of connectivity interruptions, while cloud storage provided redundancy and scalability.

The infrastructure is designed to be modular and extensible, allowing integration with additional proprietary systems or emerging technologies such as digital twins, AI-based anomaly detection, and expanded multi-sensor capabilities.

During the UC11 trials, 5G/B5G technology successfully supported real-time interactions between the service robots, passengers, and airport systems. However, some challenges were identified, particularly related to

latency stability and jitter, which can impact the responsiveness required for seamless human-robot interaction. While these issues were manageable at the trial scale, a full commercial deployment in a large, dynamic airport environment would require further improvements in network stability and scalability.

These findings highlight the role that future 6G technologies could play in addressing these gaps. Specifically, 6G is expected to provide ultra-low latency and deterministic communication, enhanced edge intelligence for real-time decision-making, and advanced dynamic resource allocation mechanisms. Such features would enable reliable, scalable, and efficient operation of AI-driven service robots and smart airport systems, ensuring continuous, safe, and optimized passenger services.

4.2.4 Other aspects

The UC11 deployment emphasized strong data security and user privacy, with all communications encrypted and access restricted to authorized personnel. The AI algorithms powering the humanoid robots and dashboard interfaces underwent extensive testing to ensure high accuracy in speech recognition, intent detection, and user interaction handling.

User experience and acceptability were central to the design. Trials confirmed high levels of satisfaction, with participants praising the system's intuitive interface, responsiveness, and ease of use. Notably, 100% of participants rated the system above average across all evaluated aspects, reflecting excellent adoption potential in a real-world airport setting.

Efforts were made to ensure digital inclusion, with clear instructions, multilingual support, and accessible interaction modes for users with varying levels of tech familiarity. The system also supports personalized experiences, adapting robot responses based on user queries and preferences.

From a sustainability perspective, UC11 leverages energy-efficient robotic platforms and dynamic resource allocation to minimize energy consumption, while edge processing reduces unnecessary data transmission.

Finally, the trials benefited from strong stakeholder engagement, particularly with airport personnel, ensuring alignment with operational needs and facilitating long-term integration prospects.

Looking ahead, future 6G capabilities could further strengthen these aspects by introducing enhanced privacy-preserving mechanisms, AI-native network management, and integrated sensing features. These advancements could enable even more secure data handling, seamless personalization, and improved energy efficiency, while supporting inclusive and accessible services at larger scale. Although the current UC11 deployment successfully addressed these requirements using existing 5G/B5G technologies, 6G has the potential to amplify these benefits and ensure long-term sustainability and scalability.

4.2.5 Final observations

The UC11 trials validated the deployment of AI-enabled robotic assistants and multimodal dashboards within a live airport environment, demonstrating strong performance in connectivity, reliability, and user satisfaction. Real-time interactions, secure data handling, and consistent operation under variable network conditions confirmed the system's readiness for operational use.

However, the trials also revealed critical network challenges, particularly regarding latency stability and jitter, which can impact the responsiveness required for seamless human-robot interaction. These limitations underscore the relevance of future 6G capabilities, especially in achieving ultra-low latency, deterministic communication, and enhanced edge intelligence.

Additionally, UC11 highlighted the need for dynamic resource allocation, robust orchestration, and scalability features central to the 6G vision. The integration of energy-efficient platforms, AI-driven personalization, and user-centric design further aligns the use case with future smart environment demands.

In summary, UC11 serves as a valuable step toward understanding the practical requirements and benefits of next-generation intelligent services in critical infrastructure environments, offering insights that inform both near-term 5G optimization and long-term 6G design.

4.3 UC12: City Parks in Metaverse

The large-scale trial, which involved 130 users, demonstrated the feasibility of an innovative concept: a game using AR and VR, designed to be played indoor and outdoor and to inform players about cultural and historical facts related to the heritage of a city or specific location. The analysis of Key Value Indicators confirmed that this approach is both engaging and entertaining for visitors, particularly younger generations. No technical issues were encountered during the trial, although some problems may arise in other scenarios, as illustrated in the following sections.

4.3.1 Performance requirements

As shown by the analysis of KPIs during the trial, the most resource-intensive phase on the 5G network was the VR segment, during which four players simultaneously battled the "boss" (an evil wizard).

Indeed, the VR session took place indoors and relied on cloud servers located at TIM's laboratory. While the 5G network provided a generally acceptable level of performance, it revealed limitations in sustaining the low latency and high downlink bitrate necessary for supporting a larger number of concurrent users. These constraints were particularly evident in scenarios requiring high interactivity and graphical fidelity, as noted in earlier evaluations.

In contrast, the AR app required significantly less network capacity, even during the initial phase when assets were downloaded to the device. The geo-localised AR game's performance metrics align well with its design goals. The caching approach ensures high tolerance for downlink variability, while the low uplink and latency requirements deliver a responsive and seamless user experience. The chosen architecture supports smooth gameplay across various network conditions.

The analysis of the download bitrate of a VR headset showed an average of 48 Mbps, with peaks reaching 125 Mbps. Given that the measured download bitrate at the trial site (Talent Garden) never exceeded 0.5 Gbps, the system could support only four simultaneous players—posing a limitation for potential commercial deployment. These performance levels were adequate for single-user or small-group interactions with immersive media, as demonstrated during the live trials. Moreover, besides scaling up to larger audiences with more concurrent users, also higher-quality assets (e.g., photorealistic 3D models or real-time multi-user interaction) would imply that higher throughput and lower latency will likely be required.

The round-trip latency measured during the trial was 69 ms (compared to 21 ms measured by Ookla Speedtest for the network only), exceeding the recommended limit of 20 ms, which is considered best practice to prevent motion sickness in sensitive individuals. Fortunately, none of the players reported such symptoms during the trial. From these measurements, it is not possible to single out the latency of the network itself from that of the overall infrastructure and app, which would likely be the main contributors to such high latency where attention should be devoted in future developments.

Consequently, while the current 5G infrastructure met the demands of this specific trial setup, future deployments, particularly under real-world conditions with mobility, network contention, and device diversity, will benefit from the enhanced capabilities promised by 6G networks, such as ultra-low latency, guaranteed bandwidth allocation, and context-aware network adaptation.

4.3.2 Network functionalities

The experience was structured into two distinct phases: an outdoor segment leveraging AR and an indoor segment utilizing VR.

The AR session was delivered outdoors, with cloud servers hosted at the Politecnico di Torino and connected via the public 5G network. To optimize performance, several assets were preloaded onto the users' devices at the start of the experience, significantly reducing the volume of real-time data exchanged during gameplay.

This approach, combined with a robust caching strategy, ensured a smooth and stable user experience even in the face of fluctuating network conditions. Overall, the infrastructure performed reliably throughout the AR phase. However, in future scenarios where experiences of various cultural and historical sites are offered on one

App, all assets would need to be downloaded at the start of the game, thereby requiring significantly higher bitrates.

4.3.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The infrastructure for both AR and VR segments performed in line with KPI requirements. However, an observed significant variability was observed—up to an order of magnitude—in public network bitrate across the cultural sites used in the AR experience. Although this did not impact the current trial, it could affect other games requiring constant connectivity. Thus, ensuring uniform coverage is critical for the success of similar outdoor experiences.

The system architecture was designed to be modular, scalable, and extensible. It supports integration with additional proprietary platforms and emerging technologies, including digital twins, AI-driven interactive agents, and enhanced multi-sensor capabilities. This flexibility lays the groundwork for future innovation and expansion. Looking ahead, upcoming iterations will need to incorporate advanced latency optimization strategies. These should address not only network-related challenges—such as bandwidth limitations and congestion—but also computational factors like system processing capabilities and the overall complexity of interactions. Achieving seamless performance at scale will be critical to supporting more immersive, high-fidelity, and collaborative immersive experiences.

4.3.4 Other aspects

The analysis of the 130 KVI questionnaires collected after the trial demonstrate a high satisfaction level around 80% for the criteria Availability, Acceptance, Edutainment, Cultural connection, Social sustainability, and Inclusion.

The addition of a cultural quiz with a leaderboard of the total score of the participating teams was instrumental for encouraging learning about cultural and historical aspects of the visited site. The comparison between the guided and the digital tour, showed a slightly higher preference for the latter.

The integration of cultural exploration, teamwork, and engaging mini-games was seen as a fun and innovative way to learn. The main areas for improvement mentioned by participants included technical issues with the tablets and app, such as bugs, lag, and problems with the map, which was often difficult to navigate, zoom, or follow (also due to ongoing park works). Participants also highlighted challenges with the clarity of directions and functionality of the devices, including VR headsets being somewhat uncomfortable for glasses wearers.

A secure data management policy governed the handling of player data, ensuring the protection of information generated by each team. Transition between the AR and VR segments was facilitated by a manual input system: each team entered a unique code that triggered the transfer of key AR outcomes—such as collected assets and total time spent—into the VR environment. This mechanism allowed for continuity across the two experiences and enabled personalized progression based on prior performance. To enable future integrations and automation, establishing a direct, secure connection between the AR and VR systems would eliminate manual data entry.

4.3.5 Final observations

The trial ran smoothly and was not hampered by network limitations. The KVI analysis suggests that the game's ability to blend educational and entertaining elements is central to its success, complementing traditional performance metrics and user experience indicators. However, some potential technical limitations of future developments have been identified and are reported hereafter.

Based on the gathered measurements, the public 5G network configuration used for the trial would not have been capable of supporting two concurrent groups of four players each, a setup which represents a realistic scenario for commercial applications. The main bottleneck lies in the network's inability in the configuration used for the trial to handle the required downlink traffic. Besides, the measured latency required to play the game, although remaining below the maximum threshold of 100 ms, was still significantly higher than the limit recommended to prevent motion sickness in sensitive individuals. This finding indicates that future research is needed on both the infrastructure and App to reduce round-trip travel time. Lastly, the variability of the network coverage detected in the outdoor part of the game, although did not impact the implemented experience, could pose significant challenges for more complex applications. Towards this end, 6G networks could provide the higher bitrate and lower latency for future commercial applications involving more simultaneous users.

Despite this constraint, the trial successfully demonstrated the innovation's value, and its commercial potential is clear as it transitions from a proof of concept to a minimum viable product. The "edutainment" concept holds strong potential to promote cultural and historical heritage across European cities and locations.

During the trial phase, only four cultural locations and corresponding mini-games were included in the AR experience. The concept is easily scalable. A full city experience could include up to ten heritage sites, supported by a library of mini-games tailored to each location. To realize this, collaboration between cultural heritage experts and game designers will be essential.

The AR component could be offered also alone via a freely downloadable app on the Play Store and Apple Store, with users downloading specific content for each site as needed. Primary target customers of this App would include municipal authorities interested in promoting tourism, such as the City of Turin—recently named the 2025 European Capital of Smart Tourism. The solution could also be monetized, for instance, by offering access to schools and tourists for a nominal fee.

4.4 UC13: Extended XR Museum Experience (Turin)

The large-scale trial conducted in March 2025 across four municipal museums in Turin, involving over 200 participants, validated an innovative approach: the use of AR, VR, AI and the **Metaverse** to make cultural and historical museum visits more engaging, particularly for younger generations.

4.4.1 Performance requirements

In the AR component of the experience at Palazzo Madama and GAM, data transmission over the 5G network was minimized, as the primary assets were preloaded onto the devices. Additionally, interactions with AI-driven characters performed satisfactorily and did not require high bitrates or low latency. In fact, a user with a tablet required for interaction with the AI character, that is a main innovation of this use case, on average only 265 kbps and a peak of 300 kbps. This implies that there would be no practical limits on the number of users that can simultaneously enjoy the application at a museum.

The VR part of the experience at the same museums, which also incorporated elements of the Metaverse, was more demanding. Peaks of 13 Mbps download and 50 ms round-trip latency were recorded with six simultaneous users. While no participants reported discomfort, it is worth noting that standard recommendations suggest a round-trip latency of under 20 ms to avoid motion sickness in sensitive individuals. This lower latency is typically achievable when most of the application runs locally on the device rather than in the cloud, which could be an objective for future development.

Measurements conducted during pre-trial testing showed that network latency alone already exceeded the 20 ms threshold, even before accounting for app-specific delays (excluding the delays produced by Ookla Speedtest measurement App). Therefore, although ultra-low latency (such as that expected from future 6G networks) would benefit this application, although it is not strictly critical for functionality.

Also, in the case of the Museo Pietro Micca and Museo del Risorgimento, the 5G public network was able to handle the experience with no hiccups. The measured downlink per user was 1.2 Mbps while the uplink per user was 0.8 Mbps. Contrarily to UC12, where a larger number of users could stress the network, this has not been the case for this use case.

4.4.2 Network functionalities

The 5G network performed reliably during the trial, despite the detection of several data transmission errors. These were automatically corrected by the TCP and did not affect performance. In fact, TCP corrects packet transmission faults through a combination of mechanisms including acknowledgments, retransmissions, sequence numbers, checksums, and timeout mechanisms, ensuring reliable and ordered data delivery even in the presence of packet loss or corruption.

During the trial, both latency and throughput remained within acceptable thresholds for single-user or small-group applications. This performance was largely supported by the nature of the content, which was either pre-downloaded or transmitted at relatively low bitrates. Consequently, the system's demand for real-time, high-

bandwidth data transmission was limited, reducing the stress placed on the underlying network infrastructure. On such basis, more advanced capabilities—such as dynamic resource allocation, edge computing integration, and orchestration—were not exercised during the trial. These features, while not essential in the current low-complexity use cases, but could play a role in future, scaled deployments. In scenarios involving high-fidelity graphics, interactive multi-user environments, or real-time AI-driven components, the ability to dynamically allocate resources, offload computation to the edge, and coordinate services in real time will be essential to maintaining performance, responsiveness, and overall user experience.

To prepare for these future demands, subsequent iterations of the system will need to incorporate and rigorously test these advanced functionalities under more complex and resource-intensive conditions.

4.4.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

Two of the participating museums were connected via 5G to servers hosted at Politecnico di Torino, and the other two to servers located in the TIM laboratory. Given that the 5G signal inside the museums was weak, in each museum two 5G-to-Wi-Fi CPE units were installed near windows to ensure optimal 5G signal reception. These CPEs connected wirelessly to the user devices inside the buildings via Wi-Fi and served as a bridge between the public 5G network and the internal infrastructure. This setup enabled access to cloud resources and facilitated stable connectivity for the experience.

The system showcased strong cross-device compatibility, demonstrating its ability to operate seamlessly across a range of endpoints, including smartphones, tablets, laptops, and VR headsets. The underlying software protocols ensured consistent performance and user experience, regardless of hardware differences or connectivity variability.

The infrastructure deployment strategy was designed with scalability and adaptability at its core, laying the groundwork for seamless integration of next-generation technologies. In particular, the architecture is well-positioned to incorporate key innovations anticipated with the rollout of 6G, edge computing for reduced latency and distributed processing, and AI-driven network management for real-time optimization and predictive maintenance.

4.4.4 Other Aspects

The analysis of KVI questionnaires, confirmed that participants found the interactive activities (games, quizzes, and exploration tasks), both fun and effective for learning. Many appreciated working in pairs or groups at Palazzo Madama and GAM, noting that collaboration made the experience more enjoyable and helped build stronger connections with others.

A recurring theme was the educational value of the experience, with several individuals stating that it helped them focus on important details in artworks and historical content they might have otherwise missed. Some felt the experience was more engaging and impactful than traditional classroom lessons. AI and digital tools were also praised for enhancing the learning experience.

Interacting with AI assistants and historical figures made the content feel more vivid and realistic. The use of VR was particularly well received. Participants described the VR activities as immersive, entertaining, and memorable. They appreciated being able to explore locations that are typically inaccessible, such as historic tunnels at Museo Pietro Micca or the parliamentary chamber at Museo del Risorgimento and found the ability to view these spaces from different perspectives to be especially valuable for understanding their structure and significance. Several participants found the blend of virtual and real-world experiences particularly effective. Moving from a digital simulation to an actual visit of the same space helped solidify their understanding and made the learning more tangible. Many participants also noted the accessibility of the experience, highlighting how it allowed people with limited mobility or those less interested in traditional museum visits to engage more deeply with cultural content. Some commented that the opportunity to preview or virtually visit locations may help feel more prepared or interested in the physical experience. Overall, the experience was described as enjoyable, educational, and innovative, with many participants expressing that it made learning about history and art more accessible, interactive, and memorable.

There were also suggestions for improvement. Some participants reported initial confusion due to unclear instructions and a lack of guidance in the VR environment. Others pointed out technical issues such as lag, blurry

visuals, and bugs, and recommended enhancing the visual quality, interface, and spatial design for a more intuitive and immersive experience. The VR component was seen as somewhat limited, with many calling for more interactive features like mini-games or activities to boost engagement. Feedback on the AI assistants was mixed: while the idea was appreciated, responses were often viewed as repetitive or unclear, especially when using natural language, which hindered learning and interaction. Language accessibility was also a key concern, with many participants requesting Italian translations or subtitles, as the absence of these features excluded non-English speakers. Additional suggestions included incorporating historical scenarios, immersive simulations, printed materials, detailed guides, or live facilitation to enrich the overall experience. Overall, participants felt that with targeted improvements, the experience could become significantly more engaging, accessible, and educational.

4.4.5 Final observations

From a technical perspective, the apps performed well across all four museums using the existing public 5G network. Some concerns were raised regarding round-trip latency, which exceeded the 20 ms threshold recommended to prevent motion sickness in VR headset users.

Regarding bitrate, the trial involved only a limited number of images and videos transmitted over 5G. However, future implementations involving higher-resolution media or a larger number of simultaneous visitors could risk network saturation, depending on traffic volume and content size.

While an Italian version of the AI interactive guide is being developed, the developers will take stock of the feedback from the participants to improve future versions of the apps.

These apps can be adapted and deployed in other museums and exhibitions worldwide. However, while the underlying methodology and technology can remain consistent, each new implementation would require significant additional development, including custom graphics, narrative design, documentation, and AI training.

In conclusion, the operation of this use case would not justify the transition from 5G to 6G unless new features are added in the future requiring enhanced performance, such as higher bitrates, ultra-low latency, native AI integration, massive device connectivity, network slicing, true XR and holographic interfaces.

4.5 UC13: Extended XR Museum Experience (Athens)

The deployment of the AR/VR solution to enhance visitor experiences at cultural and historical sites was supported by 5G field trials, which demonstrated that current networks could handle immersive AR/VR experiences for small groups under controlled conditions, with positive user feedback on performance and usability. However, scaling to larger audiences and more complex interactions will require advances in network capabilities and infrastructure. This section reviews key findings from the trials and highlights where 6G technology will be essential for broader, seamless deployments.

4.5.1 Performance requirements

Based on the field trials conducted at Technopolis using commercial 5G infrastructure, the AR/VR applications demonstrated satisfactory technical performance aligned with the needs of immersive content delivery. For the downlink throughput, an average of 0.75 Mbps was recorded per user, enabling smooth downloading and efficient delivery of lightweight AR/VR content in short durations with minimal buffering. The round-trip latency averaged at 298 ms, ensuring near real-time feedback and interaction, suitable for non-critical immersive experiences, while the one-way latency measured at 149 ms, supporting responsive media rendering and smooth user navigation.

Additional performance indicators, such as an average download duration of 1.51 seconds, an average file size of 0.03 MB, and a sustained average bitrate of 92.1 Kbps, confirmed the network's ability to support short interaction loops and uninterrupted content delivery under trial conditions.

It is important to note that these results were obtained in a controlled environment, with a limited number of concurrent users and pre-optimized content designed to minimize bandwidth demands. These values were sufficient to support single-user or small-group interactions with immersive media, as demonstrated during the live trials. However, to scale up to larger audiences, more concurrent users, and higher-quality assets (e.g.,

photorealistic 3D models or real-time multi-user interaction), higher throughput and lower latency will likely be required. For example, multi-user or collaborative VR, cloud-rendered environments, and higher-fidelity 3D assets would necessitate lower latency and increased bandwidth. In such scenarios, target values of <50 ms one-way latency and >10 Mbps downlink throughput per user may be required to maintain immersion, responsiveness, and synchronization at scale.

Consequently, while the current 5G infrastructure met the demands of this specific trial setup, future deployments, particularly under real-world conditions with mobility, network contention, and device diversity, will benefit from the enhanced capabilities promised by 6G networks, such as ultra-low latency, guaranteed bandwidth allocation, and context-aware network adaptation.

4.5.2 Network functionalities

The trial utilized a commercial 5G network. The setup operated reliably and demonstrated sufficient capabilities to support immersive AR/VR experiences under the controlled conditions of the live demonstration.

Despite moderate traffic and limited concurrent users, the network maintained consistent performance without critical disruptions. Basic fault tolerance and recovery mechanisms handled occasional packet loss or minor connectivity fluctuations, which did not significantly impact user experience.

Latency and throughput were within acceptable ranges for single-user or small-group applications. However, the applications operated with pre-downloaded or low-bitrate content, limiting the need for real-time, high-bandwidth transmission. As such, more advanced functionalities—such as dynamic resource allocation, edge computing support, and real-time orchestration—were not fully stressed during the demonstration but are expected to become critical in scaled deployments.

Future iterations targeting wider audiences or richer, collaborative XR environments will likely require enhanced features such as low-latency orchestration to support real-time rendering and interactivity, advanced load balancing and slicing to manage concurrent users with different device profiles, edge-assisted computation to offload processing from mobile devices, and scalable fault-tolerant connectivity for uninterrupted user experiences in dynamic environments.

These capabilities are anticipated to be core enablers of next-generation 6G infrastructures, supporting not only immersive content delivery but also seamless service continuity and personalized user experiences at scale.

4.5.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The setup provided stable connectivity and smooth application performance for a limited number of users, using optimized content and supported devices.

The system relied primarily on cloud infrastructure to distribute modular content efficiently, while edge computing was only partially utilized. For larger-scale or more latency-sensitive deployments, stronger integration of edge computing will be needed to support real-time responsiveness and reduce device-side processing.

Device compatibility was adequate across smartphones and headsets used in the trial. However, broader deployment will require support for a wider range of hardware and operating systems, including legacy devices.

Basic data management and monitoring were handled effectively using a backend system that collected real-time performance metrics. These capabilities will become increasingly important for scaling, ensuring efficient resource use and proactive troubleshooting.

The implemented modular API-driven architecture supports the integration with proprietary systems and emerging technologies, including advanced AI services or 6G features like network slicing and dynamic orchestration.

While the current setup met the needs of the trial, commercial deployment will require better coverage, enhanced coordination between cloud and edge components, and more flexible infrastructure to support diverse usage scenarios and user mobility.

4.5.4 Other aspects

Deploying immersive AR/VR applications successfully requires more than just strong network and infrastructure performance. Ensuring robust security protocols is vital to protect user data and maintain trust throughout

the experience. Thorough testing and appropriate user training are essential to address operational challenges and facilitate smooth adoption.

User experience and accessibility remain central to success, making the applications inclusive and enjoyable for a diverse audience. As these solutions scale, sustainability and energy efficiency will become increasingly important to minimize environmental impact.

Equally critical is engaging all stakeholders, from developers to end users, to tailor the experience, support personalization, and encourage long-term acceptance and use.

4.5.5 Final observations

The trials conducted demonstrated that current 5G technology can adequately support immersive AR/VR use cases under controlled and limited conditions, such as low concurrency and pre-configured device settings. KPIs including throughput, latency, and reliability met the immediate needs of the applications, and user feedback confirmed high levels of satisfaction and engagement.

However, scaling these services to commercial deployments with larger user bases, more diverse devices, and richer real-time interactions will require advancements beyond today's 5G capabilities. Specifically, 6G networks will need to provide enhanced throughput, ultra-low latency, and more sophisticated network functionalities like dynamic resource allocation, edge computing integration, and fault-tolerant connectivity.

Concerning infrastructure, the current modular and containerized system architecture lays a solid foundation for future integration with emerging technologies anticipated in 6G. Still, further improvements in coverage, device management, and orchestration will be essential to ensure seamless, high-quality experiences on a scale.

Finally, broader considerations such as security, AI accuracy, sustainability, and user training must be factored into future deployments to ensure the technology is not only powerful but also reliable, accessible, and user-friendly.

In summary, while 5G provides a viable starting point, the evolution toward 6G will be critical to fully realize the potential of immersive cultural experiences in real-world commercial environments.

5 Additional Use Cases and trials from the Open Call

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of the Open Call sub-projects within the CTE domain, reporting on the additional 7 use cases and trials performed, their associated options, newly introduced sites, developed applications and technologies, trial activities, and validation outcomes in terms of KPIs and KVI. Trials were performed under Options 1a (Turin5Games, Torino 4U, Augmented Reality, and 5GAUGMENTED), Option 1b (6GVision, and DREAMPARK), and Option 2 (Football Stadium and Remember Ascari). The sub-projects deployed in several new locations, including Petach Tikva (Israel), Turin, Naples, Antwerp and Bucharest, thereby extending both the geographical and technological scope of the experimentation campaign.

For each sub-project, a comprehensive description of the use case is provided, outlining the system's objectives, operational environment, and core technological components. This is followed by an examination of the developed applications and technologies, detailing the software and hardware solutions, communication technologies, and their integration within the system architecture.

The documentation then covers trial activities across different measurement phases and locations, including operational conditions and real-world validation challenges. Finally, it presents KPI validation results with quantitative data on latency, throughput, positioning accuracy, network coverage, and system reliability, alongside KVI validation capturing stakeholder feedback. Together, these elements provide a complete view of the development process from deployment to evaluation, offering valuable insights into the performance and stakeholder perceptions of advanced 5G-enabled solutions.

All information reported here has been collected from the Final Reports submitted by the Open Call sub-projects that will be included in the deliverable D7.3, scheduled for publication in December 2025. An overall analysis is provided at the end of the section to summarize insights on technical performance, user experience, and the scalability and replicability of the proposed solutions.

5.1 Football Stadium

Football Stadium sub-project provided a use case carried out in an Israeli Premier-League municipal football stadium Petach Tikva (PT) Stadium. The deployed system is an advanced 5G wireless communications system which provides novel services to the venue audience, enhanced connectivity and a handful of applications developed specifically for the entertainment of the football fans in the stadium.

Table 26. Football Stadium: Use Case description.

Use Case description
The trial's use case involved operating a Beyond 5G network in a medium-sized stadium with a capacity of 11,000 for a football match. In Phase 1 of the project, real-time performance-related data (including 26 different parameters) was harvested from the network to create datasets that would enable the system performance at this hotspot location to be analysed, understood and improved, and a digital twin of the stadium to be created. In Phase 2, the precise locations of 5G UEs were measured during a football match. Location measurements were performed in three cases: a walking spectator, a sitting spectator using a phone, and a fixed phone. Additionally, a survey was conducted to measure the value of the B5G network to game spectators, as well as the associated application uploaded by a large number of fans (>300), which enabled them to receive services such as 'instant video replays of player performances', 'ordering food and merchandise to your seat', and 'statistical information'.

Table 27. Football Stadium: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
The 5G network installed by RunEL in the PT stadium is a hybrid public/private network that operates in both SA and NSA modes. It comprises six cells that cover the stadium field and the areas of the stands. In Phase 2 of the project, RunEL added new radio units (RUs) and a location server capable of accurately measuring the location of 5G end devices, such as mobile phones, using a patented RunEL algorithm.

Methods and strategies were developed to enable the RunEL team to measure the accuracy of these location measurements.

In addition, a new application (Stadicom) was developed and installed on the phones of over 300 team fans. This app enabled them to receive services such as: 'Live scoreboard'; 'Premium content'; 'Food and commerce', etc.

Table 28. Football Stadium: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The Phase-2 trial was performed in the town of Petah Tikva in Israel. The trial took place during Premier and National Israeli league football matches, with thousands of spectators present in the stadium, an average of one thousand of whom were using 5G phones with SIM cards from the Tier-1 Cellcom operator and were connected simultaneously to the installed RunEL B5G private network. The main activity involved adding supplementary Radio Units (RUs) and a location server to measure the position of various phones in the stadium in different situations (steady and moving). Additionally, a survey was conducted by distributing a questionnaire to over 100 spectators with the Stadicom stadium app installed on their phones, to evaluate the value of the B5G network and the services provided by the app. Twenty-six questionnaires were returned to RunEL and were used to analyse the selected KVIs.</p>

Table 29. Football Stadium: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>Eleven KPIs were validated in Phase-2 trials of the B5G football stadium project. The validated KPIs include KPI#01-Downlink throughput per user [Mbit/s], KPI#02-Uplink throughput per user [Mbit/s], KPI#07-Coverage, KPI#10- Accuracy %. All the validated KPIs met the initial requirements.</p> <p>The most critical requirement studied in this project was the User Equipment (UE) Localization accuracy (KPI#18). The requirement was 0.5 meters for a moving spectator and 0.1 meters for a static phone, both requirements have been successfully met in the trial with measured results of 1 centimetre location accuracy for a static phone use case. The reason for considering this KPI as the most critical and significant is since this KPI represents a major improvement in the state of the art, current reported results are in the range of 1 meter, so the results measured in this report represent a record breaking two orders of magnitude improvement in UE localization accuracy measurements.</p>

Table 30. Football Stadium: Outcomes of the KVIs validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation
<p>Two main KVIs have been allocated, analysed and assessed: KVI-1, 'Cultural Connection', aims to increase access to cultural events, such as sports events (football matches), while KVI-2, 'Inclusiveness around services and applications', aims to improve service availability for all. To gather information, RunEL distributed a questionnaire with six questions related to the above KVIs to around 100 football fans in the stadium on the day of a football match. Twenty-six filled questionnaires were returned to RunEL for further analysis. The respective scores for KVI-1 and KVI-2 were 4.5 and 4.9, which are very high and lead us to conclude that improving communication services, providing applications to enhance the services offered to football fans, and ensuring a better and more enjoyable experience in the stadium will increase the number of fans participating in these cultural events (KVI-1 objective) and improve inclusiveness and service availability for all (KVI-2 objective).</p>

5.2 Turin5Games

This use case aims at assessing user and technology related aspects of 5G Cloud Gaming, a service where users can play games and immersive experiences including advanced edutainment scenarios running in the cloud infrastructure. Video and haptic feedback actuator controls are streamed in real time to the 5G user device. Interaction between player and game are managed over 5G networks with overall user experience broadly independent on user device processing power.

Table 31. Turin5Games: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>5G Cloud Gaming enables on-demand access to a potentially vast catalogue of games and experiences at any time, using low-cost 5G and 5G-connected devices, as well as low-latency controllers. T5G assess the capabilities of 5G and beyond technologies in terms of latency and bandwidth in challenging scenarios in both standard environments and crowded "hot spot" areas, as well as system requirements and possible standardisation opportunities.</p> <p>Our BYOG service model allows users to connect any games they already own or can purchase from multiple outlets to the T5G platform, which serves as a virtual console and is accessible at any time from different user devices. 5G BYOG provides on-the-go access, offering end users a highly convenient proposition.</p> <p>The use case includes private sessions with friendly trial users, public trial sessions managed with a fully digital user experience, and 'hot spot' or 'massive venue' heavy-load sessions to investigate current commercial 5G NSA network limits. There is also one example of a B2B vertical use case for driving school simulation sessions (in cooperation with a licensed driving school).</p>

Table 32. Turin5Games: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>Application growth has required design and development of the shaks.eu service portal and turin5games.com project portals, porting, optimization and configuration of the cloud gaming platform into the public cloud infrastructure. The project has developed solutions aimed at optimizing costs for running the trial activities, e.g. due to the "burstiness" of such sessions, by dynamically managing GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) resources, and at improving player interactivity (e.g. local CDN for portal assets to improve load response times), customization of the player app, new authentication system, questionnaire integration and technical KPI reporting solution.</p> <p>Additional development activities have been dedicated to devices, including controller firmware, and the development of prototype Android Beam projectors based on a modular mini set-top box form factor.</p> <p>The gaming portal provides users with relevant information (including GDPR) and allows them to select the game they wish to play. Once the gaming session is complete, users will complete a User Experience/KVI questionnaire via a digital survey platform. However, the online KVI questionnaire will be available at any time, so that during long testing sessions, users can pause the game and complete questionnaires relevant to the part of the session just completed.</p> <p>The other relevant activities are related to the configuration of gaming devices.</p>

Table 33. Turin5Games: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial activity encompassed two main locations within the Turin hub area and nearby region, accounting for 93% of trial sessions, along with several remote locations utilized for benchmarking purposes including Rome, the Abruzzo region, and Barcelona, among others. The testing employed 5G NSA commercial broadband service as the primary connection method, with marginal use of other connection types, and comprised approximately 800 trial sessions involving over 250 individual users. The distribution of trial sessions revealed that 62% were conducted by individual trial users, 31% involved two trial users within the same game session, and 6% featured multiple trial users participating in the same game.</p>

Table 34. Turin5Games: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>Extensive KPI validation was achieved via integrated and external tools, about 800 trial user sessions were used to measure and validate service requirements and public 5G NSA network performance based on</p>

commercial low cost 5G smartphones and a high performance 5G modem. Most of measured results are based on indoor trial sessions in line with our service assumptions. Outcome is summarized below:

Service end-to-end latency: target value 20 ms, < 40 ms for acceptable performance, with graceful degradation for higher values. Requirements and possible improvements were identified for user location dependent routing for B5G scenarios, also to improve possible integration of Cloud Gaming with B5G networks.

Single connection sustained throughput: 20 Mbps for good performance, the obtained value is smaller than the initial assumption (50 Mbps).

Aggregate throughput: The 5G NSA downlink network capacity was estimated around 600 Mbps, as the network were loaded with up to 26 CCUs each, running at about 20 Mbps sustained rate. These results are broadly in line with initial assumptions especially for the tested in-door scenario.

Number of connections: 5G NSA capability was measured to carry up to 26 CCUs.

Effects on devices: device CPU performance and memory load measured are compatible with very low cost 5G devices, better than our initial assumptions

Table 35. Turin5Games: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>Extensive KVI validation took place by using an online data gathering tool with about 800 questionnaires completed by trial users. Overall KVI results are good with the following highlights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall User Experience rating: 4,12/5 with consistent value across age groups • User rating of T5G 5G cloud gaming vs traditional platforms: 3,99/5 • Most highly rated user experience points: simplicity, portability, convenience of 5G ubiquity • Possible improvement aspects: quality, fluidity, response time, weight of the trial kit • Willingness to buy a service package: 79% • Willingness to buy same or similar devices as those tested: 80% • Net Promoter Score (NPS): 21 • User rating of inclusivity of the trial service: 4,3/5 • User rating of sustainability of the trial user service: 4,26/5 • Most highly rated additional verticals: Education, Training

5.3 Torino4U

The use case involved a large-scale trial stressing the use of public mobile access in the Turin area, where all Italian operators deployed their own 5G NSA infrastructure. Users have been invited to download the application and interact with eight geolocated 3D objects and five historic reconstruction videos at various locations around the city centre. No operator or technology restrictions have been required to conduct the trial. Stendhapp collected network measurements from the mobile and server ends to assess performance KPIs, as well as conducting user experience surveys.

Table 36. Torino4U: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>Torino4U provides users with an easy-to-use mobile application specifically created to stimulate the interest of cultural tourists. Leveraging 5G technology and extended reality, which is latency-critical due to the file size of 3D objects, the app delivers an engaging visitor experience, enabling users to discover new places and view short descriptions in various media. Users can also view 3D reconstructions of objects, places, historical events and buildings.</p> <p>The case is based on the Torino UNESCO Creative City for Design and aims to engage tourists by offering digital VR/AR content at various locations across the city. This proposal falls under the Ministry of Tourism programme for promoting municipalities belonging to the UNESCO Creative Cities Network.</p>

Table 37. Torino4U: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>Torino4U use case enhanced the Stendhapp application by introducing new functionalities for a large-scale trial.</p> <p>Stendhapp application is composed of a front-end app, downloadable from official stores for Android and IOs terminals (smartphones and tablets) and a back-end application built on docker technology over an Ubuntu server. The storage database used is MongoDB Atlas. Back-end application and database are available in cloud.</p> <p>The Front-end app has been developed in Flutter to include media and virtual reality (ARviewer) players, and it can collect application performances via Firebase by Google. It exploits open-source API by CartoDB to present point-of-interests on digital map.</p> <p>The Back-end application has been developed in NodeJS technology to provide communication interface server via API Rest, to interpret and prepare responses to each interrogation, to query dB and format the output, to provide calculation for optimized and customized itinerary. Moreover, it has been implemented a Machine Learning module (docker contained) in Python (Tensorflow) for image recognition functionalities.</p> <p>All functionalities at both ends have been deployed in time for the starting trial date of 6/12/2024. During the trial phase, small modifications took place at both ends to tune and correct some not critical functionalities.</p>

Table 38. Torino4U: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>From 6/12/2024 to 31/03/2025 Stendhapp performed a large-scale testing in Turin city centre. During the period Stendhapp collected 44507 transactions (server interrogations) from 374 users/devices located in the Turin testing area.</p> <p>Stendhapp personnel and professional interviewers have been on-field in Turin city centre for 6 live sessions, where they directly involved potential users to download Stendhapp from App and Play stores, invited to view enhanced content (media or AR object) and to respond to an in-app questionnaire.</p> <p>In the trial period Stendhapp collected 329 valid questionnaires that have been analysed and generated a comprehensive set of KVI's, including application responsiveness, user experience and engagement, economic, environmental and societal sustainability and edutainment impact.</p>

Table 39. Torino4U: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>NR-NSA is the current 5G implementation by Italian MNOs (Mobile Network Operators). The throughput performances in Turin testing area are wide enough for the most used mobile applications that don't need high data volume transfer.</p> <p>The measured total application time (RTT) for 90% of transactions using T4U Stendhapp application has resulted higher than expected (1146 ms vs 1000 ms). Therefore, application optimization shall be deployed on server side to lower the server response time of some demanding transactions. Most mobile applications will not have problems with mobile radio access performance after NR-SA 5G on-field implementation.</p> <p>Generally, the uplink KPIs respected the target thresholds that have been set for the trial, while the measured download throughput has been lower than expected (40,7 Mbps vs 80 Mbps) mainly due to long path between mobile radio access area and server location (avg. 80 ms ping) causing a bottleneck in achievable effective throughput.</p> <p>The new features have attracted a lot of interest among users and have worked with sufficient quality and stability. Server platform has been stable and reliable, dimensioning in term of computing capability and memory has been good for the generated traffic. The image recognition functionality loaded the total server for less than 50% in about 3 sec, providing a service with room for improvement.</p>

Augmented reality objects have been the core of project success and download time for 3D object fruition has been longer for an optimized user experience (about 15 sec per 90% of ARView transactions [113 trs in 5G]).

Table 40. Torino4U: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>A survey was conducted with hundreds of tourists, citizens, and student groups. These participants were exposed to various design-related VR/AR content in selected areas of Turin city centre via their smartphones and were then asked to complete an online questionnaire for analysing KPIs and KVIs. The KVI for this use case include performance indicators, user experience indicators and social and environmental impact indicators.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceptability: 5/5 – target achieved • Cultural connection: the number of cultural points of interest visited by user is 4,55. • Economical sustainability: 57,4% of the people paid a ticket for an average of 2,1 events/places visited. The declared total amount spent for entrance tickets, means of transport, parking, drinks, meals, tourist guides, souvenirs purchase, etc. has been on average 42,62€. • Edutainment: on average each respondent has visited 4,5 cultural points of interest. 33,5% of respondents declared having visited more points of interest than planned. • Environmental sustainability: 95% of trips are made sustainably. 14,6% of respondents declared that without Stendhapp they would have used different means of transportation. • Societal Sustainability, measured as perceived increase in wellbeing, is 4,28 – target achieved. • User experience: average rating for the Usability rating is 5 and for Makes your visit easier is 4,33 – target achieved. • User Engagement: average rating for overall interest is 3,21 raising to 4,28 when considering VR/AR content. Pleasantness, Usability and Responsiveness are rated 5, the average result is 4,64. 90% of respondents would recommend Stendhapp to a friend - target achieved.

5.4 6G Vision

The use focuses on updating the monolithic 5G OAI (Open Air Interface) gNB (gNodeB) to support Open RAN architecture, enabling disaggregation into O-CU and O-DU components, while conducting indoor coverage measurements and assessing reflective surfaces to improve radio coverage. Additionally, the project develops and evaluates a vision-aided Millimeter Wave (mmWave) gNB capable of predicting line-of-sight blockages and performing proactive beam switching in indoor scenarios. A web-based application for controlling and monitoring the 5G FR2 network has been developed and tested with end users, alongside an Augmented Reality application for visualizing mmWave beams, demonstrating promising technologies for future 6G networks particularly in FR2 and FR3 band deployments.

Table 41. 6G Vision: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The 6G Vision sub-project enhances the TrialsNet use cases by integrating advanced 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project) FR2 mmWave capabilities and upgrading the existing 3GPP FR1 OAI-based gNB testbed within the 5G Open indoor environment at IMEC. The project begins by updating the existing monolithic 5G OAI gNB to support.</p> <p>Open RAN architecture, which enables the gNB to be disaggregated into O-CU and O-DU components. The project includes indoor coverage measurements of the 5G FR2 signal and assesses the use of reflective surfaces to improve radio coverage in the FR2 bands. Additionally, it develops and evaluates a vision-aided mmWave gNB capable of predicting line-of-sight (LOS) blockages and performing proactive beam switching in indoor scenarios.</p> <p>A web-based application for controlling and monitoring the 5G FR2 network has been developed and tested with end users, as has an AR application for visualising mmWave beams.</p>

Table 42. 6G Vision: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The application is a web-based platform that can be used to visualise and configure the vision-aided 5G FR2 Open RAN testbed. It provides a set of features to facilitate the real-time monitoring of network KPIs and include pre-defined, easy-to-use configurations accessible via intuitive menus, which facilitate hands-on experimentation with 5G FR2 use cases. Working as an abstraction layer, it facilitates the use of the OAI stack, accelerating 5G/6G research and innovation. The application and dashboard were used to collect KPIs during the 6G Vision trial, including 5G FR2 coverage measurements, the impact of reflective surfaces on extending 5G FR2 coverage, and evaluating the proposed vision-aided gNB for overcoming LOS blockage. Notably, the application developed within the 6G Vision project is integrated with the 5GO open testbed at IMEC and will remain available for network management and monitoring beyond the project's duration.</p>

Table 43. 6G Vision: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial activities were conducted at the IMEC facilities in Antwerp. Fourteen end users, comprising researchers and University of Antwerp students with backgrounds in telecommunications and 5G were invited by IMEC to participate in the trial.</p> <p>The trial involved various indoor scenarios and 5G FR2 network configurations and was structured into three main components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of 5G FR2 indoor coverage. • Assessment of 5G FR2 coverage extension using mmWave reflectors. • Analysis of LOS blockage effects in FR2 and validation of the vision-aided 5G FR2 gNB. <p>During the trials network performance KPIs (DL/UL bitrate, RTT, RSRP, RSSI, SINR, SNR, MCS, BLER) and KVI were collected.</p>

Table 44. 6G Vision: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>This trial has demonstrated that a 5G FR2 cellular system requires a clear line-of-sight (LOS) between the gNB and the UE to ensure a stable end-to-end connection. The 5G FR2 radio coverage assessment at 28 GHz showed a stable 5G connection with 243 Mbps downlink (DL), 108 Mbps uplink (UL), and 14 ms latency measured at 40 meters (LOS) from the gNB. Peak throughput was recorded at 5 meters from the gNB, reaching 322 Mbps in downlink and 132 Mbps in uplink. A person blocking the LOS in the 5G FR2 link caused a path loss degradation of approximately 15 dB, resulting in a throughput drop from 322 Mbps to 150 Mbps.</p> <p>The use of reflective surfaces demonstrated a 20 dB gain in RSRP measured in shadowed areas. In these conditions, a stable 5G FR2 connection with 200 Mbps downlink and 100 Mbps uplink was achieved using a static reflector illuminating a shadowed area.</p> <p>This trial also validated the feasibility of a vision-aided proactive beam-switching mechanism to minimize LOS blockage effects in 5G FR2. An App, leveraging video sensing data from a 3D video camera and a Machine Learning algorithm, was able to predict potential LOS blockages and proactively switch the beam toward a reflector, redirecting the 5G signal to the UE and mitigating signal attenuation. This capability was demonstrated with a person blocking the link, showing almost no impact on the 5G FR2 link throughput. Vision-aided base stations combined with reflective surfaces have proven to be promising technologies for future 6G networks, particularly for deployments in FR2 and FR3 bands.</p>

Table 45. 6GVision: Outcomes of the KVIs validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation
<p>The selected KVI focused on the user experience of the developed web application and GUI (Graphical User Interface) dashboard for the 5G FR2 Open RAN network control and monitoring. To access the user experience, the evaluation has used the concept of Mean Opinion Score (MOS). The MOS was measured through a survey consisting of five questions, each rated on a scale from 1 to 5, conducted with 14 testbed users. The participants included IMEC researchers and University of Antwerp students with a background in telecommunications and 5G, who were invited by IMEC to take part in the survey. Prior to completing the questionnaire, the Allbesmart team provided a detailed presentation of the application as a tool to facilitate the management and monitoring of the 5G FR2 test network. Users were also invited to perform hands-on 5G FR2 experiments using the web-based GUI before filling out the questionnaire and providing feedback. The average MOS across the five questions is 4.4 which is considered Very Good.</p> <p>The users' feedback was very positive, clearly highlighting the added value of the web application developed within the 6GVision project in facilitating the use of the OpenAirInterface stack and accelerating practical experimentation with 5G FR2.</p>

5.5 DREAMPARK

The project creates an immersive and gamified experience of Valentino Park in Turin, allowing users who are not physically present to access and enjoy content related to the park's physical landmarks through various gamification elements. This edutainment experience is designed to engage users both emotionally and cognitively, making it suitable for both entertainment and educational purposes, with a compelling narrative centered around defeating the Dark Wizard Fosco. Built on the Reflectis platform owned by Anothereality, the application provides comprehensive tools for social interaction and collaboration within virtual environments, including real-time 3D rendering, video and text chat, avatar customization, and content creation capabilities. The project complemented UC12 by adding a VR edutainment experience to the AR part of the park of Valentino developed by CROSEU, which would allow users to play it from remote.

Table 46. DREAMPARK: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The project aims to create an immersive and gamified experience of Valentino Park, located in the city of Turin.</p> <p>The goal is to allow people who are not physically present in the park to access and enjoy content related to its physical landmarks through various gamification elements.</p> <p>It is an edutainment experience designed to engage users both emotionally and cognitively, making it suitable for both entertainment and educational purposes.</p> <p>The storyline of the experience has been crafted to create a challenge tied to the setting of the park, where the project developed and envisioned a compelling narrative, deeply connected to the park's setting, centered around a final goal: defeating the Dark Wizard Fosco.</p>

Table 47. DREAMPARK: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The Reflectis platform, owned and operated by Anothereality, served as the foundational software for the development of this immersive experience. Reflectis provides users with a comprehensive suite of tools designed to facilitate and enhance social interaction and collaboration within a diverse range of virtual environments. Its features include real-time 3D rendering, video and text chat, avatar customization, and content creation tools (such as the creator kit), allowing users to build and share their own virtual spaces.</p> <p>To fully meet the specific requirements of this project, which included the need for a password system, data measurement, and some tweaks to make challenges and gameplay work properly, certain custom features were developed and integrated into the Reflectis platform.</p>

Table 48. DREAMPARK: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial phase occurred in Turin, using the 5G commercial network, with three events between January and March 2025, and a closing event in April 2025. Focus groups of at least 40 people, in two locations, interacted remotely using the 5G network provided by TIM.</p> <p>The initial trials evaluated core functionality and gathered feedback, while the final trial deployed a more user-friendly version. Links Foundation assisted in identifying users, targeting students, and providing their headquarters as the main testing location. User data was anonymous, only age and gender were collected. For the final trial two locations were used: Links Foundation and Talent Garden. During trials, participants were divided into two groups, one testing Dreampark and the other attending a presentation about the project. The staff provided constant support during the events.</p>

Table 49. DREAMPARK: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The KPI validations for #01 and #07b were positive, as the measured values exceeded the minimum/desired targets, showcasing better performance and user experience than initially projected. This positive outcome can be attributed to the client devices' ability to leverage more bandwidth than expected, and the ample bandwidth available from the backend during the trials.</p> <p>While KPI #02's validation was negative due to lower upstream bandwidth, this was acceptable as the Dreampark project did not require high upstream throughput. The lower upstream bandwidth was due to the application's design, which primarily involved the exchange of metadata and did not utilize bandwidth-intensive features such as screen sharing and video streaming.</p> <p>Regarding KPI#08 the trial reported a positive evaluation, as the measurements were in range as expected.</p>

Table 50. DREAMPARK: Outcomes of the KVI's validation.

Outcomes of the KVI's validation
<p>The outcome of Dreampark project's final report shows the trial phase was successful, with the final application receiving positive feedback from over 90% of the participants (80% being the target value). The user experience was evaluated through a questionnaire divided into two sections that collected both demographic information and specific feedback on the VR experience, including visual detail, interaction design, and ease of navigation. The results show that 91% of participants used the VR headset, and over 90% gave positive feedback (4 or 5 stars), surpassing the 80% target. Additionally, 32% stated that only VR would be the ideal platform for this type of experience, proving that VR generated a more incisive engagement.</p> <p>The feedback also helped to identify areas for improvement in the application.</p>

5.6 5GAUGMENTED

This use case enhanced Naples' UNESCO World Heritage Site through an immersive AR tour accessible via smartphone QR Code scanning, linking to a Web App across eleven selected locations with strong 5G connectivity. The technical solution utilized real-time content streaming through a WebGL-based rendering engine using and server-streamed AR content for efficient performance and scalability. Successfully reaching approximately 1,500 users over four months, the initiative demonstrated its potential as a scalable model for enhancing cultural heritage experiences, validating the crucial role of NSA 5G networks in achieving satisfying user experiences and confirming that technical performance is key to user satisfaction and narrative impact.

Table 51. 5GAUGMENTED: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The proposed use case focuses on the conceptualization, development, and trial of an Augmented Reality (AR) tour for the UNESCO historic centre of Naples. Visitors can access the tour directly from their mobile devices by scanning a QR Code and connecting to a Web App.</p> <p>The use case is scalable and replicable in other cities or public spaces with sufficient network coverage, especially in areas not managed by museums. The tour is designed to enhance accessibility to cultural heritage through immersive, interactive experiences.</p> <p>During the Trial phase, QR Codes have been distributed free of charge by AR Tour personnel, via a local network of Bed & Breakfasts and partner museums already working with AR Tour. The trial has involved around 1,500 users over four months.</p>

Table 52. 5GAUGMENTED: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The application is accessible through a Web App that, once the QR Code is scanned, enables users to view the list of available tour stops, receive alerts when near a tour stop, and trigger playback and AR visualization through the smartphone camera. The app is structured in 11 stops, exclusively in areas with strong 5G coverage activated during the pilot phase, and the server-side infrastructure is supported by the AWS platform, providing the necessary scalability and cost-effective server hosting through web servers with horizontal scalability, load balancing, and CDN for static content, while utilizing HTTPS, encryption, and data sanitization for security, and implementing caching, pagination, and efficient queries to improve performance. The client-side application is based on a WebGL-based rendering engine using Three.js, an XML-based tour structure, and streaming content loaded progressively from the server.</p>

Table 53. 5GAUGMENTED: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial was carried out over 73 testing days, across 11 locations in Naples, with a target of 1,500 users. Each stop of the tour consists of one or more AR scenes, and each scene contains multimedia content. This content, which is quite large (300–400MB), is streamed directly to the tourist's browser. Therefore, the server's availability during service delivery and the downlink speed becomes highly relevant.</p> <p>This confirms the need for 5G-level performance.</p> <p>The trial also includes data collection related to the specific stop and performances of the system, such as timestamp, location, size of streamed data, server latency, download speed, how long the user had to wait to start the playback of the scene, user feedback in the form of in-app questionnaire.</p> <p>All data have been collected anonymously and stored for later analysis.</p> <p>The trial confirmed that fluidity is not a technical detail — it is the foundation of perceived quality in mobile-based AR experiences. Across all locations and user groups, responsiveness emerged as the main driver of usability, content appreciation, and emotional engagement.</p>

Table 54. 5GAUGMENTED: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>During the trial, several KPIs were monitored: Latency, Downstream speed and Scene load time.</p> <p>The data showed that network performance (especially download speed and low latency) is crucial to ensuring fluid, intuitive, and satisfying user experiences. When speeds exceeded 50 Mb/s, the app became responsive and close to 100Mbps enables seamless and immersive AR storytelling.</p> <p>Conversely, speeds below 25 Mb/s resulted in frustration, perceived poor content quality, and high abandonment rates, even when the actual content was unchanged. Even well-designed storytelling is undermined by lag and frustration. Between 25 and 40 Mb/s, the experience stabilizes but fails to fully engage.</p>

Table 55. 5GAUGMENTED: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation
<p>The trial aimed to analyse the relationship between mobile network performance and the perceived quality of the user experience during an interactive tour based on AR storytelling. To achieve this result, user questions were integrated within the same section of the app usage. At the end of each stop, users were first asked to evaluate the smoothness and continuity of the experience. Upon completion, a second question regarding the perceived quality of the content was presented.</p> <p>Since both questions were asked within the same user session, it was possible to correlate system performance (server availability and network speed) with the user's perceived experience in terms of Usability and Content Value. Specifically, when users experienced a wait time longer than one second before starting the content or when playback was highly discontinuous, the feedback on both the application's usability and the content quality turned negative.</p>

5.7 Remember Ascari

The use case is an extension of TrialsNet's UC13. The project delivers a cultural innovation project that demonstrates the application of 5G-powered immersive technologies within the cultural and tourism sectors by exploring the life and legacy of Formula One driver Alberto Ascari through an interactive and immersive multiplayer mixed reality format. The project was implemented at the National Automobile Museum of Turin (MAUTO) as a 4-person interactive Mixed Reality (MR) exhibition, utilizing a dedicated private 5G network to support immersive technologies including roomscale interactivity, archive audio, photos, video passthrough, mixed reality, and 360 cinematography requiring ultra-low latency and high bandwidth connectivity. Developed as a location-based VR and multiplayer MR application for Meta Quest 3, the experience combines VR, AR passthrough, and synchronized real-time interactions through core technologies.

Table 56. Remember Ascari: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>Remember Ascari: MR in MAUTO – Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO) is a cultural innovation project designed to demonstrate the application of 5G-powered immersive technologies within the cultural and tourism sectors. The project focuses on a VR and multiplayer MR presentation that explores the life and legacy of Formula One driver Alberto Ascari through an interactive and immersive multiplayer mixed reality format.</p> <p>The experience was implemented at MAUTO, utilizing the museum's automotive heritage and institutional framework. A dedicated private 5G network was tested and deployed for the trial to support immersive and emerging technologies, including roomscale interactivity, archive audio, photos, video passthrough, mixed reality, and 360 cinematography, which require ultra-low latency and high bandwidth connectivity.</p> <p>The project was delivered as a 4-person interactive MR exhibition that combined narrative content, technological implementation, and multiplayer collaboration to present a model for immersive cultural storytelling.</p>

Table 57. Remember Ascari: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The application is a location-based VR and multiplayer MR developed for Meta Quest 3. Designed as a 4-player multiplayer experience, it combines VR, AR passthrough, and synchronized real-time interactions via a dedicated 5G network. The experience explores the life and legacy of Alberto Ascari through room-scale interactivity, motion capture, and 360° video environments.</p> <p>Core technologies include 6DoF room scale navigation, proximity and object-based interactions, archive media integration, and a custom multiplayer framework based on client-server architecture. Users navigate seamlessly through levels using portal transitions and engage in meaningful, narrative-driven actions. The final phase culminates in a collaborative MR Formula 1 pit stop, where teams execute synchronized tasks in real time.</p>

Developed in Unity with optimized 3D assets, bespoke shaders, and adaptive sound design, the application showcases high-performance rendering tailored to the constraints and capabilities of standalone VR hardware, enhanced by low-latency 5G connectivity.

Table 58. Remember Ascari: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The main trial was held at MAUTO in March 2025, involving over 105 participants in multiplayer Mixed Reality sessions powered by WINDTRE's 5G network. Users booked via MAUTO's site and received onboarding materials in advance.</p> <p>On-site, participants were welcomed, equipped, and guided through a structured experience. Feedback was collected via tablets post-session.</p> <p>The trial confirmed the experience's emotional impact, technical reliability, and accessibility, validating its scalability for future cultural and educational contexts.</p>

Table 59. Remember Ascari: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The most important KPIs for the project are Band Throughput and Latency, reported through speed tests. The maximum download throughput is around 180 Mbps, meeting the required KPIs for the Cloud Streaming of the videogame. Speed Test involves third-party servers, representing a real and random condition of the internet transmission and Speed Test validates the analysis of the KPIs. The most critical requirement to meet have been the upload throughput: the link is based on a public and commercial 5G network, that is structured to be an asymmetrical data connection, with a higher download rate and a lower upload rate for commercial reasons.</p> <p>Further implementations might be analysed with the 5G Stand Alone Core Network, such improving latency KPI, a parameter that will optimize the synchronous videogame sections.</p> <p>Moreover, the 5G Slicing may dedicate part of the radio link network to this specific use case, even in a very crowded place under the same BTS coverage.</p> <p>Indoor coverage with higher 5G frequencies, of the order of tents of GHz, may be implemented to increase the throughput, leading to a less stressed connectivity in very congested areas.</p>

Table 60. Remember Ascari: Outcomes of the KVI's validation.

Outcomes of the KVI's validation
<p>The evaluation was structured around five KVIs: Accessibility, Engagement and Inclusion, Acceptance, Edutainment and Cultural Connection, and Economic Scalability. Across all dimensions, user feedback confirmed the experience's success in both impact and usability. 96% of participants expressed willingness to repeat the experience, and 88% stated they would pay for it. Edutainment emerged as the key value indicator, with 80% learning new information about Alberto Ascari and 38% wanting to explore his story further.</p> <p>Accessibility and audio/video quality received high ratings (4.2 and 4.5/5), while 90% found the multiplayer format enhanced the experience. Interaction was considered intuitive by over 80% of users, though minor challenges were noted during the Pit Stop segment.</p>

5.8 Augmented Reality

The use case Mobile Augmented Reality for Outdoor PoI (Points of Interest) Enrichment has created a mobile Android application for enhancing the experience of the visitors of an outdoor site (such as a city's historical landmarks, an outdoor museum, a university campus) through AR and Machine Learning. Deployed initially on the campus of POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest across three landmarks, the application enables users to point their phones at outdoor structures while the system performs real-time object detection and segmentation, overlays bounding boxes or masks, and displays contextual information with audio descriptions and tappable AR pins. Built using Google's ARCore, Scene Semantics, and SurfaceView for real-time overlays, the

application integrates object detection and segmentation with models trained on crowdsourced data and refined through federated learning over 5G networks and supporting federated learning updates while maintaining data privacy.

Table 61. Augmented Reality: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The use case is implemented as a modular Android application capable of detecting outdoor PoI and enhancing them through AR. The solution combines 5G/B5G connectivity, edge computing, and federated learning (FL) to provide contextual, real-time, and interactive experiences. The initial deployment was carried out on the campus of POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, leveraging three landmarks. Users interact with the application by pointing their phones at outdoor structures, while the system performs object detection and segmentation in real time, overlays bounding boxes or masks, and displays contextual information directly on the screen. Additional interaction is provided through audio descriptions and tappable AR pins. The primary objective was to increase user engagement through immersive AR while maintaining data privacy, achieved by relying on federated learning where user data never leaves the device. The use case demonstrates how AI and AR technologies, supported by modern mobile networks and edge computing, can enhance cultural exploration and educational outreach. The use case includes components such as real-time inference, post-processing, local model updates via LiteRT, and feedback-driven training. The trial validated the approach under real-world 5G conditions with public participants. The application is adaptable to other environments, and the framework can be extended to museums, city landmarks, or cultural heritage tours.</p>

Table 62. Augmented Reality: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The project resulted in a modular Android application built using Google's ARCore, Scene Semantics, and SurfaceView for real-time overlays. The application integrates object detection and segmentation with models trained on crowdsourced data and refined through federated learning over 5G networks. Detection is based on a custom YOLOv11s model, converted to quantized TFLite FP16, optionally accelerated with GPU delegates. Post-processing applies non-maximum suppression and consensus filtering, while segmentation masks are overlaid directly onto the camera view. The application displays contextual labels with distance and name information, while a bottom sheet shows descriptive text and supports text-to-speech functionality. Users can evaluate detections with thumbs-up or thumbs-down feedback, with negative feedback storing detection output locally, and LiteRT triggering model updates when the device is idle and charging. Model updates (10–30 MB) are sent to an edge Flower server for aggregation. Users can toggle between detection and segmentation modes or activate sparkles to enhance the AR view. The interface is responsive, supports accessibility features, and runs efficiently across 5G SA/NSA and Virtual Private Network (VPN)-backed Wi-Fi connections. Timeworx.io facilitated annotation with over 15,000 tasks from 1,000+ contributors, while edge offloading was benchmarked and demonstrated improved latency on weaker devices. The modular architecture supports future additions such as AR maps, gamification, or crowdsourced content, making the application adaptable across multiple smart tourism and education contexts.</p>

Table 63. Augmented Reality: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial was conducted in March 2025 over a two-week period within the campus of POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest. Ten structured sessions were organized with a total of 66 participants. The participant pool included students, academic staff, and external guests, covering a wide range of age groups, digital skill levels, and user profiles. The tested areas focused on three landmarks: the Rectorate building, the Aula Magna, and the Time Column sculpture. These points of interest were selected due to their accessibility, symbolic relevance, and proximity to Orange Romania's 5G antennas. Each session began with a short introduction and device handover, followed by free exploration using the application. Participants interacted with the detection, segmentation, and AR overlay components, with guidance provided only when</p>

requested. Data was collected for KPIs covering Machine Learning (ML) inference latency, application round-trip time, detection precision, segmentation alignment, and edge offloading efficiency. Devices used included Pixel 6a, Motorola Edge 30 Pro, and OnePlus 9 Pro, operating over 5G SA/NSA and Wi-Fi with VPN fallback. Both regular and reverse iPerf tests were conducted to measure uplink/downlink performance, while HTTPping was used for application-layer latency tests. The methodology required no prior AR knowledge, and participant feedback consistently rated the application as intuitive, responsive, and useful, validating both its design and deployment approach.

Table 64. Augmented Reality: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation

ML performance was validated with an accuracy of 99.2%, recall of 100%, and an mAP75 score of 90%. Network performance measurements confirmed that the infrastructure meets the demands of the AR-based federated learning use case. iPerf tests showed stable uplink and downlink throughput, with maximum recorded values of 20.2 Mbps (uplink) and 526 Mbps (downlink) in 5G SA conditions. Speedtest tools (Ookla, nPerf, PingTools) reported peak download speeds of up to 897 Mbps and upload speeds of 39 Mbps in the 5G Lab, while outdoor tests confirmed sustained performance above 100 Mbps download and 14-18 Mbps upload. Latency was consistently low, with ping idle values dropping to 12 ms in lab tests and HTTPping response times as low as 52 ms. This demonstrated that latency and bandwidth were sufficient to support real-time interactions with the edge node. Federated learning updates (10-30 MB in size) were transmitted within seconds, even in outdoor conditions. The round-trip time to the edge node, measured using HTTPping, remained well below the 100 ms threshold and often under 40 ms. Most KPIs defined at the start of the project were met or exceeded. The most demanding aspects (real-time inference and responsive feedback under variable network conditions) were successfully addressed. Future network improvements should target more robust jitter control, seamless edge handovers, and increased support for concurrent federated learning tasks, which would enhance scalability, offloading efficiency, and responsiveness in large-scale deployments.

Table 65. Augmented Reality: Outcomes of the KVIs validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation

Out of the 8 tracked KVIs, all were validated through structured questionnaire analysis. Acceptability scored 92.8% for ease of use and 90% for navigation comfort, despite only 68.6% initially feeling comfortable with AR. Edutainment reached 88.5%, confirming that the application blends education and interaction. System responsiveness achieved 95.7%, and 91.4% of users rated their overall experience positively. Cultural connection scored above 85% on all metrics, demonstrating that the application helps users resonate with heritage and enhances appreciation for local culture. Digital inclusion also exceeded expectations, with 97.2% acknowledging cross-device accessibility and 92.9% confirming usability across proficiency levels. Even perceived accessibility for users with disabilities reached 72.8%, indicating progress. Societal sustainability metrics were met: 90% saw cultural knowledge as more accessible, and 81.4% noted stronger community connection. The weakest score was 68.6% for responsible tourism, which was outside the application's focus. These results, well beyond the 75% threshold in most categories, validate the application's relevance for cultural engagement, education, and inclusive design. Moreover, user suggestions (such as AR maps, gamification, crowd input, and linked content) clearly align with the project's vision. Taken together, the KVI results confirm the potential for scalable, smart AR deployments in education, tourism, and public outreach.

5.9 Added value brought by the sub-projects

From a holistic perspective the inclusion of 8 sub-projects to CTE domain has increased the impact and relevance of the domain, demonstrated real-world applicability and showing how the project's technologies and solutions can solve actual challenges within the domain. Testing new solutions with real users in new environments can prove the adaptability of solutions to new contexts, proving its replication and its cross-sector adoption. New use cases with new business models, value chains and go-to-market strategies mean maximizing

project impact showing that different technologies are flexible, inclusive with different type of users and robust under different conditions.

Specifically, the sub-project Turin 5Games has expanded to a completely new subdomain, such as Cloud Gaming. 5G Cloud Gaming is an innovative Gaming service where users can play games and immersive experiences including advanced edutainment scenarios running in the cloud infrastructure. Video and haptic feedback actuator controls are streamed in real time to the 5G user device. Interaction between player and game are managed over 5G networks with overall user experience broadly independent on user device processing power. The sub-project Football Stadium has included a new network setup: a hybrid setup combined a public NSA 5G network with a dedicated SA private slice operated by Stadicom. The system supported high-density user scenarios, enabling real-time delivery of personalized services, live video feeds, and interactive fan engagement features. Notably, seamless integration between the public and private networks allowed end-users to transparently transition between connectivity layers. New technologies have been tested by the sub-project Augmented Reality and the vision-aided proactive beam-switching mechanism to address the LOS blockage issue in 5G FR2 (mmWave) by the 6GVision sub-project. One of the sub-projects, DREAMPARK, has complemented with its gamified experience designed to engage users through immersive storytelling, visually captivating 3D environments, and interactive gameplay mechanics the UC12. Finally, Turin 5Games, 5G Augmented Reality and Torino 4U sub-projects have expanded the scale of the trials involving a total of over 2,100 end-users.

In general, the Open Call sub-projects contributed to a better understanding of the performance requirements and functionalities needed for future 6G networks. For instance, Turin5Games investigated Quality of Experience (QoE) and viability of 5G Cloud Gaming under different network conditions and environments, innovative devices, and explored opportunities for standardization of system capabilities to improve Cloud Gaming potential on 5G telco networks also in perspective on future 6G networks. In DREAMPARK sub-project the data consumption on the local network was significantly higher than the anticipated requirement for a 5G network. 5G Stadium trial has proven high-precision, resilient 6G positioning in dense environments. Finally, Augmented Reality sub-project has proved that if additional AR-based features are introduced in the application would require extra ML processing and computations. In this sense, moving beyond 5G and towards 6G would be mandatory, to offer clients an excellent QoE and enhance the way they visit and interact with an outdoor location.

6 Conclusions

This document, D5.3, provides an in-depth analysis of the CTE domain core UCs and sub-projects from the Open Call process, serving as the concluding public deliverable of WP5. The contributions have addressed diverse real-world use cases across the domain, sports' entertainment, tourism, edutainment, and culture, involving thousands of end-users in trials. The results validate both technical performance and user experience, demonstrating the feasibility and scalability of the developed solutions.

For each UC, the document delves into the update on development activities, final application, pre-trial and trial activities in the sites located in Madrid, Athens and Turin. It provides a comprehensive overview of the implemented application designs, infrastructure components, functionalities, and measured KPIs and KVI's during the trials for each use case. The main remarks and key observations for each UC are summarized hereafter,

UC10 “Immersive Fan Engagement” (Madrid): Pre-trials at 5TONIC lab included NR-DC setup and FWA trials focused on 180°/360° camera validation and streaming protocols. The final trial took place during a basketball match at Movistar Arena with 40 participants, combining In-Venue and remote viewing via immersive cameras and a mobile app. This event provided a realistic high-pressure environment to validate system performance, capturing high-bandwidth video streams over 5G and distributing them for VR and mobile streaming. All trials met their defined KPI thresholds, validating the performance of each CPE unit under field conditions. Notably, Service Availability consistently achieved 100%. The aggregated results confirm system reliability, with KPIs indicating robust performance across the network. In-Venue scenario met targets for both downlink and uplink, as well as At-Home scenario. Aggregated field trials results indicated robust network performance. As for KVI's, the evaluation of User Experience and Acceptance for both mobile streaming and VR demonstrated strong, positive correlations with perceived Ease of use, Enjoyment, and Usefulness. Mobile streaming achieved a slightly higher overall User Experience score (82%) compared to VR (80%), while also showing a marginally stronger acceptance rate. Both technologies confirmed their appeal to early adopters. Mobile streaming users were physically present inside the stadium, experiencing the atmosphere and crowd engagement, which enhanced their sense of immersion. VR also achieved strong immersion via 360° view and interactive features.

UC11 “Service robots for enhanced passengers’ experience” (Athens): Pre-trials improved platform analytics with new thermal camera data processing. The final trial at AIA tested humanoid robots and crowd management systems, focusing on AI-driven remote operation under passenger flows. The trial highlighted the applicability of service robots in a high-demand environment, assessing technical performance and user experience. The system demonstrated exceptional reliability and availability, KPIs reached 100% while ensuring continuous video uplink from robots. Despite these positive outcomes, the trials revealed critical network challenges related to latency stability and jitter that could significantly impact system responsiveness in high-stress scenarios. Regarding KVI's, overall appreciative feedback was received, all ten participants provided positive ratings (100% scoring above 4/5) across all assessed KVI's. Trust and Resource Optimization and Operational Efficiency were the highest valued (over 4.4/5) crediting improving staff efficiency, reducing waiting times, and accelerating services. Also scoring over 4/5 scoring in User Experience, Acceptability and Digital Inclusion demonstrate intuitive interface, seamless interaction and ease of use aligned with user needs.

UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” (Turin): Pre-trial and field trials in 2024 assessed 5G performance. The trial involved 130 students navigating gamified AR/VR experiences in Parco del Valentino and Talent Garden. This allowed testing both the technical limits of 5G connectivity and the educational and cultural impact of immersive, location-based experiences. For KPIs performance, VR Segment got the most resource-intensive values. Application Round-Trip Latency averaged 69 ms, exceeded the limit of 20 ms to prevent motion sickness in sensitive individuals, though no participants reported such symptoms during the trial. The AR Segment required less network capacity, the Application Round-Trip Latency registered 15 ms. While the current 5G infrastructure met the demands, the public network would not have been capable to support two concurrent groups of four players each. This point to a justification for future transition to 6G and further optimization efforts. The analysis of 130 KVI questionnaires showed a high satisfaction level of around 80% across all criteria. The digital tour was preferred over a traditional guided tour that was used as a contrast sample. The following KVI's were the best rated: Availability, Acceptance, Edutainment and Cultural Connection, regarding enjoyable experience and increased interest, and Social Sustainability and Inclusion, as users in the trials collaborated with other students and the experience was considered available to people with disabilities. The experience could be extended to heritage sites. Also, AR and VR components could be developed as separate experiences. The AR component

could be exploited by creating a freemium app available on app stores. The VR component could be integrated into video games, offering a multiplayer experience.

UC13: “Extended XR Museum Experience” (Turin): Pre-trials measured 5G latency/bitrate. Final trials at four municipal museums involved 82 participants, including students and teachers, that provided a realistic evaluation in public museum environments, testing multiple devices (tablets, smartphones, VR headsets). The applications performed well across all four museums using the existing public 5G network under. While adequate, the round-trip latency exceeded recommended thresholds for motion sickness, and future high-resolution media or more simultaneous visitors could risk network saturation. The current operation does not justify a transition from 5G to 6G unless new features requiring enhanced performance (e.g., higher bitrates, ultra-low latency, native AI integration, massive device connectivity) are added. For KVI performance, 70% appreciation was achieved across all indicators. Participants found high educational value. AI and digital tools enhanced learning, and VR activities were immersive and memorable. The experience was noted for its Accessibility, engaging people with limited mobility. Although the experience suggested that digital tools serve as support rather than replacements for human guides. Also, suggestions were registered, participants noted confusion due to unclear instructions, technical issues and repetitive AI assistant responses. For Palazzo Madama and GAM, the use case tested four technological options: AI-powered interactive guides, AR-based games linked to artworks, VR in the metaverse, A “build-your-own museum” experience. These options could be commercialized in the future, either as a complete package or as standalone solutions.

UC13 “Extended XR Museum Experience” (Athens): The trial at Technopolis, Athens, engaged 30 participants exploring the Corinth Canal and Parthenon via AR/VR over a commercial 5G network. This trial demonstrated the practical integration of advanced connectivity with educational and cultural applications. While the commercial 5G infrastructure achieved satisfactory results under controlled conditions, limitations emerged for immersive content delivery. The system's DL Throughput per User proved adequate for lightweight AR/VR content downloading, but application latency posed challenges for deeply immersive experiences, scaling to larger audiences, implementing more complex interactions, and supporting higher-quality assets. This will require improvements in 6G networks to achieve throughput and latency requirements. Field trials received positive feedback across all KVIs, with Cultural Connection achieving the highest score of 4.7/5 and 100% of participants indicating strong resonance with the apps' ability to foster meaningful cultural engagement. Trust and Acceptability scored 4.6/5, with 97% and 100% positive ratings respectively, reflecting high confidence in the apps' reliability and welcoming design. User experience and Edutainment each received 4.5/5 ratings highlighting the apps' intuitive navigation, visual appeal, and engaging educational content. Digital inclusion scored 4.2/5 with all participants rating above 3, indicating the apps successfully accommodate. The evaluation of the use case deployments revealed solid performance for B5G/6G applications, while highlighting challenges related to scalability and latency. UC10 showed sufficient throughput (80 Mbps) and low latency (12.8 ms), supporting real-time streaming but raising concerns for high user densities. UC11 demonstrated reliable uplink (5 Mbps per robot), though latency could impact robot teleoperation in high-stress environments. UC12 met AR throughput requirements but experienced high latency (298 ms), limiting real-time interactions. UC13, deployed in Turin and Athens, operated well under controlled conditions, yet one-way and round-trip latency (149–298 ms) could hinder immersive or large-scale experiences. Overall, the trials showed that while current infrastructure supports engaging applications, future deployments will require lower latency and increased bandwidth to scale effectively. Additional challenges included network dependencies on stable 5G uplinks, the need for edge-cloud hybrid architectures, GDPR and AI Act compliance, and coordination with operational sites such as museums and airports.

Finally, the following section summarizes the significant results achieved by the eight additional Open Call sub-projects within the CTE domain. The key findings and outcomes for each use case are presented below:

Football Stadium (Petah Tikva): The trials validated KPIs, including DL and Uplink throughput, Coverage, and Accuracy. Achieving a UE localization accuracy of 1 centimetre for static phones is remarkable and can be considered groundbreaking in the context of KPI #18.. KVI scores were positive for Cultural Connection and Inclusiveness. The project has established new benchmarks for stadium connectivity and localization services while validating both the technical feasibility and societal value.

Turin5Games (Turin): Through 800 trial user sessions, the validation achieved 20ms end-to-end latency targets with acceptable performance and network capable of supporting up to 26 concurrent users at 20 Mbps. Also

is noted compatibility with low-cost 5G devices that exceeded initial expectations. User satisfaction reached 4.12/5 overall with 3.99/5 rating compared to traditional gaming platforms, showing appreciation for simplicity and portability, resulting in 79% willingness to purchase with high Inclusivity and Sustainability ratings.

Torino4U (Turin): The sub-project validated 5G NR-NSA with adequate throughput but with key challenges including RTT download throughput due to network bottlenecks, and slow AR 3D object downloads. Despite technical optimization needs, the KVI validation demonstrated exceptional User Satisfaction with perfect 5/5 acceptability scores, strong Cultural Engagement, solid Economic Sustainability with 57.4% purchasing tickets and total spending €42.62. Successful Edutainment outcomes with 33.5% visiting more locations than planned and environmental benefits with 95% users using sustainable transportation.

6Gvision (Antwerp): The sub-project upgraded the OAI gNB to an Open RAN architecture and validated solutions to improve mmWave FR2 coverage. Trials showed high throughput in clear line-of-sight but strong degradation under blockage, mitigated through reflective surfaces and vision-aided proactive beam-switching. A web-based monitoring tool, positively rated by users (MOS 4.4/5), proved valuable for experimentation.

DREAMPARK (Turin): The sub-project showed validation in KPIs, mixed but acceptable results: while upstream bandwidth was lower than ideal, it met the needs of a metadata-focused application, and efficient bandwidth use and backend availability were measured. KVI results were positive, with over 90% of users rating the VR experience favourably, and 32% identifying VR as the ideal platform. The trial validated both technical performance and strong user engagement.

5GAUGMENTED (Naples): KPI evaluation confirmed that download speed and latency are key to satisfying AR storytelling. Speeds above 50 Mbps ensured responsiveness, while anything below 25 Mbps led drop-off. KVI analysis demonstrated a direct link between network performance, perceived usability and content quality, highlighting that even well-designed content is undermined by slow or unstable playback.

Remember Ascari (Turin): KPI validation confirmed strong performance for cloud gaming with 180 Mbps download throughput, though limited upload capacity remains a key challenge. Recommendations include 5G SA, slicing, and higher frequencies. KVI results were highly positive, with 96% willing to repeat the experience and 88% willing to pay. Edutainment was a standout, and users praised accessibility, audiovisual quality, and the multiplayer format, validating the experience's educational and engagement potential.

Augmented Reality (Bucharest): The sub-project validated excellent ML and network performance for AR-based federated learning, with up to 897 Mbps download, low latency, and KPI compliance even in outdoor conditions. While jitter control and scalability remain areas for improvement, results confirmed infrastructure readiness. KVI feedback was positive across Usability, Edutainment, Cultural Connection, and Digital Inclusion, exceeding 75% in nearly all dimensions.

In summary, D5.3 represents the comprehensive finalization of testing activities across all project and sub-project use cases, gathering substantial quantitative and qualitative evidence to assess performance against originally established targets.

The collected measurements offer a solid foundation for evaluating system responsiveness, reliability, and scalability while providing insights toward future 6G development. Key considerations include the need for ultra-low latency, dynamic resource allocation, and guaranteed bandwidth to support high-concurrency immersive scenarios. Hybrid edge-cloud architectures will be critical to optimize performance, ensure scalability, and manage the growing number of users and devices. Furthermore, solutions must remain user-centric and accessible.

Overall, these findings position the current trials as a pivotal step toward defining 6G-ready architectures and operational models. The collected insights provide a solid foundation for future developments, ensuring that the next generation of connected, intelligent systems can deliver fully immersive, reliable, and scalable experiences.

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Annex A - UC10: Immersive Fan Engagement pre-trial activities

These pre-trials are structured into two distinct phases, each focusing on different network configurations to ensure comprehensive testing and analysis.

Trial 10.1 - Immersive Fan Engagement

YBVR and ERC worked together to carry out the pre-trial test at 5Tonic laboratory in Leganés, Madrid.

A preliminary pretest was conducted in December 2023 ahead of the subsequent pretrial tests described in Deliverable 5.2 [2]. The pretrial test was done in two phases, the first in July 2024, which tested the latest Rel-17 CPE and 180-degree cameras. As the release did not support the 360° degree camera, this prompted YBVR to use a more advanced and efficient streaming protocol to go with the latest and faster network capacity.

The second pre-trial was carried out in two occurrences, during mid-October where an initial validation of the 360° camera with the new protocol was done, and the third one carried out during December, using in both cases 4 mmWave CPE prototypes based on Qualcomm's SDX75 architecture.

The detailed network diagram depicted in Figure 99, represents the setup configured in the laboratory based on the framework of YBVR. In particular, the In-Venue scenario foresees the following setup:

- Cameras capture live footage (8x HD cameras) shown in a control room illustrated in
- Production in the venue processes the video (mosaic construction),
- Streaming uplink via 5G (link 2) sends the processed content to the YBVR platform at the edge (media servers),
- Streaming downlink via 5G (link 3) delivers the content to mobile devices.

While for the At-Home scenario it consists of:

- 360° and 180° cameras capture the footage— with the 360° feed transmitted via fibre and the 180° feed via a 5G link,
- Production at the edge process the video (stitching, live production, ingest server),
- Streaming uplink via fibre (link 5) sends content to the YBVR platform in the cloud,
- The cloud optimizes FOV (Field of View), syncs, and acts as a live origin (will use CDN for significant number of users),
- Streaming downlink via 5G (link 6) delivers the content to headsets and mobile devices.

Figure 99. Pre-trial Production setup.

The first phase of the pre-trial used the NR-DC setup provided by Ericsson at 5Tonic laboratory, which uses mid-band (FR1) frequencies acting as anchor for the high-band (FR2) ones. The second phase, focused on FWA

using only the high-band (FR2) configuration in SA (stand-alone) employing Ericsson cutting-edge software functionalities preventing the use of anchor cells, as the user equipment (UE) supporting FR2 frequencies is attached directly in the 5G SA network. This test was carried out between October and December 2024 and aimed to provide high-speed broadband to specific target areas.

First phase (NR-DC Tests)

In the initial network setup (Figure 100), a Mikrotik switch [23] is connected to the internet through Link5 by cable to the UPF (User Plane Function) Parrot. But during the tests, the configuration evolved, and the configuration and connection of cameras were changed.

Figure 100. Initial pre-trial network setup.

Diagram in Figure 101 illustrates the NR-DC Pre-trial setup, showcasing the key components and their inter-connections for the trial environment. The setup highlights the data flow and interaction between each component through network links, enabling comprehensive testing of network’s capabilities.

Figure 101. NR-DC Pre-trial setup.

In the following, the key components of the pre-trial setup are reported:

- The network setup integrates both mid-band and high-band frequencies for enhanced connectivity and optimized traffic flow:
 - 5G Mid-band (N78 - 3.5 GHz) and high-band (N258 - 26GHz) configurations using Ericsson 5G NPN (Non-public Network) equipment,
 - Connectivity via a Mini-PC, Askey CPEs [24] NR-DC, and switch,
 - Modifications included reconfiguring Mini-PCs and APNs (Access Point Name) for optimized traffic routing.
- Devices used to ensure connectivity and efficient network performance:
 - Xiaomi 13 and 12 for testing, with APN (Access Point Name) adjustments,
 - Cameras: Panasonic BGH1 180°[25], ZCam E2N 180° [10] and Titan Insta 360° for video streaming,
 - OBS/VMIX server with two decklink HD cards for having a total of eight video outputs. Video files recorded should be locally stored on the server to simulate the 8xHD camera video signals,
 - Meta Quest 3 VR headset [5]
 - Stitching server to receive the video camera feed for calibrating it,
 - Ingest server with Ubuntu distribution and YBVR ingest server.
- Software and tools used to facilitate network configuration, traffic optimization and performance monitoring to ensure smooth operation:
 - AWS cloud [12],
 - Grafana dashboards for throughput and latency monitoring.

In-venue pre-trial test (referenced as **10.1_NR-DCInvenue**) emulates real-world usage where a mosaic of x8 HD TV feeds is streamed in real-time within the venue, allowing the viewers to seamlessly choose their preferred main feed throughout the show. This test was deployed in 5Tonic laboratory. A series of tests, considering the links as marked in the previous Figure 101 were carried out to measure the KPIs defined by UC10. In particular:

- **Link 2** (Figure 102): 81.5 Mbps (mean). Target: 80 Mbps.

Figure 102. Link 2 data throughput.

- **Link 3** (Figure 103): >12 Mbps (mean) required to maintain bandwidth while device is reproducing the video feed. Target: 10 Mbps.

Figure 103. Link 3 data throughput.

- **OWD (One-Way Delay) Link2 and Link3** (Figure 104): 12.8 ms (mean). Target: 1/60 fps = 16.67 ms.

Figure 104. Jitter on Link2 and Link3.

The results measured in the previous Figure 102 to Figure 104, considering uplink and downlink aggregated throughput (in Mb/s) and OWD (in ms) were measured with the probes that are collecting the mentioned KPIs in the MiniPCs where the CPEs were connected, as indicated in the previous Figure 101.

At-home pre-trial tests (referenced as **10.1_NR-DCAtHome**) emulates real-world usage where an immersive experience base on video VR is streamed in live to home, giving to the viewers the capacity to choose between different immersive views whenever during the show. This test was deployed in 5Tonic laboratory. A series of tests, considering the links as marked in the previous Figure 101, were carried out to measure the KPIs defined by UC10:

- **Link 4 (3x 180° cameras)** (Figure 105): 145 Mbps (mean). Target: 150 Mbps. The observed Uplink mean throughput is not above than pre-defined target. However, there is no bottleneck in any of the devices or links, the lower value is simply since the video flow does not use more bandwidth. Still, higher values are observed in the network, measuring a peak value of 153Mbps in UL.

Figure 105. Link 4 data (3 cameras).

- **OWD Link 4 and Link 6** (Figure 106): 5.22 ms (mean). Target: 1/60 fps = 16.67 ms.

Figure 106. Jitter Link 4 and Link 6.

The results measured in the previous Figure 105 and Figure 106, considering uplink aggregated throughput (in Mb/s) was measured in this case with the counters extracted from the gNB, and OWD (in ms) was measured with the probes that are collecting the KPI in the MiniPCs where the CPEs were connected, as indicated in the previous Figure 101.

The results demonstrated through the tests are summarized in the following:

- The streaming protocol used in these tests is RTSP, using UDP transport protocol for video feed and TCP or session signalling. The behaviour has improved over the previous pre-test trial, where RTMP (TCP) were used.
- Results showed consistent Uplink throughput, peaking near target rates (e.g., 80 Mbps average for 100 Mbps) for the at-home cameras.
- Ethernet disconnections and manual interventions were required to stabilize the connection.
- Some connectivity issues with NAT (Network Address Translation) and firewalls, resolved by reconfigurations.

The challenges encountered during the trials have been the following:

- Some periodic session loss was registered, which needs to be addressed by both radio and video teams.
- New tests using a more resilience streaming protocol (as SRT) could be considered.
- Recommendations for enabling DNS across subnets for better IP management were discussed.

The following Table 66, summarizes the setup parameters, from the RAN perspective, that were used in the NR-DC tests as detailed above.

Table 66. Setup RAN parameters for NR-DC.

Setup parameters	Setup ID: 10.1_NR-DCInVenue & 10.1_NR-DCAtHome
Radio access technology	5G NR FR1+FR2
Network type	Experimental
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	FR1: 1W FR2: 2.5W (8 cells)
Frequency band	FR1: n78 FR2: n258

Bandwidth per component carrier	FR1: 100 MHz FR2: 100MHz (*8 DL + *4 UL)
Sub-carrier spacing	FR1: 30 kHz FR2: 120 kHz
MIMO	FR1: 4x1 FR2: 2x2
Duplex mode	TDD patterns: FR1: DDDSU FR2: DDDSU (UL Heavy: DSUUU)
Askey CPEs NR-DC Supported Component Carriers	FR2: 100MHz (*4 DL + *4 UL)

Second phase (High-band)

The second phase of the pre-trial was carried out with the final CPE prototypes based on Qualcomm's SDX75 architecture. For these tests, the 5G network deployed was based on the final configuration of high-band antennas operating in SA, without using another 5G anchor cells. Thus, the CPE prototypes supporting high-band in SA were used.

In the following Figure 107 it is described the high-band SA based pre-trial setup. Three Qualcomm high-band SA CPEs were used for the "At-venue" cameras. These CPEs were served by the first 5G sector, while the 4th CPE was connected for the TV Control room and had 5G coverage from the second 5G sector.

Figure 107. High-band SA Pre-trial setup.

In the following the key components of the pre-trial setup are reported:

- Network Setup for implementation of high-band configuration with optimized connectivity and IP management:
 - 5G high-band SA (N258, 800MHz) two sector configurations using Ericsson 5G equipment.
 - Connectivity via a Qualcomm high-band SA CPEs and switch.
 - DHCP and Port Forwarding rules configured in the high-band CPEs.
 - Fixed Public IP for each CPE.
- Devices used to maintain connectivity and optimized network performance:
 - Qualcomm based high-band SA CPEs.
 - Cameras: Panasonic BGH1 180°, ZCam E2N 180° camera [10], and Titan Insta360° [9] for video streaming.

- OBS/VMIX server with 2 decklink HD cards for having a total of 8 video outputs. Video files recorded should be locally stored on the server to simulate the 8xHD camera video signals.
- Meta Quest 3 VR headsets.
- Stitching server to receive the video camera feed for calibrating it.
- Ingest server with Ubuntu distribution and YBVR ingest server.
- The software and tools utilized to support network configuration, optimize traffic, and monitor performance to ensure seamless operation.
 - AWS cloud.
 - Grafana dashboards for throughput and latency monitoring.

The test performed with this setup focused on the At-home scenario which emulates real-world usage where an immersive experience base on video VR is streamed in live to home, giving to the viewers the capacity to choose between different immersive views whenever during the show. A series of tests carried out at 5Tonic's lab, considering the links as marked in the previous Figure 107, were carried out to measure the KPIs defined by UC10 and specified in the following.

In the At-home pre-trial test (referenced as 10.1_mmWAtHome_01), the Titan Insta360° camera, part of the YBVR equipment, is connected to Qualcomm high-band SA CPE3 generating uplink (UL) traffic, while a laptop connected to Qualcomm high-band SA CPE4 is receiving the video in downlink (DL):

- Link 4 (only one 360° camera) and Link 2 (TV control room) (Figure 108):
 - Camera Bitrate: 4K 360@60Mbps 211 Mbps (mean) in UL - Camera
 - 236 Mbps (mean) in DL – TV control room
 - Target: 100Mbps

Figure 108. Link 4 and Link 2 (only one 360° camera).

- Main remarks:
 - Uplink Throughput Testing: 211 Mbps: Stable performance for 360° cameras (connected via Qualcomm high-band SA CPE3)
 - Downlink Throughput Testing: 36 Mbps: Local TV room (laptop) connected to Qualcomm high-band SA CPE4.
 - Challenges: No main challenges are derived from these tests since the result was successful.

As can be seen in Figure 108, both uplink and downlink aggregated throughput (in Mb/s) KPIs were considered, in this case extracted directly from counters in the gNB, as no MiniPCs nor probes were involved in this set-up. The throughput depicted here is aggregated at node level, however, link 4 is assigned to 5G 1st sector, while link 2 corresponds to 5G 2nd sector, part of the Ericsson equipment.

In the other At-home pre-trial (referenced as 10.1_mmWAtHome_02), a ZCAM E2N Camera (CAM1 180°), part of the YBVR equipment was connected to Qualcomm high-band SA CPE1 and the Titan (CAM3 360°) Camera was connected to CPE3, generating uplink (UL) traffic, while a laptop (control center) connected to CPE4 is receiving the video in downlink (DL):

- Link 4 (360° and 180° camera) and Link 2 (TV control room) (Figure 109):
 - 109 Mbps (mean) in UL - Cameras
 - 24.7 Mbps (mean) in DL – TV control room, mTarget: 25Mbps
 - The observed downlink mean throughput is not above than pre-defined target. However, there is no bottleneck in any of the devices or links, the lower value is simply since the video flow does not use more bandwidth. Still, higher values are observed in the network, measuring a peak value of 48.1 Mbps in DL in this specific test.

Figure 109. Link 4 and Link 2 (Both 180° and 360° cameras).

- **Main remarks:**
 - Uplink Throughput Testing 109 Mbps: Stable performance for 360°/180° camera (connected via Qualcomm high-band SA CPE1/CPE3)
 - Downlink Throughput Testing 24.7 Mbps: Local TV control room (laptop) connected to Qualcomm high-band SA CPE4.
 - Challenges: Some local connectivity issues were found to remote controlling the camera.

As can be seen in Figure 109, both uplink and downlink aggregated throughput (in Mb/s) KPIs were considered, in this case extracted directly from counters in the gNB, as no MiniPCs nor probes were involved in this set-up. The throughput depicted here is aggregated at node level, however, link 4 is assigned to 5G 1st sector, while link 2 corresponds to 5G 2nd sector, part of the Ericsson equipment.

In the following Figure 110, Figure 111, and Figure 112, it can be seen the overall equipment set-up used during these pre-trial tests, from both partners involved, Ericsson and YBVR.

Figure 110. 180° and 360° cameras utilized by YBVR for pre-trial.

Figure 111. Ericsson equipment set-up for pre-trial (5G NPN flight-rack, high-band antennas and CPEs).

Figure 112. YBVR equipment set-up for pre-trial.

The following Table 67, summarizes the setup parameters, from the RAN perspective, that were used in the high-band tests as detailed above.

Table 67. Network setup RAN parameters for High-band Tests.

Setup parameters	Setup ID: 10.1_mmWAtHome_01&02
Radio access technology	5G NR FR2
Network type	Private
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	2.5W (8 cells)
Frequency band	n258
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz (8 carriers)
Sub-carrier spacing	120 kHz
MIMO	2x2

Duplex mode	TDD Pattern: FR2: DDDSU
Qualcomm high-band SA CPEs Supported Component Carriers	FR2: 100MHz (*8 DL + *4 UL)

Table 5 below shows the summary for the Trial 10.1 described above.

Table 68. Summary for pre-trial activity.

Summary	
Trial ID	10.1
Setup ID	NR-DC At-Home, NR-DC In-Venue; mmW At-Home
Facility/Site	5Tonic
Objective	Test the current 5G network capabilities to comply with UC10 requirements
Description	6 links types have been defined and emulated in the lab
Executed by	YBVR and Ericsson
Components involved	5Tonic Lab & Network, YBVR immersive fan solution
Targeted KPIs	KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#09 (Application one way latency)
Measurement tools	Ericsson probes (only NR-DC tests) Ericsson gNB counters (all tests)
Ethics requirements implementation	Faces of participants as beta users has been blurred in the videos captured for dissemination propose
Involvement of beta-users	Survey to meter KVI's has been probed with beta users to check the consistency of the indicator calculation method

Table 69 presents test case results for network performance, including downlink, uplink, and latency, in different scenarios.

Table 69. Measurement results for pre-trial activity.

Case ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
10.1_NR-DCInvenue_01	KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#04: 80 Mbps KPI#09: 16.67ms	KPI#03: 12 Mbps KPI#04: 81.5 Mbps KPI#09: 12.8 ms	Complied
10.1_NR-DCAtHome_01	KPI#04: 150 Mbps KPI#09: 16.67 ms	KPI#04: 145 Mbps KPI#09: 5.22 ms	Complied, no limitations found
10.1_mmWAtHome_01	KPI#03: 100 Mbps KPI#04: 100 Mbps	KPI#03: 236 Mbps KPI#04: 211 Mbps	Complied
10.1_mmWAtHome_02	KPI#03: 25 Mbps KPI#04: 25 Mbps	KPI#03: 24.7 Mbps KPI#04: 109 Mbps	Complied

Annex B - UC11: Service robots for enhanced passengers' experience pre-trial activities

This section details the analytics component deployed within the UC platforms before the main trials.

Trial 11.1 - Service robots for enhanced passengers' experience

Analytics component

The analytics component of the WINGSPARK plus platform that is utilised for UC11 aims to monitor crowd congestion and flow in crowded areas. For this purpose, after receiving the video source as input, object detection is performed to identify humans. Then a tracking algorithm is applied to the detections to assign a unique ID to each detected human. After the tracking results are gathered for a time window, a second level of analysis is performed to produce multiple statistics that give a representative picture of the crowd concentration and flow. As also mentioned in section 2.2, new statistics were calculated for each of the eight installed cameras (three previously installed and five new), as detailed below:

- Total number of people in the area of interest (count),
- Average delay time and speed,
- Average flow rates,
- Congestion areas (hotspots),
- Waiting queue lengths at selected points,
- Queue change rate (throughput),
- Passenger mobility patterns and direction of travel,
- Alarms for abnormal conditions.

Furthermore, specific areas of interest were defined within the FOV of each camera. In some cases, more than one area of interest, represented as masks, was defined per camera. For each area of interest, dedicated statistics were calculated. During the pre-trial activities, different mask configurations were validated to identify the optimal coverage for each area. The results are detailed in the sections below.

General Statistics

To provide an analysis of human activity within the monitored environment, first statistics are calculated for the entire frame over a predefined time window. The primary metrics include:

- **Total Number of People Detected:** The total count of individuals detected within the frame during the specified time window.
- **Average Speed:** The average speed of detected people, derived from their trajectories over time. This helps assess movement dynamics within the monitored area.
- **Average Flow:** Defined as the rate of people moving through the frame, expressed in terms of people per minute. This metric provides insights into the density and movement patterns of the observed population.
- **Average Delay:** The mean time individuals remain stationary or move slowly within the frame. This metric is particularly useful for identifying congestion or areas where movement is impeded.

Directional Analysis

To further track people's movement patterns, detected individuals are classified based on their movement direction (Figure 113). Eight primary directions defined: East, North-East, North, North-West, West, South-West, South, and South-East. Each direction corresponds to a 45-degree range within a 360-degree field. For every detected individual, their trajectory is calculated using all their positions in the frame during the time window. Based on the trajectory's angle, individuals are classified into one of the eight predefined directions. Directional statistics are compiled and displayed for the predefined time window, providing insights into the predominant flow of movement and potential hotspots of directional traffic.

Figure 113. Directional Analysis for people movement tracking.

Area of Interest (AOI) Statistics

To analyse specific regions within the monitored environment, AOI are defined, such as queues, check-in counters, or security checkpoints. For each AOI, the number of detections that fall within their spatial boundaries is monitored and the corresponding statistics are calculated (Figure 114). Metrics calculated for these AOIs include:

- **Total Number of People:** The total number of people detected within the AOI over the specified time window. The metric helps measure the density or usage intensity of the area.
- **Flow Rate:** the rate of movement into and out of the AOI, expressed as people per minute. High flow rate may indicate efficient throughput, while lower rate could suggest bottlenecks or delays.
- **Throughput:** Defined as the net number of people exiting the AOI (“number of people going out” – “number of people going in”). This metric highlights the efficiency of the area in managing traffic and is especially relevant in controlled environments such as security checks or ticket counters.

During the pre-trial phase all the above statistics were measured from all the cameras and resulted in the replacement of some masks to better depict the area of interest. Based on these data captured during this period the AI model utilised in UC11 will be re-trained till the trial.

Figure 114. Spatial boundaries example to monitor detections in specific areas of interest.

Annex C - UC12: City Parks in Metaverse pre-trial activities

TIM executed multiple 5G network capacity assessments at the Talent Garden building, deploying VR equipment connected through 5G routers to evaluate network performance under realistic conditions. Simultaneously, CROSEU conducted site-specific testing at Parco del Valentino to verify AR application performance across various experience locations.

Trial 12.1 - City Parks in Metaverse

On 13/11/2024, TIM carried out preliminary field tests on the capacity of the public 5G network (see Table 70) at the Talent Garden building on 8/7/2024, 4/11/2024 and 13/11/2024. Toward this end two 5G routers were positioned next to windows of the auditorium that were connected via Wi-Fi to four VR headsets and four laptops. On 13/11/2024, CROSEU carried out one preliminary tests on the different sites of the experience in the Parco del Valentino. Pictures of these tests can be found in Figure 115.

Figure 115. Test of the devices at Parco del Valentino on the 13/11/2024.

Table 70 and Table 71 reports the network parameters and the test summary for Trial 12.1 respectively.

Table 70. Network setup parameters for Pre-trials 12.1.

Setup parameters	Setup ID: Field
Radio access technology	5G NR Rel-15
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	mMIMO
Duplex mode	TDD

Device type	PC
Device number	4
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	Commercial

Table 71. Summary for Pre-trials 12.1.

Summary	
Trial ID	12.1
Setup IDs	Field
Facility/Site	Field_1, Field_2, Field_3. at Covent Garden Field_4. at the Parco del Valentino
Objective	Field_1, Field_2, Field_3 check bitrate and latency Field_4 test bitrate
Description	8 persons, with various devices
Executed by	F. Della Betta (TIM): Field_1, Field_2, Field_3 M. Mazzaglia (CROSEU): Field_4
Components involved	Field_1, Field_2, Field_3: VR Headsets, CPEs and Laptops Field_4.: Tablets
Targeted KPIs	Downlink, Uplink, Latency
Measurement tools	Speed-test by Ookla
Ethics requirements implementation	none
Involvement of beta-users	none

The results for these preliminary tests are reported in Table 72.

Table 72. Measurements results for Pre-trials 12.1.

Case ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
12.1_Field_1 (Talent Garden 8/7/2024)	KPI#01: 30 Mbps KPI#02: 1.5 Mbps KPI#03: 120 Mbps KPI#04: 4 Mbps KPI#08: < 100 ms	KPI#01: 53 Mbps KPI#02: 1.6 Mbps KPI#03: NM KPI#04: NM KPI#08: 68 ms	OK for KPI#01, KPI#02, and KPI#03
12.1_Field_2 (Talent Garden 4/11/2024)	KPI#01: 30 Mbps KPI#02: 1 Mbps KPI#03: 120 Mbps KPI#04: 4 Mbps KPI#08: < 100 ms	KPI#01: 49 Mbps KPI#02: 1.5 Mbps KPI#03: NM KPI#04: NM KPI#08: 71ms	OK
12.1_Field_3 (Talent Garden 13/11/2024)	KPI#01: 30 Mbps KPI#02: 1 Mbps KPI#03: 120 Mbps	KPI#01: 56 Mbps KPI#02: 1.7 Mbps KPI#03: 230 Mbps	OK

	KPI#04: 4 Mbps KPI#08: < 100 ms	KPI#04: 5,7 Mbps KPI#08: 66 ms	
12.1_Field_4 (Parco del Valentino 13//11/2024)	KPI#03: 4 Mbps KPI#04: 4 Mbps	KPI#03: 376 Mbps KPI#04: 23 Mbps	OK

The test in the Parco del Valentino on 13/11 (reference **12.1_Field_4**) was essentially performed to check the performance of the network at the different spots of the experience (Figure 116 below). It should be noted that the AR application, which was pre-loaded on the devices, uses a limited bitrate that was at peak around 1 Mbps both for download and upload. Pcap was used for the measurement of the network load in the AR phase in Park, while Speedtest and Wireshark were used in the Talent Garden.

Figure 116. Measurement of the 5G network performance at the 5 spots of the experience.

Annex D - UC13: Extended XR Museum Experience (Turin) pre-trial activities

The pre-trial essentially focused on measuring bitrate and latency. The objective was to measure the performance of the 5G public network only in the different locations of the museums where the experiences were going to take place. It was not possible to test the full applications in advance of the date of the trial given the complexity and time needed for a full installation in such open public spaces.

Trial 13.1 - Extended XR Museum Experience

The main parameters of the public network, which were the same for the four museums, are listed in Table 73.

Table 73. Network setup parameters for Pre-trials 13.1

Setup parameters	Setup ID: Field
Radio access technology	5G NR Rel-15
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	mMIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
Device type	PC
Device number	1
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	Commercial

The pre-trials in the four museums took place at different times and modalities as shown below.

Palazzo Madama

The network performance was measured on 6/2/2025 at four spots, namely: i) the presentation room, ii) in front of the painting ‘Castello di Rivoli’, and in the iii) cafeteria and iv) veranda where the VR phase, the Quiz and the KVI measurements were going to be held. The results are shown in the graphs of Figure 117, where the KPIs for each location were the averages of three or four measurements.

Figure 117. Palazzo Madama: measurements of network KPIs at Pre-trial.

GAM

The network performance was measured on 6/2/2025 at three spots in the museum, namely i) the Sala Incontri (where the introduction and VR phases and Quiz were organised), ii) in front of the painting ‘Nei Dintorni di Rivara’ by Carlo Pittara (where the transition from figurative to futurism style was illustrated), and iii) in front of the painting ‘The Ploughing’ by Fortunato DePero (where the puzzle game was shown). The average results are shown in Figure 118 below where the KPIs in each location were the average of at least three measurements.

Figure 118. GAM: measurements of network KPIs at Pre-trial.

Museo Pietro Micca and Museo del Risorgimento

As part of the pre-trial phase for the two museums, network coverage and signal quality were assessed within the rooms designated to host the trial. These technical checks were conducted during meetings with museum representatives, held in the context of progress reviews of the development of the two VR experiences:

- At Museo Pietro Micca on the 24/02/2025 with 345 Mbps for the downlink aggregate throughput and 61 Mbps for the uplink aggregate throughput.
- At Museo del Risorgimento on the 26/02/2025 with 280 Mbps for the downlink aggregate throughput and 57 Mbps for the uplink aggregate throughput.

Table 74. Summary of Pre-trials for UC13.1.

Summary	
Trial ID	13.1
Setup ID	Field
Facility/Site	Field_1: Palazzo Madama, Field_2: GAM, Field_3: Museo del Risorgimento, Field_4: Museo Pietro Micca
Objective	Measure bitrate and latency
Description	several persons, with various devices
Executed by	M. Mazzaglia (CROSEU), M. Agus (TIM): Field_1, Field_2 F. Della Betta, Claudio Barsi (TIM): Field_3, Field_4
Components involved	VR Headsets, CPEs, Laptops, Tablets
Targeted KPIs	Downlink, Uplink, Latency
Measurement tools	Speed-test by Ookla
Ethics requirements implementation	None
Involvement of beta-users	None

Table 75. Measurements results of Pre-trials for UC13.1.

Case ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
13.1_Field_1 (Palazzo Madama 6/2/2025)	KPI#01: 20 Mbps KPI#2: 10 Mbps KPI#08: < 100 ms	KPI#01: 637 Mbps KPI#02: 105 Mbps KPI#08: 31 ms	OK
13.1_Field_2 (GAM 6/2/2025)	KPI#01: 20 Mbps KPI#02: 10 Mbps KPI#08: < 100 ms	KPI#01: 417 Mbps KPI#02: 41 Mbps KPI#08: 30.9 ms	OK
13.1_Field_3 (Museo del Risorgimento) 26/02/2025)	KPI#03: 4 Mbps KPI#04: 2 Mbps	KPI#03: 280 Mbps KPI#04: 57 Mbps	OK
13.1_Field_4 (Museo Pietro Micca 24/02/2025)	KPI#03: 3 Mbps KPI#04: 1.5 Mbps	KPI#03: 345 Mbps KPI#04: 61 Mbps	OK

Annex E - UC13: Extended XR Museum Experience (Athens) pre-trial activities

The tests that were reported in deliverable D5.2 [2] for the AR/VR applications were repeated. The goal was to measure KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user), KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency), and KPI#09 (Application one-way latency), following updates on the development activities, which included improvements to the application's architecture and the subdivision of content into smaller packages for faster delivery and enhanced performance.

Trial 13.2 - Extended XR Museum Experience

These pre-trial tests were conducted at WINGS premises using the dedicated 5G campus network (Lab01), providing a controlled and high-performance environment for assessment. The Network Configuration for the pre-trials included:

- Custom 5G antenna integration,
- 5G SIM (Subscriber Identity Module) cards to ensure network communication,
- Dedicated workbench environment for testing, providing an isolated and focused setup for accurate measurement,
- Parallel testing capability with commercial 5G networks for comparison.

The testing environment was designed to facilitate controlled trials under workbench conditions, ensuring that the applications can be evaluated in a repeatable and precise manner. A key aspect of the trials in the comparative analysis of custom 5G performance against commercial networks. Real-time monitoring and detailed analytics are facilitated through Grafana dashboards, offering insights into network latency, throughput, and other performance metrics during the testing process. This comprehensive setup allowed the team to identify potential bottlenecks, validate system performance, and ensure that the updates meet the application's functional requirements under real-world conditions before moving to larger-scale trials.

Table 76 and Table 77 report the test setup configuration and the test summary, respectively.

Table 76. Network setup parameters for Pre-trials 13.2.

Setup parameters	Setup ID: Lab01
Radio access technology	5G NR Standalone
Network type	Experimental
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	1W
Frequency band	LTE 2600MHz & 5G 3500MHz
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	Up to 4x4
Duplex mode	FDD

Table 77. Summary for Pre-trials 13.2.

Summary	
Trial ID	13.2
Setup ID	Lab01
Facility/Site	Athens – WINGS Lab

Objective	To test the AR/VR applications of UC13 and measure again initial KPIs
Description	Test the AR/VR applications of UC13 utilising 5G campus network
Executed by	WINGS
Components involved	AR/VR application, asset bundles loading from a server
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user), KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency), KPI#09 (Application one-way latency)
Measurement tools	Windows Task Manager, iPerf
Ethics requirements implementation	The tests have so far been performed only in the lab without involving users. In the future, a questionnaire will be submitted to participants for assessing KVI, along a release form regarding possible privacy and ethical concern.
Involvement of beta-users	N/A

For the measurements, there is a local server that is accessible by two different IPs. One IP could be pointed by the local Wi-Fi and the other by the 5G network. Latency metrics are done by pinging directly from both network types. For the network analysis, the following metrics were used: the timestamp of the request from the app to the server, the timestamp the bundle was fetched, and the size of the file that was received.

The results of the tests conducted for UC13 in WINGS premises using the 5G campus network are reported. More particularly, the total number of asset bundles tested during the experiment, to offer an overview of the scale of the testing conducted (Figure 119) the average application round-trip latency for the 3397 asset bundles measured in seconds, to provide insights into the responsiveness and efficiency of the system during testing (Figure 120), the file size per asset bundle is depicted in kilobytes, to highlight the distribution of data sizes processed during the experiment (Figure 121), the throughput achieved for the different asset bundles on the WINGS 5G campus network is shown, to demonstrate the data transmission capabilities under the test conditions (Figure 122). The devices were connected to the 5G network, and the metrics charts are visualized using Grafana providing clear and immediate insights into the performance data.

Figure 119. Total number of asset bundles tested.

Figure 120. Average application round-trip latency for the 3397 asset bundles (sec).

Figure 121. File size per asset bundle (KB).

Figure 122. Throughputs achieved for the different asset bundles on the WINGS 5G campus network.

As depicted in Table 78, the application round-trip latency with the new approach is considered sufficient to satisfy measurement requirements, contrary to the previous results in Deliverable D5.2 [2] where for KPI#08 was reported not sufficient due to the very large size of the assets to be loaded (D5.2, section 3.5).

Table 78. Measurement results for Pre-trials 13.2.

Case ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
13.2_Lab01_01	KPI#01: 50Mbps	KPI#01: up to 150 Mbps	Network capacity is sufficient to satisfy measurements requirements.
13.2_Lab01_02	KPI#08: 80-100ms	KPI#08: 100ms	Application round-trip latency is sufficient to satisfy measurement requirements.
13.2_Lab01_03	KPI#09: 50ms	KPI#09: up to 30ms	One way-latency is sufficient to satisfy measurements requirements.

Annex F - KVIs assessment questionnaires

UC10: Immersive Fan Engagement

Table 79 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC10.

Table 79. KVI questionnaire for UC10.

KVIs	Questions
<p>User Experience (At-Home / In-Venue)</p>	<p>PERCEIVED USEFULNESS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G technology helps me watch sports event at home I believe using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G network would help me be more productive I believe using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G network would be useful in my sports viewing experience I believe using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G network would improve my life <p>PERCEIVED ENJOYMENT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I know watching sports game through VR headset/device using B5G/6G network to be enjoyable Watching a sports match through VR headset/device using B5G/6G network makes me feel good Watching a sports match through VR headset/device using B5G/6G network is fun Watching a sports match through VR headset/device using B5G/6G network is engaging <p>CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> During the VR sports match, I was fully engaged During the VR sports match, I was fully involved During the VR sports match, I had full concentration
<p>Technology Acceptance</p>	<p>PERCEIVED EASE OF USE</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> This VR headset/device using B56/6G network is easy to use Learning to use this VR headset/device using B5G/6G network is easy Instructions to navigate this VR headset/device using B5G/6G network are clear and understandable I find VR with B5G/6G network flexible to interact with <p>PERCEIVED USEFULNESS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G technology helps me watch sports event at home I believe using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G network would help me be more productive I believe using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G network would be useful in my sports viewing experience I believe using VR/mobile application with B5G/6G network would improve my life

UC11: Service Robots for Enhanced Passenger's Experience

Table 80 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC11.

Table 80. KVI questionnaire for UC11.

KVIs	Questions
Trust/Trustworthiness	I feel confident that the system secures personal information, such as passenger data collected by the robots.
	The system is transparent about how it utilizes data collected from cameras, sensors, and passengers.
	I trust the system to function reliably and consistently in managing passenger flow and providing added value services.
	The system's content and information, such as alerts and guidance using humanoid robots, appear credible and accurate.
User Experience	The system is easy to navigate and find information within.
	The dashboard's interface is visually appealing and user-friendly.
	I rarely experience technical issues or bugs while using the system.
	The system provides clear instructions and guidance for using its features.
	I enjoy spending time on the system because of its intuitive design.
Acceptance/Acceptability	The system is easy to use and intuitive for completing tasks.
	The system feels welcoming and comfortable to use for extended periods.
	I feel the system meets my needs and expectations effectively.
	The system provides a smooth and enjoyable experience overall.
Digital Inclusion	I can easily use the system regardless of my technological experience.
	The system works well even with slower internet connections.
	The system's features are accessible without requiring expensive devices.
	I can understand all instructions and guidance without technical knowledge.
	The system provides adequate support when I encounter difficulties.
Resource Optimization	The system allows for optimal use of both human and robotic resources, minimizing idle time and improving operational flow.
Operational Efficiency	The system performs tasks, such as reducing waiting times and providing passenger services, quickly and efficiently.
	The insights provided by the system, such as real-time information on waiting times and queues, assist Terminal Operations Supervisors (TOS) in planning airport resources effectively.
	Employees can easily understand and act upon the insights provided by the system.

UC12: City Parks in Metaverse

Table 81 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIIs of UC12.

Table 81. KVI questionnaire for UC12.

Questionnaire	
Availability	It was easy to access the augmented reality gaming application on the tablet
	It was easy to access the virtual reality experience
	I could quickly access the information I needed *
Acceptance	It was easy to use the augmented reality gaming application on the tablet
	It was easy to use the virtual reality headset
	It was enjoyable to use the augmented reality gaming application on the tablet
	It was enjoyable to use the virtual reality headset
	It was easy to understand the contents provided for the experience *
	It was easy to move around the park during the experience *
Edutainment	The experience facilitated the learning of new contents *
	The experience was enjoyable and fun *
	The experience was engaging *
Cultural connection	The experience made me appreciate the historical-cultural context that I visited *
	I would like to repeat similar experiences to explore other historical-cultural sites *
	The experience increased my interest in the local historical-cultural heritage *
Societal sustainability	Walking during the experience made me feel good *
	Interactions with other people during the experience were pleasant *
	Undergoing the experience with other people is an added value *

* These items were also used to assess the perceived value of the control condition (guided walk in the park).

UC13 (Turin): Extended XR Museum Experience

Table 82 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIIs of UC13 (Turin).

Table 82. KVI questionnaire for UC13 (Turin).

KVIIs	Questions
Availability	Av1 - It was easy to access the augmented reality gaming application on the tablet
	Av2 - It was easy to access the virtual reality experience
	Av3 - I could quickly access the information I needed *
	Av4 - The audio/video quality of the contents provided during the visit was adequate *
	Av5 - The quality of the responses provided by the artificial intelligence during the visit was adequate

	Av6 - The duration of the visit, including augmented and virtual reality experiences, was adequate *
Acceptance	Ac7 - It was easy to use the augmented reality functionalities on the tablet
	Ac8 - It was easy to use the virtual reality headset
	Ac9 - It was enjoyable to use the augmented reality functionalities on the tablet
	Ac10 - It was enjoyable to use the virtual reality headset
	Ac11 - It was easy to understand the contents provided during the experience *
Edutainment	Ed12 - The information provided before the visit motivated me to go see the paintings
	Ed13 - The visit sparked my curiosity about the artworks and the artists *
	Ed14 - The experience facilitated the learning of new contents *
	Ed15 - The experience was enjoyable and fun *
	Ed16 - The experience was engaging *
Cultural connection	Cu17 - The experience made me appreciate the museum's artistic and cultural heritage *
	Cu18 - The experience increased my interest in the national artistic and cultural heritage *
	Cu19 - Using these technologies brought me closer to the artistic and cultural experience
	Cu20 - I would like to repeat similar experiences to discover other artworks in the museum
Economical sustainability	Es21 - I would repeat the interactive experience carried out during this visit
	Es22 - I would visit this museum again *
Inclusion	In23 - I could fully experience the activity *
	In24 - I felt comfortable during the visit *
	In25 - Everyone can participate in the visit without difficulties *
* These items were also used to assess the perceived value of the control condition (guided tour of the museum).	

UC13 (Athens): Extended XR Museum Experience

Table 83 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC13 (Athens).

Table 83. KVI questionnaire for UC13 (Athens).

KVIs	Questions
Trust/Trustworthiness	I trust the app to function reliably and consistently
	The app's content and information appear credible and accurate.
User Experience	The app is easy to navigate and find information within.
	The app's interface is visually appealing and user-friendly.
	I rarely experience technical issues or bugs while using the app.
	The app provides clear instructions and guidance for using its features.

	I enjoy spending time on the app because of its intuitive design.
Acceptance/Acceptability	The app is easy to use and intuitive for completing tasks.
	The app feels welcoming and comfortable to use for extended periods.
	The design and layout of the app make it accessible and easy to navigate.
	I feel the app meets my needs and expectations effectively.
	The app provides a smooth and enjoyable experience overall.
Digital Inclusion	I can easily use the app regardless of my technology experience.
	The app works well even with slower internet connections.
	The app's features are accessible without requiring expensive devices.
	I can understand all instructions and guidance without technical knowledge.
	The app provides adequate support when I encounter difficulties.
Edutainment	I enjoy learning while using the app.
	The educational content is engaging and interesting.
	The app makes learning fun through interactive features.
	I feel motivated to continue using the app to learn more.
	The balance between education and entertainment is appropriate.
Cultural Connection	The app content reflects the cultural diversity of the museum.
	I feel that the app acknowledges and respects my cultural background.
	The app includes content that resonates with my cultural interests and experiences.
	The app enables me to learn about the museum's context in an engaging way.
	I believe the app promotes cultural understanding and inclusivity.

Annex G - KVIs evaluation methodology for UC10

This Annex G consolidates detailed KVI evaluation methodologies, data collection procedures, and results from UC10 during the main trial phase.

A total of 41 participants took part in the trial and provided feedback (Table 84 summarizes the profiles of the respondents). Although a few originally invited participants were unable to attend, UC10 partners successfully engaged some event attendees to fill in. After each test session, participants switched scenarios and completed a short survey evaluating their user experience. Additionally, a few passersby from the general audience tried the devices; however, individuals under the age of 18 were not allowed to participate in the survey.

Table 84. Profile of respondents.

Characteristics	Frequency		Percentage %	
	At-Home (N=40)	In-Venue (N=41)	At-Home	In-Venue
Gender				
Female	16	18	40	40
Male	21	23	52.5	57.5
I prefer not to say	3		7.5	
Age				
Under 20	6	6	17.5	15
20-29	20	23	50	56
30-39	5	5	12.5	12
40-49	7	4	10	10
50 years old and above	2	3	5	7

The survey tool used was the Qualtrics Net Promoter Score (NPS) [17] and the data was analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) [18], using the model developed by UC10 partners and are detailed in the deliverable 6.2 [26] as illustrated in Figure 123.

Figure 123. UC10 structural model.

Based on the structural model (Figure 123), this approach allows us to incorporate scale items adapted from various prior studies. A five-point Likert scale was used, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Technology innovation questions were adapted from Ding & Ding (2022) [27], perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness were adapted from Ngubelanga & Duffett (2010) [28]. Perceived enjoyment from Li

& Chen (2019) [29]. Perceived enjoyment and customer Experience from McLean et al. (2018) [30]. Table 85 presents the adaptation for each scale item.

Table 85. Measurement scales.

Constructs	At-home		In-venue	
	Mean	Standard Dev	Mean	Standard Dev
Technology innovation				
1. This innovative immersive VR/ video streaming in B5G/6G experience incorporates state of the art technology	0.251	0.048	0.260	0.048
2. This innovative immersive VR/ video streaming in B5G/6G involves major technological changes on an existing product	0.229	0.055	0.348	0.049
3. The technology of innovative immersive VR/ video streaming in B5G/6G is quite new to our industry	0.327	0.044	0.189	0.069
4. The technology incorporated in the innovative immersive VR / video streaming in B5G/6G always offers dramatic improvements than that in existing product features (TV viewing).	0.415	0.061	0.428	0.072
Perceived usefulness				
1. I think using VR for viewing 360° match/ mobile for video streaming in B5G/6G will help me get more information about the sports match I'm viewing	0.402	0.028	0.451	0.051
2. I believe using VR for viewing 360° match/ mobile for video streaming in B5G/6G would help me be more productive	0.317	0.032	0.252	0.091
3. I believe using VR for viewing 360° match/ mobile for video streaming in B5G/6G would be useful in my sports viewing experience	0.390	0.040	0.455	0.078
Perceived ease of use				
1.This VR app/mobile app connected to B5G/6G is easy to use	0.274	0.054	0.249	0.056
2.Learning to use this VR app/mobile app connected to B5G/6G network is easy	0.309	0.056	0.321	0.044
3.Instructions to navigate the VR app/mobile app connected to B5G/6G network are clear and understandable	0.302	0.061	0.186	0.080
4.I find immersive experience connected to B5G/6G network flexible to interact with	0.417	0.101	0.417	0.102
Perceived enjoyment				
1. I know watching sports game through VR headset/mobile app connected to B5G/6G network to be enjoyable	0.281	0.021	0.223	0.035

2. Watching sports match through VR app/mobile app connected to B5G/6G network makes me feel good	0.339	0.027	0.301	0.033
3. Watching sports match through VR headset/mobile app connected to B5G/6G network is fun	0.260	0.021	0.335	0.028
4. Watching sports match through VR headset/mobile app connected to B5G/6G network is engaging	0.258	0.032	0.267	0.032
Customer experience				
1. During the VR sports match, I was fully engaged	0.382	0.031	0.441	0.042
2. During the VR sports match, I was fully involved	0.328	0.029	0.339	0.032
3. During the VR sports match, I had full concentration	0.361	0.020	0.318	0.035

Table 86 presents the hypothesis testing results for UC10. Path coefficients indicate the strength and direction of causal relationships between variables, while T-statistics (values > 1.96) determine whether a hypothesis is supported or rejected. P-values further assess statistical significance, with values below 0.05 indicating significance.

Table 86. Hypotheses testing.

Path	Path Coefficients	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P-Values	Results
Technology innovation > User Experience (VR)	0.750	0.070	10.651	0.000	Supported
Technology innovation > User Experience (Mobile)	0.729	0.054	13.528	0.000	Supported
Technology innovation > TAM (VR)	0.720	0.076	9.532	0.000	Supported
Technology innovation > TAM (Mobile)	0.713	0.062	11.459	0.000	Supported
TAM > Customer Experience (VR)	0.742	0.076	9.828	0.000	Supported
TAM > Customer Experience (Mobile)	0.647	0.105	6.190	0.000	Supported

The analysis (detailed in Table 6) examined how users perceive and accept technological innovations, specifically UC10 immersive fan engagement across two contexts: mobile streaming (in-venue) and virtual reality (at-home), using KVIIs such as perceived ease of use (PEU), perceived enjoyment (PE), perceived usefulness (PU), and customer experience (CEX). The composite score was calculated by obtaining the outer weights of each variable and normalizing the values to produce an absolute score of user experience (composite score) rather than a mere estimated or ranged value.